

The added value of speech technology in clinical care of patients with dysarthria

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The added value of speech technology in clinical care of patients with dysarthria

De meerwaarde van spraaktechnologie in de klinische zorg voor patiënten met dysartrie

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The human voice is the most beautiful instrument of all, but it is the most difficult to play.

Richard Strauss

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Mendoza Ramos V., Kairuz H.A., Hernandez-Diaz M.E., Martens H., Van Nuffelen G., & De Bodt M. (2020). Acoustic features to characterize sentence accent production in dysarthric speech. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, Vol 57, 101750, ISSN 1746-8094. doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2019.101750

Mendoza Ramos V., Pauly C., Van den Steen L., Hernandez-Diaz Huici M.E., De Bodt M., & Van Nuffelen G. (2021). Effect of boost articulation therapy (BArT) on intelligibility in adults with dysarthria. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*. doi: 10.1111/1460-6984.12595.

Mendoza Ramos, V., Vasquez-Correa, J. C., Cremers, R., Van Den Steen, L., Nöth, E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2021). Automatic boost articulation therapy in adults with dysarthria: Acceptability, usability and user interaction. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*. doi: 10.1111/1460-6984.12647 PMID: 34227721

Mendoza Ramos, V., Lowit, A., Van den Steen, L., Kairuz Hernandez-Diaz, H. A., Hernandez-Diaz Huici, M. E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2021). Acoustic identification of sentence accent in speakers with dysarthria: cross-population validation and severity related patterns. *Brain Sciences*, 11(10), 1344. doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11101344

Mendoza Ramos, V., Vasquez-Correa, J. C., Nöth, E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2022). Automatic score of articulatory distortion in adults with dysarthria. Submitted to *Speech Communication*.

National first author publications

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Other publications

Englert, M., **Mendoza Ramos, V.**, Behlau, M., & De Bodt, M. (2019). GALP Qualifier Scale: Initial Considerations to Classify a Voice Problem. *Folia Phoniatria et Logopaedica*, 72(5), 402-410. doi: 10.1159/000502772 (This publication has been awarded as the best *Folia Phoniatria* Student Publication)

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THESIS

AT A GLANCE

Research goal 1: to investigate the effectiveness of boost articulation therapy (BArT) on speech intelligibility in patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria and the effect of severity of dysarthria on the outcome (chapter 2)

Mendoza Ramos V., Paulyn C., Van den Steen L., Hernandez-Diaz Huici M.E., De Bodt M., & Van Nuffelen G. (2021). Effect of boost articulation therapy (BArT) on intelligibility in adults with dysarthria. International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders. doi: 10.1111/1460-6984.12595.

Objective	Method	Conclusions
<p>RQ1. Feasibility and effectiveness of intensive articulation therapy in patients with chronic dysarthria</p>	<p>Participants 17 participants with chronic or progressive dysarthria (data collected during PhD)</p> <p>Study design Two-group pre-/post-test design</p> <p>Articulation therapy - BArT - Five sessions of 45 min during 1 week - Intensive articulation therapy on the segmental level, based on the principles of motor learning - Articulation-stimuli (mono- and bisyllabic words) for articulatory training; either <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Articulatory drill (AD; n=8) ○ Minimal pairs (MP; n=9) </p> <p>Statistical analysis - Mixed-design ANOVA - Mixed-models analysis with effect sizes (Cohen's d) - Pearson correlation analysis</p> <p>Acoustic analysis Vowel centralization: FCR= $(F2u + F2a + F1u + F1i) / (F2i + F1a)$</p> <p>Outcome measurements - Perceptual measurements of speech intelligibility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NSVO (phoneme intelligibility) ○ NSVO-Z (sentence intelligibility) ○ Automatic speech ○ Reading passage ○ Spontaneous speech - Objective measurement of articulatory skills <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FCR </p> <p>Ethics permission B300201837099</p>	<p>1. BArT significantly improves speech intelligibility in patients with chronic or progressive mild to severe dysarthria</p> <p>2. Large and moderate positive effect sizes were demonstrated within specific groups of severity</p> <p>3. Acoustic analysis revealed a reduction in formant centralization ratio</p>

Research goal 2: to evaluate the feasibility (design and development) of a new Virtual Articulation Therapist (VAT) that supports intensive articulation training of patients with dysarthria and to validate the system by end-users (chapter 3 and chapter 4)

Mendoza Ramos, V., Vasquez-Correa, J. C., Cremers, R., Van Den Steen, L., Nöth, E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2021). Automatic boost articulation therapy in adults with dysarthria: Acceptability, usability and user interaction. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*. doi: 10.1111/1460-6984.12647 PMID: 34227721

Mendoza Ramos, V., Vasquez-Correa, J. C., Nöth, E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2022). Automatic score of articulatory distortion in adults with dysarthria. *Submitted to Speech Communication*

Objective	Method	Conclusions
RQ2. Modifications in existing algorithms necessary for precise and reliable phonological error detection in Dutch patients with dysarthria	<p>Speech samples Healthy speech from the read speech part of the Corpus Spoken Dutch (Oostdijk and Broeder 2003)</p> <p>Design - Algorithm selection (state-of-the-art neural network), modifications, training and validation - Training the models with healthy speech and using Dutch language-specific phonological features for phonological error detection</p> <p>Statistical analysis Evaluation metrics: accuracy of training and validation sets, precision, recall and F-score of the models' performance.</p>	1. High accuracy of the models' performance for phonological error detection contributes to adequate automatic feedback
RQ3. The feasibility of a VAT system and the acceptability, usability and interaction of end-users with it	<p>Participants 14 participants with dysarthria</p> <p>Design - Speech algorithm: design and development - Survey: quantitative research strategy</p> <p>Articulation Therapy - Virtual - Newly designed and developed software to provide articulation therapy - Including an extensive and well-structured package of exercises - Visual and auditory modelling - Tailored user interface appropriate for patients with brain damage - Adequate feedback on utterance performance</p>	1. Initial implementation of a computer-based articulation therapy shows it to be feasible and well accepted by end-users

- Two VAT sessions

Statistical analysis

Pearson correlations analysis between different outcome variables

Outcome measurements

Quantitative evaluation of the acceptability, usability and user interaction with the VAT through a self-designed questionnaire

Ethics permission

B300201837099

Objective	Method	Conclusions
RQ4. Development of a model to objectively estimate the degree of phoneme distortion in subjects with dysarthria	<p><i>Participants & speech samples</i> 35 participants with chronic or progressive dysarthria: 12414-word samples</p> <p><i>Design</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Perceptual evaluation and annotation of articulation errors and degree of distortion- Training and validation of phoneme-dependent regression models and phoneme-independent classification models with dysarthric speech <p><i>Acoustic analysis</i> Objective measure of the degree of phoneme distortion, based on phonological log-likelihood ratio (PLLR) features.</p> <p><i>Statistical analysis</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Evaluation: five-fold cross-validation method- Performance measures:<ul style="list-style-type: none">o RMSE and the R-Squared metrics for regression modelso Accuracy and total misclassification error rate metrics for classification models <p><i>Ethics permission</i> B300201837099</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Initial implementation of objective estimation of the degree of phoneme distortion in dysarthric speech2. The prediction model is reliable in the classification of phoneme distortion and shows an overall accuracy of 73.5%3. The objective score can contribute to the automatic feedback during speech training

Research goal 3: to identify relevant acoustic features that enable classification and objective characterization of sentence accent production for dysarthric speakers of Dutch, and to validate the methodology across different speaker populations varying in the type and severity of their speech disorders and spoken language (chapter 5 and chapter 6)

Mendoza Ramos V., Kairuz H.A., Hernandez-Diaz M.E., Martens H., Van Nuffelen G., & De Bodt M. (2020). Acoustic features to characterize sentence accent production in dysarthric speech. Biomedical Signal Processing and Control, Vol 57, 101750, ISSN 1746-8094. doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2019.101750

Mendoza Ramos, V., Lowit, A., Van den Steen, L., Kairuz Hernandez-Diaz, H. A., Hernandez-Diaz Huici, M. E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2021). Acoustic identification of sentence accent in speakers with dysarthria: cross-population validation and severity related patterns. Brain Sciences, 11(10), 1344. doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11101344

Objective	Method	Conclusions
RQ5. Acoustic features to characterize sentence accent in patients with dysarthria	<p>Speech samples CATRIS corpus (Dutch speakers)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 30 control participants ○ 50 participants with dysarthria <p>Material Sentences with a varying focus position</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 180 from control participants ○ 300 from participants with dysarthria <p>Design - Automatic algorithm design and development for sentence accent detection - Perceptual evaluation of the accented syllables per utterance</p> <p>Statistical analysis Linear discriminant analysis for data reduction and automatic classification</p> <p>Acoustic analysis - Objective measures of syllabic parameters: twenty relative values of fundamental frequency (F0), intensity (I), and duration (D) within the syllable, in contrast with the previous syllable and in contrast with the entire sentence.</p> <p>Outcome measurements Relevant acoustic features for accent detection</p>	<p>1. A limited set of acoustic features to characterize the sentence accent, related to F0, intensity, and duration, could be identified</p> <p>2. The acoustic features are reliable in the classification of sentence accents in speakers of Dutch</p> <p>3. This study adds to a better understanding and description of different accent strategies in healthy speakers and speakers with dysarthria</p>

Objective	Method	Conclusions
RQ6. Cross population validation of the acoustic features (from RQ5) and objective characterization of accent production strategies at different dysarthria severity levels	<p>Speech samples</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dutch speakers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 30 control participants o 50 participants with dysarthria - English speakers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 8 participants with dysarthria <p>Material</p> <p>Sentences with a varying focus position</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 180 from control participants (Dutch) o 300 from participants with dysarthria (Dutch) o 240 from participants with dysarthria (English) <p>Design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - External validity of acoustic features that correlate with sentence accent - Perceptual evaluation of the accented syllables per utterance <p>Statistical analysis</p> <p>Discriminant analysis to identify the contribution of each acoustic feature to accent production, analyzing each severity level independently.</p> <p>Acoustic analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ten relevant values of F0, I, and D within the syllable, in contrast with the previous syllable and in contrast with the entire sentence. <p>Outcome measurements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linear discriminant equation for accent classification (un/accented syllables) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The set of acoustic descriptors is validated in a different population 2. Accurate identification of 82.8% (for Dutch) and 91.9% (for English) of the accented target syllables 3. Different strategies for accent production across dysarthria severity levels are demonstrated

PART 1

PREFACE

CHAPTER 1

General introduction

Speech production

Speech is one of the more unique forms of human communication, but it is also the most complex of naturally acquired motor skills. In normal adults, this activity is characterized by the production of around 14 sounds (phonemes) per second through the coordinated and precise movements of approximately 100 muscles innervated by multiple cranial and spinal nerves (Duffy, 2000). As a highly complex motor activity, speech production requires accuracy and speed, uses knowledge of results, is improved by practice, demonstrates motor flexibility in achieving goals, and relegates all of this to automatic control (McNeil, 2009; Netsell, 1982). Spoken language production involves the integration of neurocognitive, neuromotor, neuromuscular and musculoskeletal activities, which are divided into three main processes: (1) the cognitive-linguistic process, (2) the motor speech planning, programming and control processes, and (3) the neuromuscular execution process (Weismer, 2007; Van Der Merwe, 2009, 2021; Duffy, 2020).

The cognitive-linguistic level is a nonmotor (or premotor) speech process responsible for the conceptualization and planning of the semantic, syntactic, lexical, morphological and phonological linguistic levels of an utterance. When a person intends to communicate verbally, thoughts or emotions need to be transformed into a sequence of linguistic units that stand by the rules of a language. The selection of the correct phonemes, words, or intonation patterns are combined activities within the cognitive-linguistic process. Subsequently, the motor processes underlying speech production take place. During the next stage (planning, programming and control), the intended message must be prepared for neuromuscular execution, after which sensorimotor programs that activate speech muscles at suitable times, durations and intensities are composed. Finally, the neuromuscular execution occurs; at this phase, central and peripheral nervous system events must accurately combine to execute speech motor programs by activating different respiratory, phonatory, resonatory and articulatory muscles in order to generate the acoustic signal (Duffy, 2020). The relationship among the major divisions, primary structures and pathways of the speech motor system are illustrated in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. Major divisions of the speech motor system. Adapted from Duffy (2020).
 UMN: upper motor neuron; LMN: lower motor neuron

The motor speech process requires precise, synchronous and timely coordination of all the subsystems of speech (respiratory, phonatory, resonatory and articulatory). Unfortunately, a lesion in one or more of those structures may lead to disordered speech production, affecting speech intelligibility -the degree to which a listener understands the auditory signal produced by a speaker (Duffy, 2020)-.

Among the essential components of speech production (respiration, phonation, resonance, articulation and prosody), this research will focus on two important dimensions with a high impact on intelligibility: articulation and prosody.

Articulation

Articulation refers to the production of specific and distinguishable speech sounds that, when combined, give speech its meaning. This is primarily a function of lingual, facial, and jaw muscle activity, although laryngeal and velopharyngeal movements also contribute, producing many of the distinctive features among speech sounds (phonemes) (Duffy, 2000). The production of clearly pronounced, well-inflected speech requires precise control over the articulators; any disturbance of the neuromuscular mechanisms responsible for manipulating the articulators will lead to the production of acoustically distorted speech that is unintelligible

to listeners (Enderby, 1980). Consonants and vowels are the two main categories of speech sounds.

Consonants

Consonants are speech sounds produced by restricting or blocking the airflow through the vocal tract (Figure 1.2) and may be produced with or without vocal fold vibration. There are commonly three articulatory feature dimensions in which to describe consonants: place of articulation, manner of articulation and voicing (Ohde & Sharf, 1992).

Figure 1.2. The vocal tract

Place of articulation: is concerned with the vocal tract location of the sound articulation, where the airflow restriction or blockage during the production of sounds is made. Figure 1.3 shows the articulators involved in speech, and Table 1.1 summarizes the places of articulation for consonants.

Figure 1.3. Places of articulation

Table 1.1. Consonant places of articulation

Place of articulation	Position of the articulators
Bilabial	Both lips come together.
Labiodental	The lower lip contacts the upper front teeth.
Dental	The tongue tip contacts the upper front teeth.
Alveolar	The tongue tip or tongue blade (the part just behind the tip) contacts the alveolar ridge (the gums just behind the teeth).
Postalveolar	The tongue blade or tongue tip contacts the postalveolar region behind the alveolar ridge.
Retroflex	The sound is produced by curling the tongue tip backwards behind the alveolar ridge.
Palatal	The front of the tongue approaches or contacts the hard palate.
Velar	The back of the tongue contacts the soft palate (or velum).
Uvular	The back of the tongue contacts the uvula.
Pharyngeal	The root of the tongue contacts the pharynx.
Glottal	The sound is articulated in the larynx, at the glottis, by approximating the vocal folds for a glottal fricative or closing them for a glottal stop.

Manner of articulation: is concerned with the nature of the interference with the airflow through the vocal tract during the production of speech sounds. Based on the vocal tract constriction, the consonants can be divided into two different categories (Table 1.2), and Table 1.3 summarizes the possible manners of consonants articulation.

Table 1.2. Consonant categories based on the vocal tract constriction

Category	Description
Obstruent	A sound made with a complete closure or narrow constriction in the oral cavity, so that airflow is stopped, or frication noise is produced. It includes stops, fricatives, affricates, and trills.
Sonorant	A sound made with a relatively open vocal tract, so that cavity resonance occurs. It includes nasals, glides, and liquids.

Table 1.3. Consonant manners of articulation

Manner of articulation	Description
Stops (Plosives)	They are produced by blocking the airflow through the vocal tract so as to increase air pressure, immediately followed by a release of the air pressure. The point of occlusion of the vocal tract can be any of the points of articulation described earlier.
Nasals	They are produced by closing off the oral cavity at some point and opening the velopharyngeal port so that air flows out through the nasal cavity, resulting in a nasal resonance.
Trills	They are produced by rapid and repetitive contacts or vibration of an articulator, such as the tongue tip or the uvula, caused by an appropriate adjustment of muscle tension and air pressure buildup.
Taps (Flaps)	They are produced as a single rapid contact between the articulators, very briefly interrupting voicing (i.e. like one movement of a trill).
Fricatives	They are produced by restricting the airflow through the vocal tract to produce frication noise. The constriction point can occur at any of the articulation points described earlier.
Affricates	They are produced by releasing a stop into a fricative, usually within the same syllable.
Approximants	Sounds made by approximating two articulators, but not as close as for fricatives (used to describe glides and liquids).
Lateral approximants	They are produced at any point in the vocal tract where the tongue can make a central obstruction to the airflow.
Glides	They are produced by shifting from one vowel to another within the same syllable. Postvocalic glides are called diphthongs and fall into the vowel category. Prevoalcalic glides are called glide consonants, they are the starting points for the transition to following vowels within the same syllable.
Liquids	They are vowel-like sounds. They are produced with the vocal cavity slightly constricted. They are the starting points for the transition to following vowels within the same syllable.

Voicing: refers to the vibration of the vocal folds which are located in the larynx.

The vocal folds vibration classifies the consonants as either voiced (produced with vocal fold vibration) or unvoiced (without vocal fold vibration).

For the production of voiced sounds, a simplified representation is shown in Figure 1.4a. The vocal folds come together in light contact and vibrate at high speed along their entire length, modulating the airflow coming from the lungs through the glottis and producing sound (voice), which propagates through the vocal tract where it is selectively amplified or attenuated at different frequencies (Collins & Mees, 2003; Zhang, 2016).

For the production of unvoiced sounds, a simplified representation is shown in Figure 1.4b. The vocal folds are kept separated, similarly to the state of the larynx for normal breathing. The airflow coming from the lungs passes through the glottis without blockage to the vocal tract (Collins & Mees, 2003).

Figure 1.4. a. Larynx setting for voiced sounds, b. Larynx setting for unvoiced sounds

The IPA chart (Figure 1.5) gives an overview of the consonants for all possible languages. In addition, place and manner of articulation, as well as voicing characteristics, are indicated.

THE INTERNATIONAL PHONETIC ALPHABET (revised to 2020)

CONSONANTS (PULMONIC) © 2020 IPA

	Bilabial	Labiodental	Dental	Alveolar	Postalveolar	Retroflex	Palatal	Velar	Uvular	Pharyngeal	Glottal
Plosive	p b			t d		ʈ ɖ	c ɟ	k ɡ	q ɢ		ʔ
Nasal	m	ɱ		n		ɳ	ɲ	ŋ	ɴ		
Trill	ʙ			r					ʀ		
Tap or Flap				ɾ		ɽ					
Fricative	ɸ β	f v	θ ð	s z	ʃ ʒ	ʂ ʐ	ç ʝ	x ɣ	χ ʁ	ħ ʕ	h ɦ
Lateral fricative				ɬ ɮ							
Approximant		ʋ		ɹ		ɻ	j	ɰ			
Lateral approximant				l		ɭ	ʎ	ʟ			

Symbols to the right in a cell are voiced, to the left are voiceless. Shaded areas denote articulations judged impossible.

Figure 1.5: IPA chart for consonants

Vowels

Vowels are speech sounds produced with relatively open vocal tract resonance, always produced with vocal fold vibration and function as the nucleus of a syllable. They can be classified as either monophthongs (one vowel sound) or diphthongs (gliding of two vowel sounds together) (Ohde & Sharf, 1992). It is appropriate to describe vowels by the horizontal and vertical position of the highest point of the tongue (the dorsum), as well as the roundness of the lips and the tension in the tongue muscles; this is explained in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4. Dimensions of vowel articulation

Tongue shape	Description
High (Close)	A vowel made with the tongue raised toward the palate.
Mid	A vowel made with the tongue midway between the palate and the floor of the oral cavity.
Low (Open)	A vowel made with the tongue lowered toward the oral cavity floor.
Front	A vowel made with the tongue advanced toward the front of the oral cavity.
Central	A vowel made with the tongue positioned midway between the most forward and retracted vowel positions.
Back	A vowel made with the tongue retracted toward the back of the oral cavity.

Lips shape	Description
Rounded	Describes sounds made with a narrowing of the lip opening.
Unrounded	Describes sounds made with the lips with a relatively long horizontal opening.

Tongue tension	Description
Tense	A vowel made with the tongue muscles relatively tense.
Lax	A vowel made with reduced tension in the tongue muscles.

The IPA chart (Figure 1.6) gives an overview of the existing vowels, height and place, as well as rounding characteristics are indicated.

Figure 1.6: IPA chart for vowels

Prosody

Prosody refers to variations in pitch, loudness, and duration across syllables that help convey stress, emphasis, and emotion (Duffy, 2000)—defined as the suprasegmental properties of a language, such as intonation, tempo, stress, juncture, and rhythm (Lehiste, 1970), aspects of speech production that exceed the limits of the individual phonemes (Ohde & Sharf, 1992). Prosody reflects the combined activities of respiration, phonation, resonance, and articulation (Duffy, 2000).

The perceptual attributes of prosody can be quantified in terms of its correlated acoustic cues: fundamental frequency (F0), intensity, and duration (physical parameters) (Bolinger, 1961, 1989; Lieberman, 1967; Patel, 2011).

- The fundamental frequency (F0) is the acoustic correlate of the pitch. F0 is the rate at which a waveform is repeated per unit time. It is measured in hertz (Hz) or cycles per second (cps) (1Hz=1cps). Normative data demonstrated variations of mean F0 according to age, gender, and phonatory tasks performed. It is established that, on average, F0 for women is 225 Hz, for men, 128 Hz and for children, 265 Hz (Baken & Orlikoff, 2000; Mathieson, 2000, De Bodt et al., 2015).
- Intensity (I) or amplitude is the acoustic correlate of loudness. Intensity is the description of power per unit area. It is measured in decibels (dB). Normal voice intensity can reach 80-100dB on average (Baken & Orlikoff, 2000; Mathieson, 2000).
- Duration refers to the time length of sounds, syllables, phrases or silences. It is measured in seconds (s).

Speech disorders

A person's ability to speak naturally can be affected in different ways and by a variety of sources. Motor speech disorders are an important group, resulting from neurologic conditions, congenital or acquired, that affect the motor programming or neuromuscular execution of speech production (Duffy, 2020). This group includes apraxia of speech and dysarthria, the latter being the focus of our research.

Dysarthria

Dysarthria refers to a group of neurogenic motor speech disorders caused by impaired muscular control due to damage to the central or peripheral nervous system (Darley, Aronson & Brown, 1969a, 1969b, 1975). The induced muscle weakness, altered muscle tone and the slowing, incoordination, and inaccuracy of movements of structures involved in speech production may affect the different dimensions of speech, namely respiration, phonation, resonance, articulation, and prosody. Consequently, dysarthria affects both the segmental (i.e., individual sounds, i.e., vowels and consonants) and suprasegmental (superimposed to syllables, words, or phrases, i.e., intonation, stress, rhythm, etc.) speech characteristics (Miller, 1978; Palmer, Enderby & Hawley, 2007).

Based on the localization of the lesion in the central or peripheral nervous system, the different auditory perceptual speech characteristics and the different underlying neuromuscular dysfunctions, seven subtypes of dysarthria have been identified: flaccid, spastic, ataxic, hypokinetic, hyperkinetic, unilateral upper motor neuron (UUMN), and mixed (Darley, Aronson & Brown, 1969a, 1969b, 1975; Duffy & Folger, 1996; Duffy, 2020). Table 1.5 summarizes the more deviant speech characteristics of each type.

Dysarthria leads to reductions in intelligibility, efficiency and naturalness of speech (Mackenzie & Lowit, 2007). Subsequently, dysarthria has a significant psychosocial impact, affecting patients' participation in daily life and overall quality of life (Dykstra, Hakel & Adams, 2007; Dickson et al., 2008). The incidence and prevalence of dysarthria are not precisely known (Kent, 2004). However, it is present in many neurological pathologies, and it represents a significant portion of all acquired neurological disorders. For example, studies indicate that between 50% and 90% of people with advanced Parkinson's disease (Pinto et al., 2004), 20% who have had a stroke (Enderby & Phillips, 1986), 90% of people with moderately advanced amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) (Campbell & Enderby, 1984), and 40% of those with cerebral palsy (Pennington, Miller & Robson, 2009) will have an associated speech

disorder, which is generally dysarthria. In Belgium, the number of speech disorders in stroke (including dysarthria) is estimated at 60 % (Devroey, Van Casteren & Buntinx, 2003). The severity of dysarthria varies from mild over moderate to severe, independently of the type or localization of the lesion.

Table 1.5. Classification of dysarthria

Type of Dysarthria	Localization	Distinctive neurologic deficit	Phonation/Respiration	Resonance	Articulation	Prosody
Flaccid	LMN (cranial and spinal nerves)	weakness	stridor/ audible inspiration* breathy (continuous)* harsh (or hoarse)	hypernasality* nasal emission*	imprecise consonants	short phrases* monopitch, monoloudness
Spastic	UMN (bilateral)	spasticity	strained-strangled phonation*, low pitch*, harsh, pitch breaks, breathy (continuous)	hypernasality	imprecise consonants distorted vowels	slow rate*, short phrases, monopitch, monoloudness, reduced stress, excess & equal stress
Ataxic	Cerebellum (cerebellar control circuit)	incoordination	voice tremor harsh		irregular articulatory breakdowns* distorted vowels * prolonged phonemes* imprecise consonants	excess & equal stress*, excess loudness variations*, prolonged intervals, monopitch, monoloudness, slow rate
Hypokinetic	basal ganglia control circuit	rigidity, reduced range of movement	harsh low pitch breathy (continuous)		repeated phonemes* imprecise consonants	monopitch*, monoloudness*, reduced stress*, variable rate*, short rushes of speech*, inappropriate silences*, increased rate in segments*, increased of rate overall*

Hyperkinetic	basal ganglia control circuit	involuntary movements	voice stoppages* voice tremor* strained-strangled phonation* harsh* audible inspiration*	hypernasality	imprecise consonants distorted vowels* irregular articulatory breakdowns* prolonged phonemes*	inappropriate silences*, excess loudness variations*, alternating loudness*, prolonged intervals*, variable rate*, excess & equal stress, monopitch, monoloudness, short phrases, reduced stress
UUMN	UMN (unilateral)	weakness, (?) incoordination, (?) spasticity	strained- harsh, breathy reduced loudness		imprecise articulation irregular articulatory breakdowns	slow rate
Mixed	two or more of the localizations listed above			combinations of the above deviant speech characteristic		

*more distinctive or more severely disturbed than in other dysarthria types; UUMN: unilateral upper motor neuron; LMN: lower motor neurons

Articulation in dysarthria

Impaired speech sound articulation is a representative feature of dysarthria in general. From a perceptual perspective, imprecise consonants, distorted vowels and irregular articulatory breakdown -an unsystematic breakdown in the accuracy of speech sound production- are prominent features reported in nearly all types of dysarthria (Darley et al., 1969a; Tjaden, 2007; Duffy, 2020).

Dysarthria can affect the attributes of articulatory movements, which may alter or change the identity of phonemes. This will have acoustic consequences linked to a reduction in speech intelligibility (Tjaden, 2007). Therefore, understanding the nature of speech sound articulation (segmental articulatory behaviour) is essential for a further customized and more individualized treatment of articulation, addressing the specific areas of need for each patient.

The articulatory complexity of individual sounds is defined based on the motor adjustments necessary to achieve vowels and consonants accurately (Kent, 1992a). According to Kent's analyses of speech sounds and underlying motor movements, it seems that sounds acquired early in life (e.g. a, m) demand simpler and less refined motor adjustments, coordination and articulatory skills than later acquired sounds (e.g. v, z). Following those principles, consonants and vowels have been assigned into different phonetic complexity levels (Table 1.6) (Kent, 1992a; Allison & Hustad, 2014; Kim et al., 2010).

Table 1.6. Complexity levels of vowels and consonants as proposed by R. D. Kent (1992a).

Complexity level ^a	Phonemes	Underlying motor adjustments
Vowels		
1	/ɑ, ə/	Primarily anterior to posterior (front to back) tongue movements and slight elevation from a low carriage.
2	/u, i, o/	Maximally dissimilar vowels (acoustically and articulatory), defining vowel production boundaries (vowel triangle).
3	/ε, ɔ, ai, au, əɪ/	Quadrilateral vowel space appearance (control of /ε/); differentiation of similar sounds (/ɑ, ɔ/); precision of tongue gliding movements for diphthongs.
4	/ɪ, e, æ, ʊ/	Suitable adjustments and coordination of tongue and jaw articulation.

5	/ʒ, ʒ/	Tongue retroflexion.
Consonants		
3	/p, m, n, w, h/	Regulation of rapid vs slow (constant velocity over relatively long duration) articulatory movements (/p, m, n/; /w, h/); velopharyngeal valving (stops and nasals); voicing adjustments; primary places of articulation: bilabial, alveolar, and glottal.
4	/b, d, k, g, j, f/	Additional items with rapid (/b, d, k, g/) and slow (/j/) movements; Regulation of fine force for frication (/f/); additional place of articulation (velar).
5	/t, ŋ, r, l/	Additional items with rapid movements (/t, ŋ/); tongue configuration (bending) for /r, l/
6	/s, z, ʃ, v, θ, ð, tʃ, dʒ/	Tongue placement and fine force regulation for dental, alveolar, and palatal fricatives.
7	consonant clusters	Fine motor control for quickly and efficiently transitioning between articulatory placements

^a Based on the age of acquisition, the complexity level begins at 1 for vowels and 3 for consonants.

The articulatory complexity of speech sounds was found to be directly related to articulation errors (or misarticulation) in adults with dysarthria and consequently with a negative impact on speech intelligibility (Kim et al., 2010; Kuruvilla-Dugdale et al., 2018). Misarticulation is defined as errors in speech production resulting in the substitution, omission, distortion, or addition of sounds or the deletion of syllables (Ohde & Sharf, 1992).

- Omission: the deletion of a phoneme from a word. Other types of deletion are syllable reduction, cluster reduction, final consonant deletion, and stridency deletion.
- Addition: the insertion of an additional phoneme in a word.
- Substitution: the replacement of one phoneme by another in a word. This can be caused by place substitutions (frontal lisp, gliding, palatalization, depalatalization, fronting dentalizing, among others), manner substitutions (stopping, affrication, deaffrication) and voicing substitutions (prevocalic consonant voicing, final postvocalic consonant devoicing).
- Distortions: a variation of a target sound that is not allophonic but does not fall into another phoneme category (including lispings, nasalization, denasalization, and vowel

lengthening, among others). Most dysarthric articulation errors are distortions (Yorkston & Beukelman, 1980; Tjaden, 2007; Kirshner, 2021).

Assessment of articulation in dysarthria (perceptual and objective)

In general, the goals of articulatory assessment are to determine the nature and degree of the articulation error and to define the implications of these errors for subsequent therapy (Ohde & Sharf, 1992). Typical errors in speech sound production are consonant and vowel distortions, omissions, additions and substitutions, being the distortion of consonant sounds, the most consistent finding in dysarthria (Yorkston & Beukelman, 1980; Tjaden, 2007; Kirshner, 2021).

Auditory-perceptual judgment is the primary and gold standard tool used by speech-language pathologists (SLPs) to gather information about speech sound production characteristics (Kent, 1996; Tjaden, 2007; Forrest & Weismer, 2009). These methods include broad and narrow phonetic transcription and scaling or rating of perceptual labels such as distorted vowels, imprecise consonants or irregular articulatory breakdowns (Tjaden, 2007). However, the subjective nature of perceptual analysis may limit the validity and reliability of these measurements (Kreiman & Gerratt, 1998). Furthermore, auditory-perceptual judgments are susceptible to a variety of sources of error (for instance: auditory illusions, particularly phonemic restoration and verbal transformation, misperceptions, false phonemic evaluation) and bias (for instance, visual information can override or complement auditory information; diagnostic information can have an effect on examiner expectancy) (Kent, 1996; Eadie et al., 2011). Additionally, auditory-perceptual judgments can be time-consuming and very laborious. Also, reliability and sensitivity of perceptual evaluations of speech disturbance have been partly questioned in some studies due to controversial results of inter- or intra- rater agreement/ reliability (Bunton et al., 2007).

Instrumental methods to assess articulation may be particularly attractive. They have contributed significantly to the description and understanding of some underlying mechanisms of speech sound production. Among the instrumental techniques applied to the analysis of articulation, we have electromyography, kinematics (electromagnetic articulograph, x-ray microbeam, optotrak), imaging (ultrasound, MRI), electropalatography and aerodynamics. However, these techniques are not often used in clinical practice (Duffy, 2020). One of the most advantageous instrumental methods applied for the objective assessment of articulation is **acoustic analysis**. It is entirely non-invasive and provides objective and quantitative measures of components of the speech signal. Acoustic measures for the assessment and

characterization of articulation include vowel formant frequencies (F1, F2, F3) absolute and difference values, area of vowel triangle or quadrilateral, formant frequency fluctuation, formant transition characteristics (slope and extend) for consonant-vowel (CV) and vowel-consonant (VC) transitions, spectral moment coefficients for obstruent consonants and amplitude of energy during stop gaps, voice onset time, amplitude of first harmonic (H1) during fricative segments, durations of syllables and intersyllable pauses, sound segment duration, among others (Kent et al., 1999; Kim, Kent & Weismer, 2011; Kim, 2017). These measures can be compared with the acoustic data of neurologically normal speech, from which there is extensive literature and normative data available.

Consonants are a complex category of sounds; therefore, there is no single measure that can be applied across the entire category. Consequently, developing an acoustic measure of consonant distortion that can be applied to dysarthric speech is one of the main goals of this research work.

Treatment of articulation in dysarthria (conventional therapy and new e-approaches)

Impaired speech articulation contributes to reduced intelligibility (De Bodt et al., 2002; Tjaden, 2007). Therefore, behavioural interventions to improve articulation and consequently speech intelligibility are necessary for individuals with dysarthria. Behavioural treatments of speech can focus on improving or restoring impaired function (direct therapy) or on developing compensations that make use of residual physiologic support (indirect therapy) (Duffy, 2020). Both therapy approaches aim to improve intelligibility, efficiency and naturalness of speech, and they also require effort and motor learning. However, compensation is usually achieved faster. Therefore, this treatment strategy is preferable and more often selected by SLPs (Duffy, 2020).

Behavioural treatment of articulation may include strength exercises, stretching, relaxation, biofeedback (e.g., EMG or EPG), phonetic placement (e.g., hands-on, descriptive or pictures to work on the positioning of the mouth, tongue, lips, or jaw during speech), phonetic derivation (nonspeech to speech tasks such as blowing to facilitate the production of /u/), minimal contrasts to achieve control over consonants, clear speech (exaggerated articulation or over articulation to emphasize phonetic placement and increase precision), rate modifications to facilitate articulatory precision, among other techniques (Rosenbek & LaPointe, 1985; Duffy, 2020). Behavioural treatment of articulation mainly involves indirect strategies (e.g. rate

modifications), which have shown positive effects on speech intelligibility. However, the evidence on the short-term effects of direct articulation therapy at the segmental level of speech (e.g. minimal contrasts) is relatively sparse. Therefore, another aim of this research is to investigate the effectiveness of direct, boost articulation therapy (BArT) on speech intelligibility in patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria and the effect of severity of dysarthria on the outcome. This approach intends to reduce the impairment instead of compensating it, contributing to exploiting and developing all available residual motor skills.

Other important aspects to consider in the articulation treatments are the frequency, intensity, and duration of the interventions, which may vary depending on the type and severity of the dysarthria, motivation of the person, among others. However, most people with dysarthria can benefit from frequent and intense practice consistent with the principles of motor learning (PML) for the enhancement, retention and generalization of speech motor skills (Bislick et al., 2012; Kleim & Jones, 2008; Maas et al., 2008). Motor learning has been classically defined as a set of processes associated with practice or experience leading to relatively permanent changes in the capability for movement (Schmidt et al., 2018). The PML are related to optimal conditions of practice (amount, distribution, variability, schedule, attentional focus and target complexity) and feedback (types, frequency, and timing), leading to positive outcomes in the process of (re)learning speech movements or motor skills, which is the case of patients with dysarthria (Bislick et al., 2012). Therefore, the content of the speech articulation therapy programs must meet the PML.

Nowadays, there is growing evidence indicating that computer-based interventions may be effective and beneficial for individuals with dysarthria (Palmer et al., 2007; Ritterfeld et al., 2016; Bakker, Beijer & Rietveld, 2019), who can benefit from a more natural treatment environment, the reduction of fatiguing and time-consuming transfers to the SLP or rehabilitation centre and to practice more intensively and frequently for better outcomes. A recent study showed that there is also a considerable increase in the use of technology-assisted speech therapy for the management of adults with dysarthria (Kuschmann et al., 2021). This is in line with the general technological advances of recent years and the increasing interest of patients and clinicians (Kuschmann et al., 2021). However, the majority of automated speech therapy tools are generic to speech sound disorders in general, and only a few attempts have been made for patients with dysarthria (Deka et al., 2022). Although, most of the studies proposed fully automated therapy tools (mobile-based and computer-based) (Deka et al., 2022). Regarding the effectiveness of these tools, only a few studies have compared the performance

of the automated system with expert SLPs evaluations. They generally found a good agreement between automated responses and subjective evaluations; however, the need of comparing the accuracy of these systems with human performance is emphasized (Deka et al., 2022).

To our knowledge, there is no publicly available computerized therapy system, specific for articulation training of Dutch (Flemish) speaking subjects with dysarthria. There is still the need for a supplementary technology-based intervention that can mimic a face-to-face therapy session. A virtual therapist should optimally act like a real SLP and guide the patient through an intensive treatment program with precise feedback, for improving articulation deficit and, consequently, speech intelligibility. A search on international literature and websites of research centres in the field did not reveal a similarly conceptualized program. Also, the robustness of the existing algorithms that calculate outcome measures for detailed feedback needs further improvements (Bakker et al., 2019). This leads to another aim of this research, namely, to evaluate the feasibility (design and development) of a Virtual Articulation Therapist (VAT).

Prosody in dysarthria

Dysprosody is a perceptual hallmark of dysarthria (Darley et al., 1969, 1975; Patel, 2011; Duffy, 2020). From a perceptual perspective, common manifestations of prosodic disturbances in dysarthria include slowed or accelerated rate, monopitch and monoloudness, rhythmic disturbances and reduced ability to vary stress and accent (Peppé, 2009; Darley et al., 1969, 1975; Duffy, 2020; Kent & Rosenbek, 1982; Rosenbek & LaPointe, 1985; Yorkston et al., 1984; Lowit et al., 2010, 2014), which can also lead to reductions in speech intelligibility (De Bodt et al., 2002).

When a person wants to indicate focus or emphasis in an utterance highlighting the essential information (word or a word-group), this person is using one of the communicative functions of prosody (Peppé, 2009). Individuals with dysarthria often use this when repeating an utterance that the listeners did not completely understand the first time (Van Nuffelen, 2011). Adequate accent placement for highlighting important information in an utterance is essential for the efficient conveyance of meaning (Cutler et al., 1997). In patients with dysarthria, accent production is often achieved with pitch movement and by lengthening and increasing loudness in the target word (Patel & Campellone, 2009; Lowit et al., 2010, 2014). The combination of these strategies might vary for different severities and types of dysarthria. However, the topic requires further investigation, and this thesis will partially address it.

Assessment of prosody in dysarthria (perceptual (shortcomings) and objective analysis)

In general, the assessment of prosodic deficits is essential for diagnosing and determining the needs and priority of the treatment of speech disorders in dysarthria.

Auditory-perceptual judgments of prosody are considered the gold standard (Patel, 2011; Duffy, 2020). There are commonly three ways of perceptual assessment, an overall judgement of prosodic features, transcriptions and assessment of communicative functions of prosody (Van Nuffelen, 2011). However, perceptual judgments remain subjective by nature, affecting the validity and reliability of these measurements (Kent, 1996).

Acoustic analysis is a powerful tool for improving the precision of the diagnoses, offering objective measures. Prosodic disturbances are frequently assessed in terms of fundamental frequency or F0 (mean, peak, range, variance, slope), intensity (mean, peak, range) and duration (vowel, syllable word, silence) (Patel, 2011). Special attention is required for impaired speech; there are challenges using these acoustics analyses, especially tracking F0 due to inherent voice problems, elevated levels of glottal noise and cycle-to-cycle aperiodicity, abnormal resonance, extensive pitch variations and pitch breaks (Patel, 2011; Hlavnička et al., 2019). Consequently, qualitative analysis through auditory and visual inspection remains important (Liss & Weismer, 1992).

Obviously, acoustic analysis has a significant impact on quantifying prosodic aspects and outcome measurements. Therefore, methods to automate prosodic analysis are particularly appealing (DiCicco, 2009; DiCicco & Patel, 2008; van Santen et al., 2009). The final aim of this research is to identify relevant acoustic features that enable the classification of sentence accent production for dysarthric speakers of Dutch, to characterize sentence accent production in that group objectively, and to validate the methodology across different speaker populations varying in the type and severity of their speech disorders and spoken language.

Currently, there is general agreement in the literature that syllable duration, pitch pattern, and intensity (or subband energy) correlate with accentuation (Tamburini, 2003; Wang & Narayanan, 2007a). These acoustic parameters have been used in systems for automatic accent detection; however, there is a lack of validated automatic analysis techniques to investigate accent production in populations with speech disorders. In clinical practice, the automatic accent detection system could significantly reduce the time required to analyze speech data and provide quantitative information of prosodic parameters useful for diagnostic and outcome

measures. This could help clinicians define and implement more precise therapeutic approaches based on the identification of specific compensatory strategies of accent production. In addition, it may, in the future, allow a move away from structured sentence accent tasks toward more naturalistic speech samples as the basis for analysis.

Thesis outline

Speech technology contributes increasingly to the clinical care of patients with dysarthria. The main targets of this study will be the development of speech processing techniques for detecting different conditions that may impact speech production and its application on automated speech therapy tools. Articulation has a significant impact on speech intelligibility; therefore, the effectiveness of a direct boost articulation therapy on speech intelligibility in patients with dysarthria and the effect of the severity on the outcome are addressed in [Chapter 2](#).

[Chapter 3](#) and [Chapter 4](#) describe the design and development of a new Virtual Articulation Therapist (VAT) that supports intensive articulation training, the algorithms on which the system is based, the automatic feedback, the score of articulatory distortion and the validation of the system by end-users are covered in these chapters.

Prosody, which also has a considerable impact on intelligibility, is addressed in the subsequent chapters. It is of clinical interest to identify relevant acoustic features that enable the automatic classification of one of the main communicative functions of prosody (focus or emphasis in a sentence). This objective analysis for the characterization of sentence accent production is covered in [Chapter 5](#). In [Chapter 6](#) it is addressed the validation of the automatic accent detection and characterization methodology across different speaker populations varying in the type and severity of their speech disorders and spoken language.

Finally, [Chapter 7](#) and [Chapter 8](#) of this dissertation address the main conclusions and possible future directions of speech technology at the patients' care disposal.

General aims

The study's overall aim is to contribute to the enhancement of daily clinical care and well-being of patients with dysarthria by improving and supporting the assessment and treatment of deviant articulation and prosody that affects their speech intelligibility. This research aims to reach that target from a different perspective, using advances in speech technology and signal processing to capture broad cues of impaired speech that will allow us to increase our knowledge about behavioural treatments of articulation in this population and to increase our understanding of prosodic mechanisms and strategies through emerging techniques which include acoustically based methods.

The research will then answer the following questions:

RQ1: What is the feasibility and effectiveness of intensive articulation therapy in patients with chronic dysarthria?

RQ2: Which modifications in existing algorithms are necessary for precise and reliable phonological error detection in patients with dysarthria?

RQ3: What is the feasibility of a VAT system and the end users' acceptability, usability and interaction with it?

RQ4: Which prediction model can objectively estimate the degree of phoneme distortion in subjects with dysarthria?

RQ5: Which acoustic features characterize sentence accent in patients with dysarthria?

RQ6: Is sentence accent detectable in different populations by the same acoustic features (RQ5), and can they objectively characterize accent production strategies at varying levels of dysarthria severity?

PART 2

ARTICULATION

CHAPTER 2

Effect of boost articulation therapy (BArT) on intelligibility in adults with dysarthria

This chapter has been published in

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Abstract

Background

The articulatory accuracy of patients with dysarthria is one of the most affected speech dimensions with a high impact on speech intelligibility. Behavioural treatments of articulation can either involve direct or indirect approaches. The latter have been thoroughly investigated and are generally appreciated for their almost immediate effects on articulation and intelligibility. The number of studies on (short-term) direct articulation therapy is limited.

Aims

To investigate the effects of short-term, boost articulation therapy (BArT) on speech intelligibility in patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria and the effect of severity of dysarthria on the outcome.

Methods & Procedures

The study consists of a two-group pre-/post-test design to assess speech intelligibility at phoneme and sentence level and during spontaneous speech, automatic speech and reading a phonetically balanced text. A total of 17 subjects with mild to severe dysarthria participated in the study and were randomly assigned to either a patient-tailored, intensive articulatory drill programme or an intensive minimal pair training. Both training programmes were based on the principles of motor learning. Each training programme consisted of five sessions of 45 min completed within one week.

Outcomes & Results

Following treatment, a statistically significant increase of mean group intelligibility was shown at phoneme and sentence level, and in automatic sequences. This was supported by an acoustic analysis that revealed a reduction in formant centralization ratio. Within specific groups of severity, large and moderate positive effect sizes with Cohen's *d* were demonstrated.

Conclusions & Implications

BArT successfully improves speech intelligibility in patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria at different levels of the impairment.

Introduction

Dysarthria is described by Darley et al. (1969a, 1975) as a collective name for a group of speech disorders that are the result of disorders in muscular control of the speech mechanism, due to damage in the central or peripheral nervous system. It can affect all dimensions of speech, namely articulation, resonance, voice and prosody. Speech intelligibility is defined as the extent to which the acoustic signal produced by the speaker can be accurately captured by the listener (Hustad, 2008). The impairments derived from the affected dimensions can lead to reduced speech intelligibility, causing misinterpretation, difficulty and communication problems. Subsequently, dysarthria has a major impact on the patient's participation in daily life and overall quality of life (Dykstra et al., 2007; Dickson et al., 2008).

Articulatory imprecision is considered a key feature of dysarthria (Tjaden, 2007) reflected by perceptual characteristics such as irregular articulatory distortions, distortion of vowels and extended phonemes (Duffy, 2019). Reduced and uncoordinated articulatory displacements, due to slow, weak, imprecise and uncoordinated movements of the speech musculature, result in reduced acoustic contrasts for vowels and consonants, which in turn is linked to reduced speech intelligibility (Yorkston, 1996; Tjaden, 2007). De Bodt et al. (2002) showed that articulation contributed considerably more to speech intelligibility than other speech dimensions. It can, therefore, be concluded that addressing articulation problems is an important objective in the disorder-oriented treatment of dysarthria. In fact, Miller and Bloch (2017) show that articulation therapy is often selected by speech–language pathologists to treat their patients with dysarthria, independently of the severity of impairment.

Behavioural treatment of articulation can involve either a direct or an indirect approach. Direct methods focus on the segmental level of speech and aim to alter the identity of phonemes, whereas indirect methods focus on the suprasegmental level meaning that the strategies are superimposed on individual phonemes or sequences of phonemes and the effect on articulation is only secondary to the primary aim. Examples of indirect treatment methods are increased vocal intensity, changes in intonation and reduction of speech rate (Tjaden, 2007).

Speech–language pathologists (SLP) select the most appropriate intervention method based on factors such as the type and severity of the dysarthria, the patient's own goals, and treatment preferences obtained by assessment (Palmer et al., 2007). Duffy (2019) states that although working to reduce impairment and compensate for impairment are both appropriate, clinicians' efforts are more frequently directed toward compensation. This was confirmed in a survey by

Guns et al. (2009) and in a recent unpublished survey in which almost 70% of the 52 participating speech therapists indicated to prefer indirect treatment of articulation above phoneme-specific exercises (Van Nuffelen et al., 2019). A possible explanation could be the likelihood that compensation can be achieved more rapidly than the actual reduction of impairment (Duffy, 2019).

This preference seems to be supported by a considerable and still increasing number of studies showing a positive effect of indirect treatment strategies on speech intelligibility and articulation. For instance, there is a suggestion that speech rate is one of the most modifiable variables for improving intelligibility (Yorkston et al. 1992). This statement was supported by Martens et al. (2015) who investigated the effect of intensive treatment of speech rate and intonation on the intelligibility of dysarthric patients due to Parkinson's disease and observed significant improvements of the intelligibility scores. Other studies where rate control techniques were investigated found similar effects (Yorkston & Beukelman, 1981; Marcella et al. 1998; Hustad et al., 2003; Van Nuffelen et al., 2010). In addition, other behavioural therapy techniques seem to have a positive impact on intelligibility as well. The well-known Lee Silverman Voice Treatment program (LSVT®) appears to have a positive impact on articulatory precision, in particular vowel space area and speech intelligibility in persons with non-progressive dysarthria (Wenke et al., 2010). Sauvageau et al. (2015) confirmed an improved articulation of vowels and a better distinction of consonants as a result of increased loudness. In Sapir et al. (2003), the results of a single-case study of ataxic dysarthria indicated a short- and long-term improvement in phonatory and articulatory functions, speech intelligibility and overall communication. Cannito et al. (2012) found improvements in sentence intelligibility in patients with Parkinson's disease. The above studies demonstrate that therapy with a focus on increasing loudness can have a positive effect across the speech mechanism without direct attention to other systems (Dromey et al., 1995; Sapir et al., 2007).

One of the most appealing aspects of indirect methods, such as loud, slow and clear speech, is their demonstrated instant effect (Tjaden et al., 2014; Levy et al., 2017; Van Nuffelen et al., 2010).

In contrast with the considerable amount of evidence on indirect treatment strategies, the number of studies on direct articulation therapy is limited. However, some studies indicate that direct articulation treatment is actually worth the effort. Moreover, there is even a possibility that the focus on compensating can actually counter the process of neural reorganization to

reduce specific impairment (Dobkin & Thompson, 2000). A study that compared the effect of the LSVT and a traditional direct intervention in non-progressive dysarthria patients revealed a short- and long-term significant increase in vowel space area and intelligibility following both treatments (Wenke et al., 2010). A single-case study by Hartman et al. (1979) investigated whether a patient with dysarthria as a result of a traumatic brain injury (TBI) would benefit from following a segmental articulation therapy. The results showed an improvement in the trained tasks and, in addition, the patient was able to generalize the correct articulation to untrained words. Another single-case study by Marchant et al. (2008) compared the effect of phonetic placement therapy (PPT) and surface electromyography (sEMG) biofeedback-facilitated relaxation therapy in a child with severe spastic dysarthria. Results showed a significant improvement in word intelligibility after following the PPT. However, no perceptual improvement was observed in overall intelligibility with the severity of dysarthria suggested as a possible cause.

It can be concluded that if the patient still has the neural and muscular potential to improve speech function, an appropriate therapy can facilitate that process. It is therefore important to further explore whether patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria can benefit from an intervention on the segmental level and whether even short, boost articulation therapies (BArT) are worth the effort.

A key feature of boost therapies is intensity, one of the main principles of motor learning and neuroplasticity which are generally acknowledged as key for speech therapy (Rosenbek & Jones, 2009; Kaipa & Peterson, 2016; Duffy, 2019). Several studies have already shown that intensive treatment of dysarthria is beneficial for long-term carryover (Jones et al., 1999; Nudo et al., 2000; Ramig et al., 2001b; Bhogal et al., 2003; Kleim et al., 2003; Fox et al., 2006; Mackenzie & Lowit, 2007; Mackenzie et al., 2014; Miller, 2014). Intensity can be achieved via the frequency of treatment, repetitions within sessions or in requiring greater force, effort or accuracy during motor tasks. Other important aspects are continued practice needed for long-term structural changes in neural functioning and sensory feedback (Kleim et al., 2003; Garvey et al., 2007; Kleim & Jones, 2008; Maas et al., 2008).

To date, there are few studies that combine the principles of motor learning with a segmental approach to traditional articulation therapy. This research aims to explore this further on the basis of the research questions:

Can BArT significantly improve speech intelligibility in chronic or progressive dysarthria?

Is there a significant impact of dysarthria severity on the outcome?

Methods

The study consists of a two-group pre-/post-test design to assess the speech intelligibility of patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria before and after intensive articulation therapy on the segmental level, after one week of therapy.

Participants

Patients were recruited at the University Hospital of Antwerp and private practices by convenience sampling. In order to participate in the study, the patients had to be adults (> 18 years of age), native speakers of Dutch, with a diagnosis of chronic or progressive dysarthria due to neurogenic origin and with a score < 90% at the Dutch phoneme Intelligibility Assessment (DIA-a synonym for the abbreviation NSVO in Dutch) (De Bodt et al., 2006). Articulation therapy during the last six months was set as an exclusion criterion.

A total of 17 Dutch-speaking subjects with dysarthria (11 men and six women) were included. Table 2.1 displays subjects' characteristics and the test results of the Dutch version of the Montreal Cognitive Assessment test (MoCa) (Thissen et al., 2010) and the Speech Handicap Index (SHI) (Van den Steen et al. 2011).

Table 2.1. Characteristics of the participants

Participant	Intervention Notes: a	Sex	Age (years)	Neurological pathology	Type of dysarthria	Severity dysarthria	MoCa score ^b	SHI Score ^c
1	AD	Male	56	Idiopathic	Flaccid	Mild	24	27
2	AD	Male	55	Cerebellar ataxia	Spastic	Mild	24	32
3	AD	Male	38	Steinert disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate	25	24
4	AD	Male	60	Idiopathic	Mixed	Severe	29	42
5	AD	Female	36	Friedreich ataxia	Atactic	Mild	28	18
6	AD	Female	84	ALS	Mixed	Severe	18	42
7	AD	Female	72	Parkinson's Disease	Hypokinetic	Severe	22	50

8	AD	Female	75	Parkinson's Disease	Hypokinetic	Mild	21	41
9	MP	Male	81	Idiopathic	Flaccid	Severe	22	37
10	MP	Male	98	Parkinson's Disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate	25	22
11	MP	Female	85	ALS	Mixed	Severe	26	39
12	MP	Male	35	Friedreich ataxia	Atactic	Moderate	27	12
13	MP	Male	63	Parkinson's Disease	Hypokinetic	Mild	27	19
14	MP	Male	81	Steinert Disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate	21	26
15	MP	Male	70	Idiopathic	Flaccid	Moderate	25	9
16	MP	Female	92	TIA	Mixed	Severe	20	25
17	MP	Male	53	Parkinson's Disease	Hypokinetic	Mild	25	23

Notes:^a Intervention: AD, articulatory drill; and MP, minimal pairs.

^b Score of the cognitive test Montreal Cognitive Assessment (score range: 0–30, score \geq 26 = normal cognitive functioning).

^c Score of the Speech Handicap Index (score range: 0–60; score < 14 no impact, 14–22 light, 23–31 moderate, > 31 severe impact).

ALS, amyotrophic laterals sclerosis; TIA, transient ischemic attack.

Intervention

The participants were randomly assigned to either the articulatory drill programme (BArT-AD) or the minimal pair programme (BArT-MP). Drill refers to the systematic training of specially selected and ordered exercises (Duffy, 2019). It is a consistent way of practising. When training on minimal pairs, a form of variable practice, two sounds that differ on one distinctive feature are linked together (Bauman- Waengler, 2004). Both articulatory drill and minimal pairs were selected for the same goal, namely, to push and stimulate the motor circuits to articulate more precisely and consequently reduce sound distortions. Participants practised five sessions of 45 min during one week with each session addressing a patient-specific target sound based on the qualitative analysis of the NSVO.

Figure 2.1 illustrates the design of both BArT-AD and BArT-MP. For each target sound, the programme incorporates three exercise sections with the target sound (BArT-AD) or distinctive

contrast (BArT-MP) respectively in an initial, medial/final position and in mixed position. The sections need to be completed in consecutive order starting with the initial position.

The sections are further divided into four levels with increasing difficulty and decreasing feedback. The patient starts with training on level 1, receiving feedback from the SLP after each word (BArT-AD) or each minimal pair (BArT-MP).

At each level, the therapist gives solely feedback on the first set of words or word pairs. For the remaining two sets, the patient first must do a self-perception assessment (i.e., internal feedback) and only subsequently receives delayed external feedback from the SLP. The therapist offers several types of feedback, such as auditory and visual modelling, phonetic placement with pictural support, verbal phonetic placement, clear speech and vivid speech. During the training, there is a gradual reduction of feedback frequency. Figure 2.1 shows a summary of both intervention programmes. The well-delineated design and sequence of the therapy programmes were respected during each session.

The stimuli of the training programme were carefully selected from the book *Articulation in Practice* (Huybrechts, 1999) and the official word inventory of Dutch (Renkema, 1995). They were presented to the patients by means of a PowerPoint presentation. The target sound was highlighted by putting it in bold. During the training, the therapist scores the words of the last set. If the patient scores < 50% in the last set of the first level, level 0 is passed through once. If the patient fails again on the first level, but a correct self-perception was noted, the patient may proceed to level 2. In case of an incorrect self-perception, the training continues with another target sound to be practised.

Figure 2.1. Intervention design. Components with '(1)' are exclusively intended for the intervention articulatory drill; components with '(2)' are intended for the intervention of minimal pairs; and when nothing is included, the parts are common for both interventions. *The SLP scores each word by means of a scoring form; and **feedback.

Perceptual assessment

The baseline measurements were collected 1–3 days before the start of the therapy programme, the posttreatment speech status of the patients was assessed immediately after the therapy programme, in order to evaluate short-term effects.

Five speech tasks were included: (1) a standardized speech intelligibility assessment at the phoneme level (NSVO), (2) a standardized sentence intelligibility assessment (NSVO-Z), (3) spontaneous speech, (4) automatic speech (counting to 10 and listing the weekdays) and (5) reading the phonetically balanced text 'De Auto' (Martens et al., 2010).

Intelligibility was perceptually judged in all the speech tasks by three experienced SLP's. Tasks 3–5 were presented randomly and judged by means of visual analogue scales (VAS). The average score of the measures was used for further analysis.

Recording procedure

Speech samples were recorded before and after treatment in a quiet environment, with a high-quality headset microphone (Plantronics Blackwire 5210) positioned at a mouth distance of 5 cm, connected to a computer, and using the freely available software Audacity v.2.3.3 (sampling rate 44.1 kHz with 24-bit quantization, mono) (Audacity Team, 2019).

Acoustic analysis

Besides perceptual assessments, an acoustic analysis was performed to objectively evaluate the treatment effects of the intervention programme. The F1, F2 formant frequencies can be used to describe the articulatory movements of the tongue, jaw and lips (Kent et al., 1999), and the vowels /a/, /i/, /u/ often represent the extremes of articulatory goals. There are some commonly used methods to quantify vowel production clinically and have been used to characterize vowel articulation impairment showing promising results. One of those methods is the Formant Centralization Ratio (FCR), a sensitive, valid and reliable acoustic measurement designed to calculate vowel centralization with reduced sensitivity to inter-speaker variability (Sapir et al. 2010; Caverlé & Vogel, 2020). The FCR is applied in this study for monitoring treatment effects, as a supportive measure to perceptual evaluations. An FCR score of approximately 1 is considered to be a normal value for a healthy speaker, for dysarthric speech higher scores are expected (2 as a maximum) due to a smaller vowel quadrilateral. A decrease in vowel centralization would be expected following an effective treatment of the dysarthria. The formula to calculate FCR is represented as:

$$(F2u + F2a + F1u + F1i) / (F2i + F1a)$$

where F1 and F2 represent the first and the second formants of the vowels, respectively.

The acoustic analysis was performed using Praat software v6.1.09 (Boersma & Weenink, 2020) running on Windows OS. Acoustic segmentations were conducted taking into account intensity and pitch period. The vowels /a/, /i/ and /u/ were analysed from representative items of the NSVO assessment, pre- and posttherapy. The mean frequency values of the formants F1 and F2 were measured in the temporal midpoint of each vowel, where the energy reaches maximum intensity.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was completed by means of the computer programme IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences v.26 (IBM SPSS 26). A Shapiro–Wilk test was used to investigate the normality of distribution. A mixed-design analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to verify possible between-groups (articulatory drill versus minimal pairs) differences. Mixed-models' effects were used to analyse the effect of BArT in time with post-hoc analysis to investigate the effect of severity of impairment; the Bonferroni–Holm correction was applied for multiple testing. To account for the small sample sizes, effect sizes (Cohen's *d*) were calculated. The relationship between acoustic and perceptual evaluations was verified by means of correlation. A significance level (α) of $p = 0.05$ was used for all statistical analyses.

Ethics permission

The clinical trial was approved by the Independent Commission for Medical Ethics 'Ethics Committee Antwerp University Hospital'. All participants agreed voluntarily to participate in the study and signed an informed consent.

Results

For all intelligibility measures, the three judges showed an excellent overall interrater reliability (ICC = 0.979, $p < 0.001$, 95% confidence interval (CI) = 0.972– 0.985). The ICC for the individual tasks ranged from 0.967 to 0.983 with a strong significance ($p < 0.001$).

Between-groups (articulatory drill versus minimal pairs) differences

No significant differences were found between the effects of the two intervention programmes, allowing us to combine the data of both therapy programmes.

Effect of articulation therapy on intelligibility in time

Mixed-models analysis showed a significant increase in the intelligibility after BArT in three speech tasks, namely the NSVO, NSVO-Z and automatic sequences (Table 2.2).

Patients score higher after the intervention, respectively, a mean increase of +6% on both the NSVO ($F(1.16) = 9.129$, $p = 0.008$) and the NSVO-Z ($F(1.16) = 7.977$, $p = 0.012$). The two assessments demonstrated a moderate effect size (Cohen's $d > 0.2$) between the baseline and post-measurement. A similar improvement in perceptual intelligibility was found in the scores of automatic sequences ($F(1.16) = 5.251$, $p = 0.036$). An increase of +4% was found after the intervention, but a small effect size (Cohen's $d < 0.2$) was demonstrated in time.

Descriptive results of the other speaking tasks show overall small increments in intelligibility due to the training programme. Nevertheless, no other significant improvements were found in spontaneous speech ($F(1.16) = 3.632$, $p = 0.075$) and in the standard passage ($F(1.16) = 1.186$, $p = 0.292$). Small effect sizes (Cohen's $d < 0.2$) of the intervention were demonstrated in time.

Table 2.2. Summary of effect sizes of each speech tasks and time point for intelligibility (n = 17)

	Baseline	Post-measurement
<i>NSVO</i>		
Mean \pm SD	72 \pm 14	78 \pm 16
p-value		0.008
Cohen's d		0.41
<i>NSVO-Z</i>		
Mean \pm SD	69 \pm 25	75 \pm 21
p-value		0.012
Cohen's d		0.27
<i>Spontaneous speech</i>		
Mean \pm SD	56 \pm 32	60 \pm 30
p-value		0.075
Cohen's d		0.13
<i>'De Auto'</i>		
Mean \pm SD	67 \pm 26	70 \pm 27
p-value		0.292
Cohen's d		0.12
<i>Automatic sequences</i>		
Mean \pm SD	77 \pm 22	81 \pm 22
p-value		0.036
Cohen's d		0.19

Note: Significant p-values and large effect sizes (> 0.8) reflecting training effects are denoted in bold.

Training effects compared by severity levels

When examining the training effects, significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were found per group of dysarthria severity levels (DSLs). A comparison between the three groups, namely mild (n = 6), moderate (n = 5) and severe dysarthria (n = 6) was performed by post-hoc analysis of the mixed models. Table 2.3 represents the results of the training effects over time divided by DSLs.

The results of the standardized assessment NSVO show a significant difference between DSLs ($F(2.4) = 14.319$, $p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis determined a significant increase in time of 8%

for the mild group ($p = 0.038$). However, the significant difference was not preserved after correction for multiple testing ($p = 0.114$). Nevertheless, a large effect size was found between the scores of two time points. For moderate and severe groups, descriptive results indicate improvements of +5%; however, no statistically significant results were found. Figure 2.2 illustrates the evolution of each group of severity levels.

Table 2.3. Summary of effect sizes by groups of DSLs and time point

	Mild (n=6)		Moderate (n=5)		Severe (n=6)	
	Baseline	Post-measurement	Baseline	Post-measurement	Baseline	Post-measurement
<i>NSVO</i>						
Mean \pm SD	82 \pm 8	90 \pm 5	78 \pm 9	83 \pm 8	58 \pm 11	63 \pm 15
p-value		0.038		0.211		0.197
Corrected p-value		0.114		0.394		0.394
Cohen's d		1.36		0.70		0.41
<i>NSVO-Z</i>						
Mean \pm SD	88 \pm 10	95 \pm 3	79 \pm 13	79 \pm 9	42 \pm 19	53 \pm 15
p-value		0.051		0.861		0.005
Corrected p-value		0.102		0.861		0.015
Cohen's d		1.06		0.00		0.70
<i>Automatic sequences</i>						
Mean \pm SD	94 \pm 6	98 \pm 2	87 \pm 8	86 \pm 10	53 \pm 19	59 \pm 23
p-value		0.076		0.640		0.016
Corrected p-value		0.152		0.64		0.048
Cohen's d		1.09		- 0.12		0.32

Notes: Corrected p-values after the Bonferroni–Holm correction for multiple testing are added after the raw p-values.

Significant p-values and large effect sizes (> 0.8) reflecting training effects are denoted in bold.

The results of the standardized assessment NSVO-Z also show a significant difference between DSLs ($F(2.14) = 21.023$, $p < 0.001$). The severe group improved significantly over time ($p = 0.005$); even after the Bonferroni–Holm correction, the significance was preserved ($p = 0.015$). A moderate effect size was demonstrated. The mild group improves with +7%; moreover, a large effect size was found between the scores of the measure moments. The moderate group seems to be steady.

For automatic sequences, a significant difference was also found between DSLs ($F(2.14) = 13.901$, $p < 0.001$). The severe group increased significantly over time with +6% ($p = 0.016$); the significance is preserved after correction for multiple testing ($P = 0.048$). The mild group

improves with +4% after training and a large effect size was demonstrated. The moderate group decreased by -1% over time, which is reflected in the negative effect size score.

Figure 2.2. Training effects of the BArT divided by DSLs.

Acoustic analysis

After testing for normality, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated in order to verify the relationship between FCR and intelligibility scores, pre and post-therapy. A negative strong correlation was found for the NSVO ($r = -0.857$, $p = 0.000$). This implies that FCR scored lower in participants where positive changes in intelligibility were observed after BArT. Box plots illustrating the differences of FCR and intelligibility before and after therapy, respectively, are shown in figure 2.3. Mixed-models analysis did not show a significant difference between pre- and posttreatment values of the FCR; however, individual results of each subject showed improvements in vowel production.

Figure 2.3. FCR and Intelligibility (NSVO) before and after therapy.

Discussion

The articulatory accuracy of patients with dysarthria is one of the most affected speech dimensions with a high impact on intelligibility (De Bodt et al., 2002). Either direct or indirect methods can be used for articulation therapy in the treatment of patients with dysarthria. Although direct articulation therapy is one of the classical ingredients of speech therapy and it has-in contrast with compensatory strategies-the potential to actually improve the underlying impairment in patients with dysarthria, studies investigating its effect on speech intelligibility and its short-term effect are scarce.

To investigate the effect of BArT, implementing the principles of motor learning, two therapy programmes were designed. The only difference between both programmes is the exercise material with one programme using articulatory drills (BArT-AD) and the other one using minimal pairs (BArT-MP). This pilot study shows that a five-day BArT programme targeting the main distorted phonemes can significantly improve speech intelligibility in patients with dysarthria.

Significant increases of intelligibility were observed for three different speech tasks, at a phoneme level (NSVO), in automatic sequences and even at the sentence level (NSVO-Z). These outcomes are in line with the results of Hartman et al. (1979) and Marchant et al. (2008), showing that there is an improvement in the trained tasks. However, the former two studies are only a case report of longer treatment programmes. The results of our study demonstrated that intensive treatments focusing on the segmental level of speech succeed to elicit improvements in speech intelligibility at different levels in a short period of time. This shows that patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria can continue exploiting and developing all available residual motor skills.

The perceptual assessments are supported objectively by the results of the acoustic analysis, which revealed a reduction in FCR scores after BArT where significant improvements of intelligibility were observed. Although no statistically significant differences were found for FCR values pre- and post-treatment, the results show a positive tendency. The FCR analyses the formant frequencies of vowel articulation, while perceptual evaluation of intelligibility includes a more extensive range of parameters and focuses on both consonant and vowel production. FCR values are well correlated with intelligibility in this study. The acoustic analysis documents the therapeutic effect of the BArT in the expansion of the vowel space. The lower values of FCR obtained in this study are the result of a wider range of articulatory

movements and more precise positions of the articulators during speech. Perceived improvements in speech production due to the treatment effects are reflected in the vowel expansion toward normalcy (decreased FCR).

No significant improvements in overall intelligibility were found in spontaneous speech and the standard passage. These findings are comparable with similar studies that also aim to improve intelligibility (Pennington et al., 2006; Lowit et al., 2020) by applying different intervention methods, without any significant improvements in those specific speaking tasks. Nevertheless, the descriptive analysis showed that small but not significant gains were achieved due to the training programme for those speaking tasks. This suggests that it is important to continue with the intervention for a longer period of time. In some cases, additional practice/ techniques at the suprasegmental level for those linguistic levels might be also recommended. Previous research into motor skills clearly shows that an exercise schedule in which constant exercise is followed by variable exercise seems to be optimal (Maas, 2015). Adding variability of practising will lead to better performances on effective re-learning, retention and generalization of trained motor skills. Obviously, BArT-MP has a higher degree of variability due to the elicited contrasts while drill exercises are generally considered to be constant in nature. However, as the phonetical context (preceding or succeeding phoneme) of the target phoneme changes all the time and as section 3 consists of utterances with the target phoneme in different, mixed positions, also BArT-AD implies some degree of variability. This might contribute to the lack of a significant difference in intelligibility following BArT-MP and BArT-AD.

After careful analysis, not any remarkable difference was found in the effects of the applied articulation training programmes on the different types of dysarthria. Intelligibility improves for the majority of subjects regardless of the type of dysarthria, aetiology, severity, age, and also despite the therapy programme they followed (BArT-AD or BArT-MP). Both approaches had comparable results in the impact they have on intelligibility.

The lack of between-subjects' differences in outcome might be due to the small sample size, but might also be due to the fact that BArT uses a patient-specific error analysis and therefore a patient-specific target sound selection. Although articulation difficulties occur in all types of dysarthria, it has also been shown that the type of articulatory errors and more precisely the type of distortions depends upon the underlying pathomechanism (Antolik & Fougeron, 2013).

By using a patient-tailored method, the possible effects of BArT can be equalized for all subjects, regardless of the underlying aetiology.

A positive effect of BArT was found in each severity group for phoneme intelligibility (NSVO), sentence intelligibility (NSVO-Z) and automatic sequences. Due to the small sample sizes of these subgroups, the improvements do not reach the level of significance; however, large or moderate positive effect sizes were demonstrated. These results suggest that even adults with moderate to severe chronic or progressive dysarthria may benefit from BArT, which is of high clinical interest as the focus on direct articulation therapy often shifts to compensation in this population (Miller & Bloch, 2017). Future research needs to confirm this effect and to determine if this improvement is reflected in the patient's daily communication.

To support the recovery of disordered speech motor execution, an extensive, well-structured and hierarchical practice package of exercises is recommended. Standardized, well-structured therapy programmes for direct articulation therapy are lacking. The two programmes developed for this study seem to be feasible and well tolerated by the patients. Therefore, the structure can be used in further clinical practice and research.

Limitations

A generalization of these results has to be done with care because the study was restricted to the short-term evolution in a rather small group. Also, there is no control group without speech training to exclude spontaneous changes and order effects of repeated testing. Post-treatment reassessment of the SHI was not collected because the period for re-examination was too short for a questionnaire of this type.

Future research

Future research will focus on the mid- and long-term global effects of the BArT and the possible differences between BArT-MP and BArT-AD in a larger population. Evaluation of the effects on daily communication has also to be investigated as well as the generalization of this therapy to other levels of speech. The use of a control treatment (e.g., traditional or standard methods of dysarthria therapy) to determine whether the effects of the intervention in this population are treatment specific also warrants investigation. Besides the cost-efficacy of the intervention has to be also analysed and compared with other treatments.

Conclusions

The results of the current study demonstrated that a five session-BArT significantly improves speech intelligibility and reduces impairment in chronic or progressive mild to severe dysarthria.

CHAPTER 3

Automatic boost articulation therapy in adults with dysarthria: acceptability, usability and user interaction

This chapter has been published in

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Abstract

Background

Imprecise articulation has a negative impact on speech intelligibility. Therefore, treatment of articulation is clinically relevant in patients with dysarthria. In order to be effective and according to the principles of motor learning, articulation therapy needs to be intensive, well organized, with adequate feedback and requires frequent practice.

Aims

The aims of this pilot study are (1) to evaluate the feasibility of a virtual articulation therapy (VAT) to guide patients with dysarthria through a boost articulation therapy (BArT) program; (2) to evaluate the acoustic models' performance used for automatic phonological error detection; and (3) to validate the system by end-users from their perspective.

Methods & Procedures

The VAT provides an extensive and well-structured package of exercises with visual and auditory modelling and adequate feedback on the utterances. The tool incorporates automated methods to detect phonological errors, which are specifically designed to analyse Dutch speech production. A total of 14 subjects with dysarthria evaluated the acceptability, usability and user interaction with the VAT based on two completed therapy sessions using a self-designed questionnaire.

Outcomes & Results

In general, participants were positive about the new computer-based therapy approach. The algorithm performance for phonological error detection shows it to be accurate, which contributes to adequate feedback of utterance production. The results of the study indicate that the VAT has a user-friendly interface that can be used independently by patients with dysarthria who have sufficient cognitive, linguistic, motoric and sensory skills to benefit from speech therapy. Recommendations were given by the end-users to further optimize the program and to ensure user engagement.

Conclusions & Implications

The initial implementation of an automatic BArT shows it to be feasible and well accepted by end-users. The tool is an appropriate solution to increase the frequency and intensity of articulation training that supports traditional methods.

Introduction

Dysarthria is a neurogenic motor speech disorder caused by impaired muscular control due to damage to the central or peripheral nervous system (Darley et al., 1969a; 1975). The impairment may affect the mechanisms involved in speech production and consequently cause deficits in speech intelligibility. Imprecise speech sound articulation is a hallmark of dysarthria (Tjaden, 2007; Weismer, 2007). Research in this domain has shown that articulation is the most essential dimension of speech contributing to the overall speech intelligibility in dysarthria (Kent, 1992b; De Bodt et al., 2002). Deficient articulatory movements are linked with reduced acoustic contrast for consonants and vowels, which leads to reduced intelligibility (Tjaden, 2007; Tykalova et al., 2017). Even when neurologic bases differ among different types of dysarthrias, the impact on articulatory movements and acoustic outcomes is in general comparable (Tjaden, 2007). Reduced speech intelligibility has a major psychosocial impact. Daily life communication gets less evident, satisfactory or even impossible for subjects with dysarthria, affecting general quality of life (Dykstra et al., 2007; Dickson et al., 2008). Therefore, behavioural interventions to improve articulation and, consequently, speech intelligibility are necessary for individuals with dysarthria.

There is scientific and clinical evidence that improving articulatory skills demands intensive and frequent therapy (Duffy, 2019; Rosenbek & Jones, 2009). There is growing evidence that the content of speech therapy must meet the principles of motor learning (Duffy, 2019). Key elements of motor learning in clinical neurorehabilitation are intensive treatment, repetitive practice and sensory feedback (Kleim et al., 2003; Garvey et al., 2007; Kleim & Jones, 2008; Maas et al., 2008). Extensive research in the speech therapy domain suggests that providing large amounts of practice over a shorter period can lead to better results/outcomes for adults with communication disorders (Bhogal et al., 2003; Fox et al., 2006). A more recent study demonstrated that boost articulation therapy (BArT), in which participants perform intensive articulatory drill and minimal pairs exercises for 5 consecutive days, has a significant positive effect on speech intelligibility in patients with dysarthria (Mendoza et al., 2021a). However, the current treatments of articulation are mainly limited in time to the interactive sessions in the presence of speech–language pathology (SLP). A computer-based speech therapy approach would overcome that limitation offering patients the opportunity to practise more intensively and frequently to reduce the number of fatiguing and time-consuming transfers to the rehabilitation centre and to have access to speech therapy in their home environment. Virtual speech–language therapy would also provide patients with the possibility of an individualized

and customized therapy programme. However, this virtual therapy program only targets those persons with dysarthria who have sufficient cognitive, linguistic, motoric and sensory (auditory and visual) skills to benefit from speech therapy (Weismer, 2007).

Virtual therapy technologies are not entirely new; however, only a few attempts have been made for adults with motor speech disorders (Lee, 2019). Most of the reported studies using virtual therapy focus on adults with aphasia (e.g., Abad et al., 2013; Thompson et al., 2010; Van Vuuren & Cherney, 2014; Cherney et al., 2008; Lee et al., 2009; Kalinyak-Fliszar et al., 2015; Marshall et al., 2016; Amaya et al., 2018) and children with hearing impairment (Chaisanit et al., 2010; Eriksson et al., 2005; Massaro & Light, 2004; Da Silva et al., 2012). Automatic systems addressing the needs of individuals with dysarthria are scarce (Lee, 2019). The designed and tested experimental models include the single case study of Cole et al. (2007), which investigated the effects of Lee Silverman Voice Treatment (LSVT) with a virtual therapy system; qualitative evaluation of the system by the user shows positive results. The study of Palmer et al. (2007) compared the effects of computerized and traditional therapy for speakers with longstanding dysarthria. The computer-based program consists of games that target the accurate production of individual speech sounds and exercises for practising sounds in words, phonation, pitch and volume, allowing independent training with feedback. This approach was demonstrated to be as effective as traditional therapy improving the speech of that specific group. The study of Saz et al. (2009), which evaluated a semi-automated tool that includes different games for children and young adults, considers phonation, phonetic articulation and language understanding for Spanish speakers. The feedback given about the system by the therapist and end-users was mainly positive. The study of Orozco-Arroyave et al. (2020b) introduced a mobile application for monitoring and evaluation of patients with Parkinson's disease. The app considers different motor aspects such as speech production, limb movements and finger tapping. It allows patients to track their progression and can be used as a personal health assistant. To our knowledge, there is no publicly available virtual articulation tool providing BArT with adequate feedback, especially not for Dutch-speaking subjects with articulatory deficits.

The present pilot study aims to evaluate the feasibility of a VAT for individuals with dysarthria. The goal of the system is to guide the patient through an intensive treatment programme based on the principles of motor learning and relying on speech technology for adequate feedback. It is intended to improve articulation and consequently pronunciation, intelligibility and communication abilities.

The study also focuses on the evaluation of the system by end-users. The purpose is to investigate the acceptability, usability and user interaction with computer-assisted articulation therapy. The stakeholder's opinion is particularly valuable to ensure that the new virtual intervention provides a suitable and engaging treatment. Some important aspects to consider are the participants' ability to interact independently with the virtual articulation trainer; whether they find the user interface attractive, supportive and clear, and if they find the material to be useful. It is also important to know how end-users experience the visual feedback and their general perception of the program.

Therefore, the main goals of this study are the design and development of a new computer-based therapy program that supports intensive articulation training of patients with dysarthria, the evaluation of acoustic models' performance used for automatic phonological error detection, and a general validation by stakeholders of the usability, acceptability and interaction with the automatic system.

Methods

Participants

The developed program targets patients with dysarthria who have sufficient cognitive, motor and sensory (auditory and visual) skills to work with a computer and/or those who can rely on assistance.

In order to participate in the study, the patients had to be adults (> 18 years of age) with a diagnosis of dysarthria due to neurogenic origin (confirmed by an experienced SLP and neurologist), native speakers of Dutch and with a score < 90% on the Dutch phoneme Intelligibility Assessment (DIA) (De Bodt et al., 2006).

Participants were excluded from the study if they had serious visual or auditory problems, insufficient computer skills to use the software program independently and if an intensive articulation therapy was followed less than 2 months before the study in order to exclude possible effects of the training in the baseline of the intelligibility assessment.

Patients were recruited by an experienced SLP at the Noorderhart Rehabilitation & Multiple Sclerosis Center Pelt in Hasselt by convenience sampling. A total of 14 subjects with dysarthria participated in this pilot study; their severity level was determined perceptually by the SLP. Table 3.1 displays the subjects' characteristics. The Speech Handicap Index (SHI) (Van den

Steen et al., 2011) was administered to each participant; this instrument is a self-evaluation of quality of life and quantifies the biopsychosocial impact of the speech disorder.

Table 3.1. Characteristics of the participants

Participant	Sex	Age (years)	Neurological pathology	Type of dysarthria	Severity dysarthria	DIA score (%)	SHI score
1	Male	59	MS	Flaccid	Moderate	80	60
2	Male	76	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate	82	18
3	Female	76	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Mild	90	32
4	Male	58	MS	Mixed	Mild	68	20
5	Male	70	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate	60	39
6	Male	67	Stroke	Flaccid	Mild	90	10
7	Male	47	Friedreich ataxia	Ataxic	Mild	82	17
8	Male	57	MS	Flaccid	Moderate	62	41
9	Male	29	TBI	Flaccid	Mild	84	13
10	Female	76	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Mild	88	38
11	Female	67	Stroke	Flaccid	Mild	76	25
12	Female	92	Stroke	Ataxic	Mild	88	51
13	Female	66	MS	Spastic	Mild	90	23
14	Male	67	Stroke	Spastic	Moderate	76	1

Notes: MS, multiple sclerosis; TBI, traumatic brain injury; DIA, Dutch phoneme Intelligibility Assessment. Score of the Speech Handicap Index (SHI) (score range: 0–60; score < 14 no impact, 14–22 light, 23–31 moderate, > 31 severe impact).

Ethics permission

Ethical approval for this study was obtained by the Regional Committee of Medical and Health Research Ethics (B300201837099). All participants agreed voluntarily to participate in the study and signed an informed consent form.

Software

Design criteria

The VAT was designed for patients with articulation deficits in which a virtual therapist, acting like a real SLP, guides the patient through an intensive treatment program to improve articulation and consequently speech intelligibility. The developed software runs as a desktop application and can be installed on any computer. The VAT has multiple roles and functions:

motivating and stimulating the patient, giving clear instructions, analysing the target utterance, and providing adequate feedback based on automatic acoustic analysis of speech.

The development of the VAT system consisted of three main steps: (1) the development of an extensive database of exercises for articulation training; (2) the implementation of an algorithm for phonological error detection in order to provide the necessary feedback to the patients; and (3) the embedding of the set of new developments in an attractive, patient-friendly user interface.

Extensive database of exercises and intervention design

The integrity of speech sounds is a major factor in determining intelligibility (Kent, 1992b), thus the direct treatment of articulation at the segmental level of speech is the aim of this therapy program. This approach intends to reduce the speech impairment, and its effects may be also generalized to connected speech. A strong correlation between word intelligibility and sentence intelligibility was also found in previous studies (Yorkston & Beukelman, 1978; Weismer et al., 2001).

The content of speech material consists of two different: intensive training programs to improve articulation and phoneme intelligibility in persons with dysarthria. Based on the principles of motor learning, the training programs comprise articulatory drill and minimal pairs.

There are four levels of difficulty in each program, structured per target position of the consonant, in initial, medial and final position in the words. This allows the patient to go through intensive therapy. In a previous study, this particular approach (figure 3.1) resulted in significant improvements of intelligibility at different levels of speech in a group of adults with dysarthria (Mendoza et al., 2021a). The extensive, well-structured and hierarchical practice package of exercises recommended in that previous study is implemented in the VAT.

The exercises only include a series of mono- and bisyllabic words. These types of words are usually not problematic to understand or to read for patients with mild cognitive impairments. Most of the selected words are meaningful and emphasize the correct pronunciation of the target phoneme, making the therapy more effective and goal oriented. The stimuli were carefully selected by experienced SLPs from a traditional articulation programme ‘Articulation in Practice’ (Huybrechts et al., 1999) and from the official word inventory of Dutch (Renkema, 1995) to increase the number of stimuli.

Figure 3.1. The intervention design (Mendoza et al. 2021). The components labelled (1) are exclusively intended for the intervention articulatory drill. The components labelled (2) are intended for the intervention of minimal pairs. When nothing is included, the parts are common for both interventions. *SLP scores each word by means of a scoring form; and **feedback.

Algorithm selection and modifications

The algorithm used in the program for phonological error detection derived from the acoustic signal is based on existing models (Vasquez-Correa et al., 2019) using state-of-the-art gated recurrent neural networks (GRNN). It has been shown to be accurate at evaluating the dysarthria severity of patients with motor speech disorders, such as patients affected with the neurodegenerative Parkinson's disease (Orozco-Aroyave et al., 2020a; Miller et al., 2020).

The algorithm is a statistical approach to the human perception process and is based on the speech-production mechanisms. It extracts the log Mel-filterbank energy features from the acoustic signal and maps them into phonological features. Individual speech frames are

represented by a vector with information about place and manner of articulation. This vector captures the posterior probability of a speech frame to belong to one or more phonological classes (e.g., plosive, nasal, bilabial). The model was originally designed for Spanish, and most of the extracted characteristics were related to vowels. Therefore, modifications were necessary in order to reliably characterize consonants, and extended to detect the Dutch-specific phonological characteristics.

The combination of place and manner of articulation and voiced characteristics were used to describe the consonants in Dutch. Hence, the algorithm was retrained using the language-specific phonological features (Verhoeven, 2005) (Table 3.2) along with the read speech part of the Corpus Spoken Dutch (Oostdijk & Broeder, 2003), which is an extensive corpus (903043 words) of contemporary standard Dutch as it is spoken nowadays in the Netherlands and Dutch-speaking part of Belgium. With the refinement and extension of the models, trained on healthy speech and capable to recognize all the phonological features, it can be used to detect more specific articulation errors/deficits in subjects with dysarthria. Accuracy, precision (positive predictive value), recall (sensitivity) and F-score (harmonic mean of the precision and recall) performance measures to evaluate the models are offered in the results section.

The newly trained algorithm extracts the phonological posterior probabilities from the acoustic signal, and it is used to identify phonological errors present during the articulation training. However, the system does not make any decision with respect to the type and degree of error at the phoneme level (if the error was an addition, substitution, omission or distortion).

Table 3.2. Consonants place and manner of articulation (Verhoeven, 2005)

	Bilabial		Labio-dental		Alveolar		Post-alveolar		Palatal	Velar		Uvular	Glottal
Plosive	p	b			t	d			(c)	k	(g)		(ʔ)
Nasal		m		(ɱ)		n			(ɲ)		ŋ		
Trill						(r)						R	
Fricative			f	v	s	z	(ʃ)	(ʒ)		x	y		h
Approximant		w							j				
Lateral approximant						l			(ʎ)				

Note: Voiced consonants are on the right side.

User interface

The training program (VAT) has three stages. In the first, the user selects the target sound that he or she will train (figure 3.2). Once the selection is made, a video instruction with the description and examples of the correct production of the sound (visual model) is given. This support is provided with frontal and lateral video recordings that show the correct way of sound production in an easy, friendly and interpretable way (figure 3.3). Finally, auditory modelling of the words is also offered when the set of exercises starts. The patient repeats the target words, and the system will automatically capture and analyse the signal.

Subsequently, detailed visual feedback on the articulatory precision is provided. The graphs show whether or not the distinctive features of the target sound were present (figure 3.4). This detailed information, which is generally difficult to impossible to detect and quantify by the human ear, allows patients to work more precisely in the improvement of the articulatory movements. Misclassification or false detections of distinctive features could occur in the case of present background noise; therefore, it is recommended that patients practise in a quiet room and are encouraged to use a head-mounted condenser microphone.

For the general design of the user interface, the font, font size and button sizes are big, simple and clean, intended for elderly and patients with brain damage.

Figure 3.2. Sound selection.

Figure 3.3. Visual modelling.

Figure 3.4. Auditory modelling, exercises, and feedback.

Instruments to measure user interaction, acceptability and usability

After two therapy sessions of 45 min each, all the participants evaluated the computer-based therapy program. Usability, acceptability and interaction with the software were assessed through a questionnaire.

A questionnaire designed specifically for this study was completed by end-users after two sessions of practising with the VAT. The survey had the intention of evaluating software usability and acceptability from the user's point of view. The questionnaire was designed based on other questionnaires that addressed similar software-related topics, such as the Software Usability Measurement Inventory (SUMI) (Kirakowski & Corbett, 1993), the General Computer Skill Questionnaire (Klinkenberg et al., 2004) and the ASISTO questionnaire (Deruyter & Staessens, 2018); the items were restructured focusing on the VAT.

The set of questions addresses important topics that should be considered in order to succeed in future user engagement. It has a total of 32 items and is divided into five sections:

- Usability and operability: this section is designed to evaluate the patient's perception of the software functionality as a tool, if they feel comfortable working with it, if they can interact independently with it and if they find it friendly and easy to use, in general.
- Program and layout: this section focuses on how the users experience the visual and auditory support received during them practising and how attractive and clear the layout is perceived.
- Exercises: this section is designed to evaluate the user's perception of the usefulness of the training therapy and if they feel that the selected set of exercises is helpful for improving articulatory skills and consequently speech intelligibility.
- Feedback: this section is designed to evaluate the perception of the visual feedback that is given during therapy.
- Experience in the use of multimedia: with this section we would like to have the tendency of multimedia usage in daily life. It will give some insights into how likely or often we can expect the use of the software.

Each section contains several statements that participants have to score using a five-point Likert scale, where a score of 1 corresponds to 'completely disagree' and a score of 5 corresponds to 'completely agree'. The number of statements varies among sections; therefore, an average score is necessary for each section. Thereby, the questionnaire can have a maximum score of 25. The survey has also a section where the user might add suggestions or comments in order to improve the engagement and usability of the software. The survey is applied after two therapy sessions. For an overview of the questionnaire, see appendix A.

Training sessions

Before the start of the training, the goal of the virtual therapy and the steps of the program were explained in detail to every subject who participated in the study.

Training session 1

At the beginning of the first session, the DIA and SHI were conducted, followed by the supervised training moment. The selection of the target speech sounds to be trained was based on the error analysis of the DIA. The speech therapist started the computer and software and explained to the patient how to select the target speech sound and the level. Thereafter, it was demonstrated how to obtain auditory modelling of a training item, how to click to the next or preceding item, how to listen again to the patient's own speech production and how to go back

to start. It was explained in detail how to understand and manage the given feedback. After the first session, all subjects received a printed version of the manual to consult at home if necessary.

Training session 2

The second session took place after a maximum of 2 days following the first session. During this session, patients worked completely autonomously with the VAT. It was expected to train with the same target sounds at the same level as during the first session. They were supposed to understand and manage the visual feedback in order to adjust their articulation. The questionnaire was administered at the end of this session. The supervisor was present for assistance if necessary.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of the data was performed with the software program IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences v. 25 (IBM SPSS 25). The distribution of the data was checked for normality by means of the Shapiro–Wilk test, with a significance level of 0.05. Correlations between different variables were explored in order to investigate the relationship between the frequency of multimedia use, and between subsections of the questionnaire, and the overall evaluation of the program.

Results

Algorithm performance

The trained Dutch models achieved high accuracy rates for the detection of all trained phonological classes. This statistical approach of the human perception process has detection rates $> 88\%$ (*F*-score). During the learning process frequently occurring speech sounds of the language were modelled with higher accuracy than infrequently occurring sounds, but in general the results are considered accurate enough for the discrimination between each specific phonological class. Table 3.3 summarizes the performance of the models for the training dataset and the validation dataset (also called the development set). Precision, recall and *F*-score performance measures are also offered.

Table 3.3. Performance of the models for Dutch

Phonological class	Accuracy training set	Accuracy validation set	Precision	Recall	F-Score
Nasal	0.945	0.935	0.957	0.935	0.941
Plosive	0.942	0.910	0.936	0.910	0.917
Fricative	0.926	0.936	0.949	0.936	0.940
Approximant	0.916	0.889	0.965	0.889	0.917
Trill	0.899	0.937	0.969	0.937	0.949
Labial	0.941	0.917	0.948	0.917	0.927
Coronal	0.871	0.884	0.895	0.884	0.887
Dorsal	0.885	0.902	0.934	0.902	0.912
Glottal	0.947	0.979	0.991	0.979	0.984
Voice	0.911	0.935	0.935	0.935	0.935
Vowel	0.898	0.892	0.912	0.892	0.896
Bilabial	0.956	0.916	0.958	0.916	0.930
Labiodental	0.954	0.975	0.985	0.975	0.978
Alveolar	0.874	0.885	0.898	0.885	0.888
Postalveolar	0.975	0.994	0.998	0.994	0.996
Pause	0.975	0.978	0.979	0.978	0.978

Survey

Usability and operationality

Although some participants needed help with the mouse control, an average score of 4.14 out of 5 was given to the section ‘Usability and operationality’ (figure 3.5). This means that the patient’s perception of the software functionality was generally found as easy to use and understand. Most participants agreed that the VAT is user-friendly and can be used independently, but the answers to the statement ‘I would use the program daily at home’ were quite diverse. Half the subjects agreed or totally agreed, five were neutral and two disagreed. This could be related to the experience and daily use of multimedia, which was scored the lowest on the questionnaire, results which are presented below and that will be analysed later in this study. Figure 3.5 summarizes the average score of the items in this section.

Usability and operability

Figure 3.5. Usability and operability scored on a Likert scale (1 = ‘completely disagree’ and 5 = ‘completely agree’).

Program and layout

The section ‘Program and layout’ received an average score of 4.46 out of 5 (figure 3.6). Most of the users found the program attractive, with a clear layout. The visual and auditory support for the target sound production was perceived as appealing and supportive. Finally, all subjects would recommend the use of the VAT to other patients.

Program and layout

Figure 3.6. Program and layout scored on a Likert scale (1 = ‘completely disagree’ and 5 = ‘completely agree’).

Exercises

The section ‘Exercises’ received an average score of 4.23 out of 5 (figure 3.7). The users found the set of exercises to be clear and useful. This is particularly important because this type of repetitive and intensive training tends to be tiresome; therefore, it is essential that users find out the usefulness of the selected set of exercises that can help to improve their articulatory ability.

Figure 3.7. Exercises scored on a Likert scale (1 = ‘completely disagree’ and 5 = ‘completely agree’).

Feedback

The majority of users perceived the visual feedback given during therapy as clear and attractive. The section ‘Feedback’ received an average score of 3.96 out of 5 (figure 3.8). However, for this section the patients provided several suggestions to improve the stimulation and motivation of the user. They recommended also adding auditory feedback by the VAT in case of correct target production.

Figure 3.8. Feedback scored on a Likert scale (1 = ‘completely disagree’ and 5 = ‘completely agree’).

Experience in the use of multimedia

The section related to the participants’ use of multimedia received an average score of 3.06 out of 5 (figure 3.9), being the lowest of the questionnaire. These results clarify the score given before to the statement of daily usage of the software at home. Although the majority of the participants have some kind of multimedia device for entertainment, they do not use it every day. This is an interesting point that should be considered for the assignment of therapy frequency and duration.

A moderate correlation was found between experience in the use of multimedia and the perceived quality of the program $r = 0.554$ ($p = 0.04$), which was measured as the total score of the questionnaire. Patients with higher knowledge or experience with the usage of

multimedia tended to have a more positive perception of the quality of the software-based therapy. However, patients with less experience or interest in multimedia also showed a positive attitude to the therapy.

Figure 3.9. Use of multimedia scored on a Likert scale (1 = ‘completely disagree’ and 5 = ‘completely agree’).

Sections with a higher impact on the patient’s perception of the program

From a practical and statistical point of view, most of the aspects that were addressed in the questionnaire are considered highly significant for the end-users’ perception of the quality, acceptability and usability of the computer-based therapy program. The biggest impact on the overall score was related to the feedback, followed by the exercises; also usability and operability were highly significant for end-users. The program and layout seem to be important for practical use, but not statistically significant in the perception of acceptability and usability of the VAT (Table 3.4).

Table 3.4. Pearson correlation coefficients and significance level between the total score and the subscales of the questionnaire

	Use & Operation	Program & Layout	Exercises	Feedback
Total-Score	0.672** (p=0.009)	0.408 (p=0.147)	0.761** (p=0.002)	0.785** (p=0.001)

Note: Correlation is significant at the *0.05 level (two-tailed); and **0.01 level (two-tailed).

Discussion

This pilot study evaluated the feasibility of a VAT that guides patients with dysarthria through a BAiT program, combining speech technology, phoneme-specific feedback and motor learning principles. It is generally accepted that for motor speech disorders, greater therapy frequency leads to better ultimate performance (Dobkin & Thompson, 2000). The VAT addresses the need for an accessible program granting patients the opportunity to train their articulatory skills more intensively and frequently. The tool provides a set of exercises, visual

and auditory modelling of target utterances, and adequate feedback with accurate performance. It has an accessible interface for patients with brain damage who often deal with other motor and sensory dysfunctions and have limitations in language and cognition. Additionally, it can considerably increase the capacity of speech therapy for patients with practical limitations (distance, financial restrictions, etc.).

The results of the pilot study show that the VAT addresses the elementary aspects necessary to deliver the BArT successfully and to ensure the user's engagement. The study-specific questionnaire addressed the functionality, layout, content of the speech material used and feedback given during training. Quantitative evaluation after two sessions of interaction with the system shows that this study cohort, consisting of patients with mild to moderate dysarthria, but with sufficient cognitive, language, visual and auditory skills, were in general positive about this new computer-based therapy approach. These results were consistent with previously published virtual therapies in the field of speech and language therapy (Cole et al., 2007; Saz et al., 2009; Engwall et al., 2006; Eriksson et al., 2005). The majority of participants ensured that the VAT is attractive, user-friendly and can be used independently. The usefulness of the software was evaluated by two different statements within the survey, whether they found the type of exercises to be useful as well as the given automatic feedback.

Patients' responses confirmed that it is a useful tool that can help to improve their communication. The visual feedback was found to be attractive, clear and easy to interpret; however, there are some suggestions for its improvement and for keeping the user motivated, which is a key factor for successful training sessions. The recommendations include the addition of auditory feedback with a more stimulating and encouraging response, as a suggestion, applause that is played when the target sound is correctly pronounced, which can make the success in target production more evident to the users. Previous research indicates that rewarding feedback after accurate expressions is crucial to maintain a high motivation (Halpern et al., 2012; Oster 2006). Participants also pointed out that providing an overall score of articulation will grant a better view of their progress.

The section related to the use of multimedia in daily life shows that this specific group of participants (mainly elderly patients or with brain damage) are not highly motivated to use multimedia devices; however, most of them indicated a positive attitude toward the VAT program. This could be interpreted as they feel the program can be helpful to improve their articulatory skills while practising in their environment.

The general outcomes from the questionnaire can also be essential for traditional face-to-face therapy methods of articulation. SLPs may use these outcomes to provide better, more efficient and individualized articulatory therapy, taking into account that a well-structured and hierarchical programme of exercises is necessary and needs to be goal oriented, and the most valuable information they can offer to the patients is good and encouraging feedback.

The involvement of patients in the early stage of the design and developmental process of the system is a way to guarantee the usability and acceptability of the program. The recommendations/ suggestions made by the participants will lead to a suitable, easy-to-use and engaging virtual therapy.

Limitations

The study was restricted in time to two VAT therapy sessions interacting with the software program in a rather small cohort. This implies that the results of this pilot study are preliminary and cannot be generalized. In future validation studies, a larger number of patients should be included. Adding qualitative interview data and perspectives of caregivers and patients' family members may also lead to additional insights. Finally, the questionnaire can be upgraded by adding an item related to how accurate the subjects felt the feedback was.

Future research

Future research will focus on the evaluation of therapeutic effectiveness after introducing the VAT in daily patient care. This will include a higher number of subjects and objective measures of longitudinal articulatory improvements. Also, future research will focus on the optimization of the acoustic models for the automatic error detection in dysarthric speech, the development of an objective acoustic measure of sound distortion, and the correlation analysis of automatic versus perceptual measurements of the degree of distortion. Qualitative evaluation of the system by a wider community that includes caregivers, SLPs and patients' family members will also be investigated. The integration of exercises with higher linguistic levels will also be the focus of future work. The VAT will be released as an open-source system, with a general public licence. It will also be communicated via professional organizations of speech therapists and patient groups.

Conclusions

The computer-based articulation therapy for adults with dysarthria seems to be feasible and well accepted by the end-users of this pilot study. Most participants have a positive attitude

towards the use of the VAT. Even participants with limited computer skills/experiences are able to use the VAT independently. High accuracy was obtained on the performance of the models used for error detection, which contributes to adequate automatic feedback. However, the survey points out that improvements to the system are still necessary, and all the suggestions given by the stakeholders will be considered.

The inclusion of patients in the design and development of these types of software is significantly important for usability, acceptability and engagement with e-therapy, which appears to be a good option to increase the frequency and intensity of practice while supporting the traditional methods. The VAT offers clear applicability with an added value for the Flemish health facilities, including a positive impact for a specific group of patients.

CHAPTER 4

Automatic score of articulatory distortion in adults with dysarthria

This chapter has been submitted to *Speech Communication*

Mendoza Ramos, V., Vasquez-Correa, J. C., Nöth, E., De Bodt, M., & Van Nuffelen, G. (2022). Automatic score of articulatory distortion in adults with dysarthria.

Abstract

Background

Articulation is one of the speech dimensions that contribute significantly to speech intelligibility. Assessment and treatment of speech sound distortions are highly clinically relevant in patients with dysarthria. Currently, clinicians mainly rely on perceptual evaluations of sound distortion. However, this procedure remains subjective by nature. Therefore, an objective score of the degree of phoneme distortion is considered an essential outcome for detailed feedback during the speech training of speakers with dysarthria. Previous attempts to develop an automatic measure of articulation errors at the phoneme level mainly relied on automatic speech recognition systems. This study explores a different approach based on the phonological characterisation of speech sounds using a state-of-the-art gated recurrent neural network.

Aims

To develop a new algorithm for the objective estimation of the degree of phoneme distortion of dysarthric speech and to investigate the reliability of the prediction models.

Methods & Procedures

Phoneme-dependent and phoneme-independent models were trained and validated using Dutch speech samples of 35 subjects with mild to severe dysarthria. The overall performance of different regression and classification models was evaluated, and the most accurate model was then selected for the prediction of distortion.

Outcome & Results

The phoneme-dependent regression models were inaccurate in predicting the degree of distortion. However, the selected phoneme-independent classification model shows a good accuracy (73.5%) in predicting the degree of distortion at the phoneme level in dysarthric speech. Nevertheless, further improvements are required to increase the model performance.

Conclusions & Implications

The new objective estimation of phoneme distortion in dysarthric speech shows to be reliable. This scoring system can be integrated into virtual articulation therapy to provide feedback during speech training.

Introduction

Articulation refers to the production of specific and distinguishable speech sounds (i.e. phonemes; Duffy, 2000). Many of the distinctive features among speech sounds are the result of accurately targeted, fast, synchronous and coordinated lingual, facial, jaw, laryngeal and velopharyngeal movements (Duffy, 2000; Kearney & Guenther, 2019). In patients with dysarthria, a neurological speech motor execution disorder characterised by slow, weak, imprecise and/or uncoordinated movements of the speech musculature (Darley et al., 1969a, 1969b, 1975; Yorkston et al., 1999; Duffy, 2020) impaired articulation is one of the main, perceptually deviant speech characteristics (Kirshner, 2003; Darley et al., 1969a, 1969b, 1975; Tjaden, 2007; Duffy, 2020).

Within the different articulatory error types in dysarthria, speech sound distortion is the most predominant compared to substitutions, omissions, or additions (Johns & Darley, 1970; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1980; Tjaden, 2007; Kirshner, 2021). Distortion is defined as the production of an intended phoneme with 'recognisable' allophonic success but with articulatory characteristics not usually associated with that phoneme (Platt, Andrews, & Howie, 1980b). From the definition, we can hypothesise that sound distortion is related to deviations in the production of one or more sound-specific features.

Several studies examining the consonant distortion types observed in dysarthric speech have shown some agreement about the articulatory complexity and its determining role in the production of misarticulated sounds. The findings indicate that complex sounds requiring refined motor control of the articulators are more likely to be produced incorrectly in dysarthric speech (Kim et al., 2010; Allison & Hustad, 2014). This theory is based on the principles of speech motor complexity described by Kent (1992a). His analysis of different studies suggests that sounds acquired early in life, such as /p, m, n, w, h/, involve less refined motor adjustments of velopharyngeal valving, voicing distinctions, and rate of lingual movement, than later acquired sounds such as /s, z, ʃ, v, θ, ð, tʃ, dʒ/, which require advanced coordination, refined adjustments of lingual position and fine force control over the articulators. Additionally, distortions in the manner and places of articulation or voicing characteristics are not consistently distributed, and certain categories are more error-prone than others across dysarthria types (Kim et al., 2010).

Findings across studies have reported higher error frequencies in the speech sound categories of fricative and affricate (manners of articulation) from adults with dysarthria secondary to

cerebral palsy (Ansel & Kent, 1992; Platt et al., 1980a; Platt, Andrews, & Howie, 1980b). Additionally, Platt et al. (1980a, 1980b) reported that errors in voicing and places of articulation such as labiodental, dental, and alveolar categories were more likely to occur compared to errors in the manner of articulation in the same group of speakers. Studies in Parkinson's disease have shown errors in the manner of articulation, such as incomplete closure in stop consonants (Logemann et al., 1978; Logemann & Fisher, 1981; Kent & Rosenbek, 1982; Ackerman & Ziegler, 1991). Voicing errors are also noticed within this population. Examples are devoicing of voiced stop consonants (Antolík & Fougeron, 2013, Duez, 2007), but the opposite is also evident, i.e., voiceless stops being realised fully or partially voiced (Kent & Rosenbek, 1982; Weismer, 1984).

Voicing errors are also present in dysarthria due to cerebellar ataxia, where devoicing of voiced consonants was also visible (Antolík & Fougeron, 2013). Other consonant distortions perceived in this population are the stops frequently described as fricated and unreleased (Kent, Netsell & Bauer, 1975). Subjects with dysarthria due to amyotrophic lateral sclerosis stand out with the more distorted consonants in the study of Antolík & Fougeron (2013). A frequent type of distortion within this group is the incomplete closure of stops (Antolík & Fougeron, 2013). Other types of distortions reported in this population include voicing of voiceless consonants (Antolík & Fougeron, 2013, Kent et al., 1990; Riddell et al., 1995), distortions in the manner of articulation, affecting stops, nasals and affricates consonants, and distortions in places of articulation such as alveolar and palatal (Kent et al., 1990, 1992).

Behavioural interventions for motor speech disorders are widely acknowledged for improving speech and communication in general (Duffy, 2020). A recently developed articulation therapy proved the value of a direct approach in improving the speech intelligibility of Dutch speakers with dysarthria (Mendoza et al., 2021a). Generally, intensive therapy has demonstrated to be effective in speech motor rehabilitation (Ramig et al., 2001a; Bhogal et al., 2003; Kwakkel, 2006; Rijntjes et al., 2009). Therefore, the need for intensive and frequent practice to reach better and more effective therapeutic results led to the development of an automatic tool that supports articulation therapy (Mendoza et al., 2021b). The technology-based intervention facilitates patients to work independently. The system includes models of target sound productions with audio-visual material, provides a well-structured package of exercises and adequate visual feedback on specific features in the production of the target phoneme based on acoustic algorithms. The automatic feedback is useful and essential for improving articulation, providing information about the utterance performance, in terms of manner and places of

articulation and voicing characteristics. Although the feedback already provided is highly informative, the patients would also benefit from feedback related to knowledge of results (KR). This type of feedback informs the extent to which a certain movement's goal has been accomplished (Maas et al., 2008; Gentile, 1972; Bakker et al., 2019). In the context of speech therapy, this result gives information about the quality of the speech outcome (Bakker et al., 2019). KR has the potential to inform about the accuracy of a certain target sound (phoneme) during speech production, which is crucial in this kind of intervention approach.

Since articulation is one of the speech dimensions that contribute significantly to speech intelligibility, thorough assessment and treatment of speech sound distortions are highly clinically relevant in patients with dysarthria. Perceptual evaluation of distortion, generally performed by means of narrow transcription, is threatened by reliability concerns and the inability of the human ear to capture the nature of the sound distortion (Tjaden, 2007). This stresses the need for an objective measure of overall and phoneme-specific (consonant) degree of distortion. This measure can be used as an essential outcome for detailed feedback during the speech training of speakers with dysarthria.

Previous attempts to develop an automatic measure of articulation errors at the phoneme level mainly relied on automatic speech recognition systems (Jiang, 2005; Pellegrini et al., 2014; Dudy et al., 2018). The Goodness of Pronunciation (GOP) algorithm is one of the best-known approaches (Witt, 1999; Witt & Young, 2000), giving an overall phone pronunciation quality. The GOP score is calculated based on the likelihood ratio that the realised phoneme corresponds to the phoneme that should have been pronounced according to the canonical pronunciation (Kanters, Cucchiariini & Strik, 2009). However, the robustness of the algorithms that calculate these measures requires further development (Pellegrini et al., 2014; Dudy et al., 2018; Bakker et al., 2019), especially when it comes to pathological speech (Rosen & Yampolsky, 2000; Pellegrini et al., 2014; Mustafa et al., 2015; Yilmaz et al., 2019; Rowe et al., 2022).

In this study, we explore a different approach for the automatic score of the degree of consonant distortion, a system based on a state-of-the-art gated recurrent neural network (Vásquez-Correa et al., 2019). This approach intends to map high-dimensional feature vectors into "phonological posteriors", which are phonological features represented by a vector with information about voicing characteristics, manner and places of articulation. These features are expected to characterise the phoneme realisations in a very precise and informative way. The same

algorithm was successfully applied in the study of Mendoza et al. (2021b) and García et al. (2021). The phoneme-specific acoustic features allowed for precise visual feedback in the VAT. However, the system does not provide any objective measure for the degree of phoneme distortion, and to the best of our knowledge, there is no similar measure for Dutch speakers affected with dysarthria. Therefore, this study would be the first attempt to develop an objective measure of the degree of consonant distortion. For that purpose, prediction models of phoneme distortion, specifically for dysarthric speech, will be developed. The reliability of the automatic measure will also be investigated. This type of automatic feedback at the phoneme level will allow the patients to increase their information on sound production. It may also be helpful in capturing subtle articulatory distortions and contribute to monitoring the improvement or deterioration of the speech of subjects with dysarthria.

Methods

Speech samples

The speech material analysed in this study is based on recordings of 12414 words collected from 35 participants, 13 women and 22 men—all adults with a diagnosis of chronic or progressive dysarthria due to neurogenic origin. Ages ranged from 28 to 89 years, with a mean age of 56 years. All participants were native speakers of Dutch and demonstrated sufficient reading, hearing, visual and cognitive skills (determined by the clinician) to perform the required tasks. Speakers were selected to represent a wide range of etiologies, dysarthria type and severity, which ranged from mild to severe. Information about each participant is presented in Table 4.1. The selected participants signed an informed consent approved by the University Hospital of Antwerp Ethics Committee.

The participants were recorded while reading a list of mono and bisyllabic words. The target phonemes were presented into initial, medial, and final positions within the stimulus words. The audio recordings were made in a quiet environment using (a high-quality headset microphone (Plantronics Blackwire 5210) positioned at a mouth distance of 5 cm, connected to a computer, and using the freely available software Audacity v.2.3.3 (sampling rate 44.1 kHz with 24-bit quantisation, mono) (Audacity Team 2019). All audios were resampled to 16 kHz in the processing stage.

Table 4.1. Description of the participants

	Sex	Age	Neurological pathology	Type of dysarthria	Severity dysarthria
1	M	56	Idiopathic	Flaccid	Mild
2	M	55	Cerebellar ataxia	Spastic	Mild
3	M	38	Steinert disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate
4	M	60	Idiopathic	Mixed	Severe
5	F	71	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate
6	F	84	ALS	Mixed	Severe
7	F	78	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
8	F	72	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Severe
9	F	75	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Mild
10	F	85	ALS	Mixed	Severe
11	M	35	Friedreich ataxia	Ataxic	Moderate
12	M	54	Steinert disease	Flaccid	Mild
13	F	38	Mitochondrial deficit	Mixed	Moderate
14	F	76	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
15	M	51	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Severe
16	M	56	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate
17	M	78	Stroke	Spastic	Moderate
18	M	78	Stroke	Spastic	Moderate
19	M	53	MS	Flaccid	Moderate
20	M	53	MS	Flaccid	Moderate
21	M	58	Stroke	Flaccid	Severe
22	F	43	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
23	F	43	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
24	M	28	Stroke	Ataxic	Moderate
25	M	46	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
26	M	46	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
27	F	35	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
28	F	35	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
29	M	33	MS	Mixed	Moderate
30	M	70	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate

31	M	48	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Severe
32	M	45	Toxoplasmosis	Spastic	Severe
33	M	68	Parkinson's disease	Hypokinetic	Moderate
34	F	89	Stroke	Flaccid	Moderate
35	M	33	MS	Mixed	Moderate

M: Male, F: Female, ALS: Amyotrophic Laterals Sclerosis, MS: Multiple sclerosis

Perceptual degree of sound distortion

The articulatory accuracy of the speech sound production was perceptually rated by three experienced speech-language pathologists (SLPs), who gave a score per target sound. They were instructed to evaluate the general degree of distortion of the target consonants on a visual analogue scale (VAS) varying from 0-10, with 0 being considered as 'correct' and 10 being 'severely distorted'. The precision of sound articulation was based on the manner of articulation, place of articulation, and voicing. The target phoneme was known to the judges, who could indicate the perceived degree of sound distortion on the VAS, but also had the opportunity to specify another error type in case of occurrence (omission, substitution, or addition). Judges were allowed to listen to each utterance only once. The final value of sound distortion for each target was calculated as the mean value of the independent measures given by the SLPs.

The inter-rater reliability was calculated using the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) index with SPSS (version 28).

Spoken corpus annotation

Once the perceptual scoring of the target phonemes was done, the speech samples were manually segmented and annotated using Praat, a freely available computer software package for speech analysis in phonetics (Boersma & Weenink, 2020). An example of the annotation procedure is illustrated in Figure 4.1. The annotated speech corpus is used for training the model to predict the degree of phoneme distortion in dysarthric speech. It can also be used for other research purposes in the field of pathological speech processing and technology.

Figure 4.1. Annotation of a speech sample (target phoneme) for articulation analysis. Annotation consisted of (1) the uttered word, (2) the target phoneme with boundaries, (3) the perceived error (in this case, Target phoneme distorted (TFd), other options are omission, substitution, or addition), (4) the mean value of distortion perceived by the professional judges, (5), (6) and (7) in case of substitution of the target phoneme, perceived phoneme by each listener.

Automatic evaluation of the degree of phoneme distortion

The proposed model for the objective assessment of the degree of phoneme distortion is shown in Figure 4.2. The automatic evaluation involves three main steps, (1) the front-end acoustic analysis of the speech signal, (2) the feature extraction for phoneme characterisation using a state-of-the-art neural network, and (3) the conversion of the feature vector to an objective score of the degree of articulatory distortion using a prediction model.

Figure 4.2. Block diagram of the proposed system for objective assessment of the articulatory degree of distortion.

Step 1: front-end acoustic analysis

The speech signal is first divided into segments of 500 ms in length and windowed into frames of 25 ms with a time shift of 10 ms. Every frame is then analysed and transformed into a feature sequence corresponding to the log-energy of the signal distributed into 33 triangular filters separated according to the Mel scale (Vasquez-Correa, 2019). This frame-level acoustic information of the speech signal represents the neural network's input layer that will generate phonological features related to the movements of the articulators in the vocal tract.

Step2: feature extraction

This study investigates a feature set that will be used for the characterisation of phonemes production. The feature set is expected to be a good representation of the speaker's performance in the different articulatory positions involved in speech. Furthermore, the feature set will be used as the input of the prediction model of the degree of distortion.

Phonological log-likelihood ratio features

In the feature extraction step, we want to map each frame's high-dimensional acoustic features (log Mel-filterbank energy features) into a new feature vector capable of describing the articulatory characteristics of the vocal tract during speech production, which can be more interpretable for clinicians and patients. For that purpose, we are using phonological features, which comprise information about the place and manner of articulation contained in the speech signal, together with voicing characteristics.

The system that maps the high-dimensional features to phonological features is a deep learning model based on recurrent neural networks (RNNs) with gated recurrent units (GRU), trained to detect the occurrence of the phonological classes. More detailed information about the neural network architecture can be found in Vasquez-Correa (2019). The model that extracts the phonological features from the speech signal was trained with Dutch-specific phonological characteristics (Verhoeven, 2005). As the purpose of an objective score of degree of distortion is to measure the deviation between dysarthric and healthy speech productions, the acoustic models were trained using healthy speech samples, specifically the read speech part of the Spoken Dutch Corpus (CGN) (Oostdijk and Broeder, 2003). After the training, the system is able to detect fifteen phonological classes plus silence. The model is highly accurate in detecting the different phonological classes, with the F-score ranging from 0.887 to 0.996

(Mendoza et al., 2021b). Table 4.2 shows the distribution of the phonemes in each of the 15 phonological classes and the model's class recognition accuracy.

Upon the manually segmented phonemes, the neural network system converts each set of log Mel-filterbank energies to phonological posteriors probabilities, and we end up with 15 features per frame. The new feature vector captures the posterior probability of a speech frame to belong to one or more phonological classes (e.g., plosive, voiced, bilabial).

The phonological log-likelihood ratio (PLLR) features are computed from the set of phonological posteriors. PLLR features have shown to be an effective way to convey frame-level acoustic-phonetic information in spoken language recognition (Diez et al., 2013a, 2014), in speaker recognition systems (Diez et al., 2013b) and for detecting native from non-native speakers (Abad et al., 2016). Considering the set of N phonological posteriors p_i , so that $\sum_{i=1}^N p_i = 1$ and $p_i \in [0, 1]$, the PLLR features are computed following Equation 1. The resulting feature space obtained from Equation 1 is bounded, as Diez et al. (2014) pointed out, which limits the features' distribution. Therefore, the next step is to project the PLLR features as described in (Diez et al., 2014), following Equation 2, where \mathbb{I} stands for Identity matrix and $\hat{\mathbf{1}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} [1_1, 1_2, \dots, 1_N]$.

$$r_i = \text{logit}(p_i) = \log \frac{p_i}{1-p_i} \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (1)$$

$$P = \mathbb{I} - \hat{\mathbf{1}}' * \hat{\mathbf{1}} \quad (2)$$

Upon the manually segmented phonemes, the 15 phonological posterior features per frame and their projected PLLR features are computed. Then, the mean value of the frame-level features assigned to one particular phoneme is calculated, ending with a vector of 15 PLLR features per target phoneme.

Table 4.2. Distribution of the Dutch phonemes into phonological classes

Phonological class	List of phonemes	Model performance (F-score)
Nasal	/m/ /n/ /ŋ/ /ɲ/	0.941
Plosive	/p/ /t/ /k/ /b/ /d/ /g/	0.917
Fricative	/f/ /v/ /s/ /ʃ/ /z/ /ʒ/ /x/ /ç/ /h/	0.940
Approximant	/w/ /j/ /l/	0.917
Trill	/r/ /ʀ/	0.949
Labial	/m/ /p/ /b/ /f/ /v/ /w/	0.927
Coronal	/n/ /t/ /d/ /z/ /ʒ/ /s/ /ʃ/ /j/ /r/ /l/	0.887

Dorsal	/ŋ/ /k/ /g/ /x/ /ç/ /R/ /j/	0.912
Glottal	/h/	0.984
Voice	/m/ /n/ /ŋ/ /b/ /d/ /g/ /v/ /z/ /ʒ/ /p/ /ç/ /t/ /R/ /w/ /j/ /l/ vowels	0.935
Vowel	/I/ /ɛ/ /ɑ/ /ɔ/ /ɹ/ /i/ /y/ /e:/ /ø:/ /a:/ /o:/ /u/ /ə/ /ɛi/ /œy/ /ɔu/ /ɛ:/ /œ:/ /ɔ:/ /ẽ/ /ã/ /õ/ /ẽ/	0.896
Bilabial	/m/ /p/ /b/ /w/	0.930
Labiodental	/f/ /v/	0.978
Alveolar	/t/ /d/ /n/ /r/ /s/ /z/ /l/	0.888
Postalveolar	/ʃ/ /ʒ/ /p/	0.996
Pause	/sil/	0.978

Step 3: articulation prediction models

Once the features are computed, the final step is to develop the model that will objectively predict the degree of phoneme distortion. In this study, we investigate different prediction models in order to select the most accurate for performing the task of scoring target phoneme production. We evaluate the performance of phoneme-dependent and phoneme-independent models, which are trained on dysarthric speech. Phoneme-dependent models are based on regression analysis of each phoneme independently, while phoneme-independent models are based on classification analysis including all the phonemes together.

Phoneme-dependent regression models

From the existing supervised machine learning algorithms, regression techniques are appropriate for getting continuous quantitative outcomes. Prediction models for scoring the degree of phoneme distortion of each individual target sound will be based on regression models. Multiple regression analyses were carried out to investigate whether the PLLR features could significantly predict objective scores of the degree of phoneme distortion. The descriptive statistics of all the phonemes that are used for training the models are presented in Table 4.3. In this study, we evaluate the performance of the different regression models of the regression learner app from Matlab (version R2019b). We can interactively train, validate, tune, and compare different regression models with that tool. It allows selecting the model that better fits the data without overfitting by applying cross-validation. There are multiple models implemented in the app: linear regression, regression trees, Gaussian process regression, support vector machines, kernel approximation, ensembles of regression trees, and neural network regression.

Evaluation metrics

It is a standard procedure to split the available data into training, validation and test sets to find a prediction model appropriate for the task. This procedure guarantees a better generalisation of the models to an independent data set. When the model performs well on a test set, then we are able to provide reliable predictions for new input samples. In this study, we use the k -fold cross validation (CV) method with $k=5$. CV is a resampling procedure used to evaluate the models on a limited database. During this procedure, the data are split into k equal groups, $k-1$ are used for training and the k th part for testing. This is repeated for all the combinations of $k-1$, leading to a final averaged estimate of the model's predictive performance. The model statistics (e.g., root mean squared error (RMSE), R-Squared) are computed using the observations in the k validation folds, and the average values are reported.

Performance measures

The root mean squared error (RMSE) and the R-Squared (R^2) metrics are used to evaluate the regression models' performance. The RMSE is an indicator of how concentrated the data is around the line of best fit. Low values of the RMSE are preferred, indicating a good fit between the model and the data; however, the values are scale-dependent. The coefficient of determination (R^2) explains the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable (the degree of distortion) that is predictable from the independent variables (15 PLLR features). The values of R^2 are between 0 and 1. Values closer to 1 indicate that more variability is explained by the model; therefore, it can better predict the outcome. For selecting the regression model with the best performance, we focused on the best overall scores of R^2 and RMSE.

Table 4.3. Descriptive Statistics of the target phonemes

Phonemes	Total (n)	VAS			
		Min	Max	Mean	Std
/w/	883	0	9	0.45	0.98
/j/	312	0	7	0.52	1.11
/f/	929	0	7.3	0.74	1.07
/n/	657	0	9.5	0.81	1.39
/g/	3	0.07	1.87	0.92	0.90
/l/	718	0	9	0.98	1.48

/z/	501	0	9	1.06	1.52
/v/	1158	0	9.9	1.11	2.09
/x/	346	0	9.5	1.25	1.56
/m/	185	0	9	1.29	1.85
/ɣ/	617	0	9.8	1.57	2.04
/ʃ/	83	0	7.8	1.64	1.83
/k/	119	0	9	1.67	2.00
/d/	490	0	10	1.68	1.84
/s/	801	0	9	1.75	1.81
/ɦ/	189	0.03	10	2.16	2.10
/b/	42	0.5	7	2.54	1.69
/ŋ/	28	0.37	8.5	2.68	1.93
/r/	1528	0.07	10	2.80	2.20
/t/	614	0	10	3.09	2.97
/p/	173	0	9.6	3.25	2.96

Phoneme-independent classification models

From supervised machine learning algorithms, classification techniques are appropriate for getting qualitative outcomes. Prediction models for scoring the degree of phoneme distortion of all the target sounds together will be based on classification models. In this case, we will split the original data into four categories according to the perceptual scores of the degree of distortion. Table 4.4 shows the distribution of the data within the new categories. Because some different categories are not well represented in the number of speech samples, we artificially enlarged the size by modifying acoustic parameters from the existing data. The applied augmentation techniques included pitch shifting, noise addition, and volume control in a probabilistic way. Specific information about the applied changes is shown in Table 4.5. In general, having a large dataset (original or using data augmentation) is crucial for the performance of classification models.

We will evaluate the performance of the different classification models of the classification learner app from Matlab (version R2019b). Multiple models are implemented in the app: decision trees, discriminant analysis, support vector machines, logistic regression, nearest neighbours, naive Bayes, kernel approximation, ensembles, and neural networks. After the

training and validation of the models, a comparison of their accuracies and validation errors is made in order to select the best model to perform this task.

Table 4.4. Categories of the degree of phoneme distortion

Categories	Interval of the degree of distortion	Number of samples (Original data)	Number of samples (Augmented data)
No distortion = 0	$d \leq 2$	7833	8937
Light distortion = 1	$2 < d \leq 5$	1761	7883
Moderate distortion = 2	$5 < d \leq 8$	547	5280
Severe distortion = 3	$d > 8$	235	2243

Table 4.5. Data augmentation pipeline

Parameters	Arguments
Augmentation mode	Sequential
Augmentation parameter source	Random
Time stretch probability	0
Pitch shift probability	0.5
Semitone shift range	[-2 2]
Volume control probability	0.5
Volume gain range	[-3 3]
Add noise probability	0.5
SNR range	[0 10]
Time shift probability	0

SNR: Signal-to-noise ratio

Evaluation metrics

In this part of the study, we will also use the five-fold cross-validation (CV) method to train and validate the model. The model statistics (e.g., prediction errors and accuracy) are computed using the observations in the k validation folds, and the average values are reported, offering an estimate of the model's predictive performance.

Performance measures

The total misclassification error rate (% of misclassified samples) and the accuracy metrics are used to evaluate the classification models' performance. Accuracy indicates the percentage of observations that are correctly classified. We also check the performance per class in the confusion matrix for a more detailed analysis of the models. For that purpose, True Positive Rates (TPR) and False Negative Rates (FNR) are analysed. TPR is defined as the proportion

of correctly classified observations per true class, while the FNR is the proportion of incorrectly classified observations per true class.

Results

For the perceptual degree of phoneme distortion measures, the three judges showed a good overall interrater reliability (ICC = 0.776, $p < 0.001$, 95% confidence interval (CI) = 0.758–0.792).

Articulation prediction models

After training and validating different models for predicting the degree of articulatory distortion in target phonemes and using two different feature sets, the results of the best prediction models are presented as follows.

Phoneme-dependent regression models

The results of the multiple regression analyses to predict the degree of phoneme distortion are presented in appendix B showing an overview of the different regression models' performance.

The Gaussian process regression (GPR) models showed, in general, better results compared to linear regression models, regression trees, support vector machines, and ensembles of trees. The GPR models are powerful, nonparametric kernel-based probabilistic models, in which the covariance function expresses the expectation that points with similar predictor values will have similar response values. Analysing the performance of these models for each phoneme independently, the R^2 metric ranged from -0.03 to 0.67 using the PLLR features. The results of the regression for the majority of the phonemes indicate that the models explained only a low percentage of the variance in the outcome variable (degree of distortion). Only for the phoneme /v/ the model explains 67% of the variance, showing the best results. The RMSE for the GPR models ranged from 0.92 to 2.74, indicating that the models cannot predict the outcome accurately.

Phoneme-independent classification models

For selecting the classification model that better predicts the degree of distortion, we focused not only on the best overall scores but also on having good and balanced scores for the individual categories. Table 4.6 shows the overall performances of the different models that were trained and evaluated.

The selected classification model is Ensemble Subspace KNN, which uses random subspace ensembles to improve the accuracy of k-nearest neighbour (KNN) classifiers. This model showed an overall accuracy of 73.5% using the PLLR features, with a total misclassification cost of 26.46 %. From the confusion matrix (Figure 4.3), we have TPR that ranges from 61% to 78% for the individual categories, and FNR range from 39% to 22%.

Table 4.6. Classification model's performance

Model Type	Accuracy (%)	Misclassification rate (%)
<i>Decision Trees classifiers</i>		
Fine Tree	49.8	50.21
Medium Tree	47.4	52.61
Coarse Tree	46	53.96
<i>Discriminant Analysis classifiers</i>		
Linear Discriminant	47	52.97
<i>Naive Bayes Classifiers</i>		
Gaussian Naive Bayes	44	55.96
Kernel Naive Bayes	46	54.02
<i>Support Vector Machines classifiers</i>		
Linear SVM	46.4	53.60
Quadratic SVM	51.9	48.09
Cubic SVM	59.3	40.71
Fine Gaussian SVM	71.5	28.45
Medium Gaussian SVM	53.6	46.37
Coarse Gaussian SVM	48	52.00
<i>Nearest Neighbour classifiers</i>		
Fine KNN	70.3	29.73
Medium KNN	60.4	39.62
Coarse KNN	52.4	47.64
Cosine KNN	59.4	40.56
Cubic KNN	60.5	39.46
Weighted KNN	69.9	30.13
<i>Ensemble classifiers</i>		
Boosted Trees	48.1	51.88
Bagged Trees	70.9	29.12
Subspace Discriminant	46.9	53.11
Subspace KNN	73.5	26.46
RUSBoosted Trees	45.2	54.76

Figure 4.3. Confusion matrix of the Ensemble classifier Subspace KNN. The classes are: 0=no distortion, 1= light distortion, 2= moderate distortion and 3= severe distortion.

Discussion

Imprecise articulation is one of the main problems of dysarthric speech that significantly reduce intelligibility. The major novelty of the present study is the development of an objective estimation of articulatory distortion at the phoneme level that targets a more detailed characterisation of the patient's performance. The predicted score is based on calculations of articulatory insufficiencies in the manner of articulation, place of articulation and voicing present in particular sounds. Furthermore, this objective measure can contribute to automatic feedback in virtual articulation therapy systems, providing the patients with an estimation of the achieved accuracy in specific phonemes or target sounds during speech production (KR-feedback).

Because so many variables can interfere with a precise production of articulation, it is very challenging to accurately and adequately measure the degree of distortion present in a specific sound. The automated articulation score, developed in this study using articulatory-based acoustic features, may provide more specific and detailed information about speech errors, helping to detect phoneme distortions. However, this implies that the predictive models responsible for detecting the articulatory deficiencies were hard to train due to the requirement of a large number of training samples and specific acoustic features required for the task. Another important fact is that the reference ratings of these deficiencies from human raters are found to be less reliable (even if the ICC shows good reliability). The fact that the clinicians

know the target phoneme makes possible an overestimation of the patient's production accuracy, which means that the available reference ratings must be treated with care.

It is noticeable to mention that the feature set applied in this study contains important phonological information. The phonological classes on which the systems were trained are mainly related to consonants, which are seen as the primary information-bearing elements of speech (Tjaden, 2007). Most of the time spent in articulation training is devoted to consonants, which make use of all the articulators and articulatory options. Another important point of this study is that the prediction models trained for detecting consonant distortion in dysarthric speech included participants with all different levels of severity (from mild to severe cases), which makes it more robust.

The results related to the phoneme-dependent prediction of articulatory distortion (presented in appendix B) show the performance of the regression models (GPR) that better fits the data. Although, for some particular cases, the R^2 performance metric is higher than 0.5 with the models trained using the PLLR feature set, there is a significant deviation between perceived and predicted scores for most of the individual phonemes. The reason could be an insufficient number of samples per specific phoneme due to non-equal frequency of sound and sound errors. In general, we can conclude that phoneme-dependent regression models were inaccurate in predicting the degree of distortion at the phoneme level. Further research with a more proportional distribution of phonemes is necessary to shed some light on this topic.

On the other hand, the results related to the phoneme-independent classification of articulatory distortion show good accuracies in model performance. Using the PLLR feature set, the Ensemble classifier -subspace KNN- can predict the degree of distortion with an accuracy of 73.5%. It also shows good performances for the four individual categories (from 'no distortion' to 'severe distortion'). These results are comparable to similar metrics based on ASR, which are also used to detect mispronunciations in disordered speech. This is the case of the study carried out by Pellegrini et al. (2014), where the system reached an accuracy of 70.2% in a population affected with unilateral facial palsy. Note that the availability of studies addressing the development of automated articulatory assessments on dysarthric speech is very limited.

Although the classification model developed in this study achieved a good accuracy, the model might not be sensitive to small changes in a patient's articulation, achieved by either spontaneous recovery or progression after therapy. Nevertheless, the automatic feedback might contribute to an effective and more motivating speech articulation therapy.

An observation of the misclassified phoneme distortion learns that mainly the final consonants show a risk of being misclassified by the system. Therefore, this pattern has to be further investigated.

Despite the need for further refinements of the prediction models, the proposed articulatory measure shows promise in determining the degree of phoneme distortion in dysarthric speech, which is of high clinical value. The automated score might increase the quality of healthcare by notably diminishing the time necessary for scoring the substantial amount of speech samples that comes with articulation therapy and will reduce the bias of listeners' subjectivity. This allows for more effective therapy with clear and objective feedback. In addition, the objective speech score proposed in this study allows the clinician to map high-dimensional acoustic characteristics with distinctive phoneme features. Such an approach has value in identifying sound segments with incorrect production of speech sounds due to slight changes in place and manners of articulation or voicing.

Limitations

The analysis of individual phonemes in isolated words may not reflect coarticulation errors that are present in connected speech. Although the accuracy of the classification system is good, there is a further need for improvement. In this sense, combining the existing features with other spectral and cepstral features might be an option. Another problem to consider is whether the developed method will be sufficient for tracking the progression of a subject in the course of therapy. In this regard, extending the database with more samples to train the classification model will allow increasing the number of categories.

Conclusions

The articulation model developed in this study, based on PLLR features and using an Ensemble classifier -subspace KNN- allows for a reliable and objective scoring of the degree of distortion at the phoneme level in dysarthric speech (from slightly to severely distorted sounds). The results indicate a good accuracy of the phoneme-independent classification model in predicting the degree of distortion across different etiologies and dysarthria severity levels. Optimising the classification model's accuracy will be the focus of future research. However, the model's current performance is considered sufficiently reliable for its implementation as part of the automatic feedback in virtual articulation therapy, a clinical tool for articulation rehabilitation of Dutch speakers with dysarthria.

PART 3

PROSODY

CHAPTER 5

Acoustic features to characterize sentence accent production in dysarthric speech

This chapter has been published in

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Abstract

Background

In oral communication, adequate accent placement for highlighting important information in an utterance is essential for the efficient conveyance of meaning. Whilst initial descriptions of accent production in the literature are mainly based on perceptual evaluations, acoustic methods have significantly contributed to the description and better understanding of this communicative function, providing quantifiable support to the perceptual judgments of clinically relevant characteristics.

Aims

This study investigated acoustic features and prosodic strategies used by both healthy speakers and speakers with dysarthria, to produce a perceptually-detectable sentence accent.

Methods & Procedures

Accordingly, 80 adult speakers (50 with a speech impairment) were asked to produce 3 pairs of sentences with different accent positions. All speech samples were perceptually judged by three experts, and were acoustically analyzed. The fundamental frequency, intensity, and duration were not only analyzed within the syllable, but also in contrast with the previous syllable, and in contrast with the entire sentence. These features were used as input for a linear discriminant analysis.

Outcomes & Results

This newly-developed acoustic approach reveals that healthy speakers mainly rely on the following features to produce a perceptually-detectable accent: a change in frequency within the target syllable, with a simultaneous increase of intensity and contrast in the frequency between the target syllable and the previous syllable. Speakers with dysarthria mainly use the contrast in frequency and intensity between the target syllable and the previous syllable, rather than the contrasting with the rest of the sentence. They also use durational parameters as an element in prosodic accent production. Although both groups use some common features, they differ significantly ($p < 0.01$) in the way they realize accent production.

Conclusions & Implications

The results of this study show that sentence accent production in dysarthric speech can be adequately described by a set of acoustic features. Until now, such description in the literature

was primarily based on perceptual evaluations. The current approach may assist in objective assessments and more appropriate therapy methods.

Introduction

In contrast to written communication, oral communication carries supplementary information by means of acoustic changes in speech production. This constitutes the so-called suprasegmental level of speech, described generally as “prosody”. A description of prosody and its role in human communication is provided by Boutsen (2003), who defines prosody as “a tool of human expression that is conveyed acoustically by way of durational, intensity, and frequency cues.”

Prosodic disorders are reported in a significant number of clinical conditions, (Stojanovik & Setter, 2011) such as autism, foreign accent syndrome, hearing loss, and dysarthria (Peppé et al., 2011; Peppé, 2011; Kuschmann et al., 2012; Chin, Bergeson & Phan, 2012; MacPherson, Huber & Snow, 2011; Martens et al., 2011; Casper et al., 2007). Dysprosody has a negative impact on speech intelligibility and the comprehensibility of oral communication, and is evident in each type of dysarthria identified by Darley et al. (1975) and De Bodt et al. (2002). The aim of our research is to improve the knowledge about dysarthric speech production. The principal population in this study are Dutch speakers affected with dysarthria.

One of the prosodic functions in Dutch is sentence focus, defined as the ability of a speaker to highlight the most important information of an utterance (Rietveld & Van Heuven, 2009). This communicative function is recognized as an important aspect of functional rehabilitation at all dysarthria severity levels, by means of sentence accent tasks (Martens et al., 2013, 2015).

The acoustics of sentence accent production in normal speech generally correlate with changes in fundamental frequency (F0) (Fry, 1958; Rietveld & Gussenhoven, 1985). In Dutch, these F0 movements, along with overall intensity, differentiate between accented and non-accented syllables in the intonation contour of the utterance (Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996a; Astruc & Prieto, 2006). Owing to the impairments involved in dysarthric speech, including little or no control over F0 movements, accent production in this population is achieved by a combination of changes in F0, intensity, and duration (Martens et al., 2011; Patel & Campellone, 2009; Lowit, Kuschmann & Kavanagh, 2014). However, in both populations, it is unclear how the differences between accented and non-accented syllables are objectively expressed, and how these changes in F0, intensity, and duration are related to the sentence and to the preceding segment of the accent location. This is what the present study aims to clarify.

Currently, auditory perceptual methods for characterizing prosodic communicative efficiency in dysarthria remain the “gold standard” in clinical practice (Penttilä, Korpijaakko-Huuhka &

Kent, 2018). However, acoustic analyses have proven their value for a more complete understanding of motor speech disorders, contributing with the quantification and description of clinically-perceived deviant speech. They provide confirmatory support for perceptual judgments (Martens et al., 2013; Duffy, 2013). Therefore, we focus on acoustic analyses of dysarthric speech.

Previous research using acoustic features to characterize sentence accent production in normal speech has been conducted, with significant value. A study by Streefkerk, et al. (Streefkerk, Pols, & Bosch, 1999) on Dutch sentences detected prominent words using a set of features concerning F0, energy, and duration. Similarly, Avanzi et al. (2010) detected syllabic prominence in spontaneous French by means of F0, duration, and pause. Studies for detecting prominence in English (Mahrt et al., 2011, 2012a, 2012b) included those concerning pitch, duration, and intensity measures. Tamburini (2006) made use of F0 movements, overall syllable energy, syllable nuclei duration, and mid-to-high-frequency emphasis. Cutugno et al. (2012) used features related to pitch movements, energy, and the duration of a syllable and its neighbors for the detection of prominent syllables in English and Italian. For Brazilian Portuguese, Johnson & Kang (2015) detected prominent syllables using pitch, intensity, and duration as acoustic features. These studies show that some machine learning classifiers and acoustic features have been employed to detect various types of prominence. Nevertheless, a more thorough understanding of this prosodic function and the strategies used by healthy speakers could be of scientific and clinical interest.

In contrast, research on the acoustic features of prosody in pathological speech is rather scarce. Dysarthric speech is very inconsistent in many ways, and needs specifically-designed methods that consider, e.g., the absence of voice, a lack of articulatory landmarks, and low intensity. However, a perceptual acoustic characterization of sentence accent production has been performed, with remarkable value. The study of Lowit, et al. (2010) analyzes F0, intensity, and duration measures for sentence stress targets, showing that a considerable number of speakers with ataxic dysarthria experience problems in signaling stress, leading to the particular use of F0 modulations and pauses to compensate for the impaired ability to use the other acoustic correlates of sentence stress. Similar results are shown in a study of children with dysarthria and cerebral palsy, where these children only manipulate changes in duration to mark sentence stress (Kuschmann & Lowit, 2019). In addition, digital manipulation of stress parameters in ataxic dysarthria shows that smaller increases in duration and intensity result in significant improvements in listener accuracy (Lowit et al., 2018). Overall intensity shows the best results.

Pitch contour modifications also show significant improvements, but are not comparable with intensity. Integration of stress parameters shows better outcomes when combined with pitch contour modifications (Lowit et al., 2018).

However, a thorough comprehension of the prosodic strategies used by patients with dysarthria could be facilitated with an objective assessment of this prosodic function. A literature review on the characterization and assessment of atypical prosody shows a need for more research in this domain (Diehl & Paul, 2009; Hargrove, Anderson & Jones, 2009; Peppé, 2009).

An overview of the acoustic measures reported to be useful for the assessment of prosody in motor speech disorders is provided by Shahin et al. (2015) and Patel (2011), who draw attention to the particular challenges for dysarthric speech, such as F0 tracking in individuals with speech impairment, the presence of pitch breaks, and hypernasality. This overview addresses the assessment of prosody and supports the introduction of acoustic measures in clinical practice, if they are time-efficient and complement the perceptual measures. The analysis of accent patterns adds to the understanding of the nature of dysarthric speech and deviant and inefficient prosodic accent (Van Nuffelen, 2011), and aids in determining the remaining acoustical cues for accent in the speech of patients susceptible for therapy.

The current state of the art regarding sentence accent production in dysarthric speech is based on perceptual analysis. Thus, at present, an adequate objective approach is missing. Therefore, it is necessary to develop appropriate measures to support auditory perceptual assessment, and to develop personalized therapy methods. The hypothesis of this study is that sentence accent production in dysarthric speech can be adequately described by a set of acoustic features.

The goals of this research are as follows:

- (1) To identify the relevant acoustic features of sentence accent production, related to the fundamental frequency, intensity, and duration within the syllable, in contrast with the previous syllable, and also in contrast with the entire sentence. These features should enable a classification of accent production for dysarthric and healthy speakers of Dutch.
- (2) To objectively demonstrate the similarities and differences between healthy speakers and speakers with dysarthria in sentence accent production.

Methods

Speech samples

Speech samples were selected from the “Computerized Assessment and Treatment of Rate, Intonation, and Stress” (CATRIS) corpus (Martens et al., 2013), which was composed for prosody research. All speakers in this database are adult native speakers of Dutch (with and without dysarthria), with different regional accents and a variety of dysarthria severities, rated on a four-point grading scale (0 = normal; 1 = mild; 2 = moderate; 3 = severe) by three experienced speech-language pathologists. The characteristics of the 80 selected speakers (30 healthy speakers and 50 speakers with dysarthria) are listed in Table 5.1.

For this study, only sentences from the focus function were used. The focus tasks consist of sentence pairs, with each sentence having a different accented word (see Table 5.2). The same three pairs of sentences were selected for every subject (a total of 180 and 300 sentences for the healthy and dysarthric groups, respectively). In this test, participants were instructed to stress the typographically-highlighted word.

Table 5.1. Characteristics of the speakers selected from CATRIS database for the experiment.

Group	Number	Sex		Severity		
		F	M	1	2	3
Dysarthric	50	19	31	30	13	7
Healthy	30	20	10	-	-	-

Note. F: female; M: male; Severity of dysarthria scale: 1 = mild; 2 = moderate; 3 = severe.

Table 5.2. Focus Sentences used in the experiment, adapted from (Martens et al., 2011).

(S1a) Ze wil geen telefoon meer krijgen. <i>She doesn't want to get any more calls.</i>	(S1b) Ze wil geen telefoon meer krijgen. <i>She doesn't want to get any more calls.</i>
(S2a) Luc werkt in het ziekenhuis. <i>Luke works at the hospital.</i>	(S2b) Luc werkt in het ziekenhuis . <i>Luke works at the hospital.</i>
(S3a) Misschien heeft Piet vakantie. <i>Maybe Pete's on holiday.</i>	(S3b) Misschien heeft Piet vakantie . <i>Maybe Pete's on holiday.</i>

Note. English translations in italics.

Acoustic analysis

The principal steps towards an objective acoustic classification of sentence accent production are shown in Figure 5.1. First, the speech signal is analyzed by the “CONTOUR” algorithm (Martens et al., 2015; Gonzalez-Moreira et al., 2015) to detect the syllabic nucleus, which is the place where the pitch perception is acoustically present. This phenomenon is influenced by the boundaries, as spectral and intensity changes occur at the consonant (House, 1995). The syllabic boundary is more evident for stops and fricatives, and less significant for liquids and nasals (Mertens, 2004). The algorithm extracts time duration, energy, and F0 for the syllabic nucleus. From these acoustic descriptors, feature sets that characterize the utterance are calculated. These feature sets, together with a perceptual evaluation of the syllables, are input to linear discriminant analysis (LDA) (McLachlan, 2004). LDA determines the relevant features for distinguishing accent production between healthy speakers and those with dysarthria. Each step of the diagram is explained in the following paragraphs.

Figure 5.1. Block diagram of extraction of relevant acoustic features to detect sentence accent.

In the present study, the acoustic analysis is performed with MatLab software (version 2010). The CONTOUR algorithm was employed to obtain a group of parameters from an isolated sentence (Martens et al., 2015; Gonzalez-Moreira et al., 2015). These parameters provide an estimate of the duration, normalized intensity (relative to the maximum amplitude value), and the fundamental frequency of the syllable nucleus, for each syllable. Figure 5.2 shows the analysis of a sentence from a speaker with dysarthria. The normalized intensity, F0 contour, and duration of the vowel nucleus are automatically determined by the algorithm. The results for all the samples are checked, and are manually corrected if necessary. This implementation offers the possibility of manually checking the detected syllables and correcting them in cases of omission or insertion errors. Then, the feature sets are recalculated. These corrections are meant to avoid further mistakes in the following steps of the study.

Figure 5.2. Outcome parameters of the CONTOUR algorithm over the spectrogram for the S2 from the Patient D13. The dashed blue line represents normalized intensity. The continuous red line represents fundamental frequency (F0). The landmarks: [*] refers to the maximum intensity value in the syllable, [+ (upper in green/lower in red)] refer to initial and final boundaries of the syllable nucleus.

Contour algorithm

The CONTOUR algorithm is mainly based on a method described by Wang & Narayanan (2007b). The original algorithm was designed for speech rate estimation. In our study, it was adjusted to measure syllabic parameters for accent detection. The modifications were necessary to detect the syllable nuclei automatically, and to calculate its fundamental frequency values in semitones and its normalized energy envelope. The procedure is described in the following paragraph, and is illustrated in Figure 5.3.

The speech signal passes through a filter bank (19 channels). Subsequently, only 12 of the top bands with higher energy content are selected and retained for processing. These bands contain the formant structure and highlight the vowel over the consonants; therefore, a maximum is associated with the syllable nuclei, whereas a minimum is emphasized near the edge of the syllable. Then, a Gaussian weighting window is applied to the temporal frames to emphasize intersyllabic discontinuities. In this study, a window size of 10 ms and 5 ms overlapping are selected. Both parameters were modified from the original algorithm, with the purpose of generating an envelope with better resolution than in the original design. Temporal correlation is then applied to each channel, to address the windowing effect of the envelope. The resulting subbands' energy vectors are cross-correlated. After these steps, we have a one-dimensional

envelope, which may contain local spurious peaks. Therefore, a smoothing step is required. In this case, a standard Gaussian filtering method is used. Finally, the syllabic nuclei are detected using the same threshold mechanism described in the peak counting stage (Wang & Narayanan, 2007b). The boundaries of the syllable nucleus are defined by the nearest minimum of the energy envelope, which are related to the vowel edges, or by vocal activity limits calculated with the robust algorithm for pitch tracking (RAPT) (Talkin, 1995). The next steps of feature generation shown in Figure 5.3 are explained in the following section.

Figure 5.3. Block diagram of the CONTOUR algorithm (adapted from Wang & Narayanan (2007b)) and feature sets generation.

Acoustic features

For each syllable nucleus, several features related to measures of duration, fundamental frequency (F0), and intensity are estimated from the energy envelope. The newly-developed feature sets are explained in detail in the next paragraphs. Duration is given in milliseconds (ms), and fundamental frequency is given in semitones (ST), a gender-independent unit suggested by t'Hart et al. (1990). Intensity is a parameter that is normalized with respect to the maximum amplitude value. Previous works suggest the use of intensity and F0 for accent discrimination (Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996a; Astruc & Prieto, 2006; Beckman & Pierrehumbert, 1986). However, even though it is well-known that using syllable duration is optional when it comes to indicating the presence of accent (Astruc & Prieto, 2006), it was included in the analysis. This is because people diagnosed with severe dysarthria have some degree of control over this parameter (Patel, 2002a), and it could be used to highlight the accented syllables.

We generated 20 features from the syllable nuclei for each sentence. They were divided into three different groups, as summarized in Table 5.3: (1) the syllable's inherent parameters, (2) the parameters of the syllable in contrast with the previous syllable, and (3) the parameters of the syllable in contrast with the sentence. This classification assumed that an accented syllable has values that differ from the rest of the utterance. The proposed feature sets are defined as follows:

1st Feature set: parameters inherent to the syllable

This group of parameters consists of seven features. The first three features are related to important changes of F0 values in the syllable nucleus (t'Hart, 1981), i.e.:

F0max - the maximum of F0 values;

F0min - the minimum of F0 values; and

$\Delta F0$ - the difference between the initial and the final value of F0 within the syllable nucleus.

The remaining features include:

D - duration, associated with the time length of the syllable nucleus;

Int - maximum intensity, related to the formant structure and the energy of the syllable nucleus;

F0&Int - the interaction of F0max minus F0min multiplied by Int, adapted from Tykalova et al. (2014), where the combination of F0 and intensity is used for stress discrimination between normal speakers and speakers with Parkinson's disease; and

Slope - the ratio between the difference of F0max and F0min with D, adapted from Mertens (2004), where the perception of pitch changes is weighted by a temporal factor.

2nd Feature set: parameters in contrast to the previous syllable

This set of six features is based on the differences between the syllable's inherent parameters and those of the previous syllable. Therefore, we consider:

dF0max - the difference between the F0max of the current syllable with that of the previous one;

dF0min - the difference between the F0min of the current syllable with that of the previous one; and

dInt - the difference between Int of the current syllable and that of the previous one.

In addition, we analyze the duration difference (dD) in three different ways:

dD - the difference between D of the current syllable and that of the previous one;

dDrange - dD normalized to the range of all dD values in the sentence; and

dDmax - dD normalized to the maximum value of dD in the sentence.

In the case of the first syllable, we use the second syllable as the previous syllable (like a mirror), because the difference is the key function in this analysis.

3rd Feature set: parameters in contrast to the sentence

It is necessary to consider the relationship of each syllable with the rest of the sentence, as experience with subjective evaluation suggests that the accented syllable must somehow be different from the rest of the sentence. Therefore, seven parameters that are in contrast to the sentence are included. For each syllable, we consider the difference between the inherent parameter values and the median of the parameter values of the whole sentence. The median is selected because it is a better estimator of the central tendency than the mean for small samples (Schultz et al., 2007). From this point of view, the designed features are:

F0maxM - the difference between F0max and its median;

F0minM - the difference between F0min and its median;

IntM - the difference between Int and its median;

Dmsyl - the difference between D and its median divided by the number of syllables in the sentence;

Dm - the normalized D with respect to the median of all of the D values in the sentence;

Drange - the normalized D with respect to the range of all of the D values in the sentence; and

Dmax - the normalized D with respect to the maximum of all of the D values in the sentence.

The complete list of parameters is summarized in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3. Summary of the features associated with each syllable to characterize the accent.

Parameters related to	Inherent to the syllable	In contrast to the previous syllable	In contrast to the sentence
F0	F0max; F0min; $\Delta F0$	dF0max; dF0min	F0maxM; F0minM
Intensity	Int	dInt	IntM
Duration	D	dD; dDrange; dDmax;	Dmsyl; Dm; Drange; Dmax;
Interaction	F0∬ Slope	-	-

Automatic classification and statistical analysis

Automatic classification and statistical analysis are performed to find the meaningful differences in the acoustic features of the accentuation process of speakers with and without dysarthria. A total of 3586 syllables were perceptually classified into two categories: ‘accented’ and ‘unaccented’. This perceptual evaluation of each syllable was performed by three experienced clinicians who independently marked the accented syllables. Subsequently, the individual evaluations were conflated by a majority rule: if at least two judges had assigned the label ‘accented’ to a particular syllable, that label was retained. Table 5.4 summarizes the number of manually-classified syllables.

Table 5.4. Number of accented and unaccented syllables for each of the analyzed groups.

Syllables	Speaker population	
	Healthy	Dysarthric
Accented	197	338
Unaccented	1160	1891
Total	1357	2229

To detect the significant features related to accentuation patterns, we selected LDA (McLachlan, 2004). This technique is considered one of the most well-used data reduction procedures (Tharwat et al., 2017), and it has been widely applied in speech processing (Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996a, 1996b; Astruc & Prieto, 2006). LDA transforms the feature sets into a lower-dimensional space, warranting maximum class separability between accented and

unaccented syllables. For this study, a stepwise variable selection method with Wilks's Lambda criteria was selected, to indicate the optimal features with higher discriminative ability (Klecka, 1980).

LDA allows for data classification in addition to dimensionality reduction. The supervised classifier is trained based on the perceptual judgments (Table 5.4) together with the extracted acoustic features (Table 5.3), using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software (version 21). This procedure is used for analyzing the differences between the two groups of syllables (accented and unaccented) with respect to several variables simultaneously, determining if meaningful differences exist between the groups, and identifying the contribution of each variable. Moreover, it is employed to classify the syllables into groups. The classification is carried out independently for healthy speakers and speakers with dysarthria. This analysis aims to look for potential differences in the accentuation process of speakers with and without dysarthria.

A hypothesis test was performed by means of a two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Schultz et al., 2007), to compare the distributions of the common features in both groups of accented syllables produced by healthy and dysarthric subjects. The two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is sensitive to differences in both the location and shape of the empirical cumulative distribution functions of the two samples. A significance level of 0.01 was used. The null hypothesis (H_0) is that features for both groups are from the same continuous distribution, meaning that no differences in accent production are found. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that they are from different continuous distributions, meaning that common features found in both populations are used in a different way to produce sentence accent.

Results

Strategies used by persons with and without dysarthria to produce accent

The LDA shows the standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients, expressing the contribution of each variable to the classification model. These results point out the relevant acoustic features predominantly used to produce accent in Dutch. These discriminative parameters are listed in Table 5.5.

To produce contrastive stress, healthy speakers seem to better control F_0 and intensity changes (F_0 &Int, ΔF_0) within the target syllable; these efforts are supported by an increase of F_0 (dF_0 max and dF_0 min) in relation to the previous syllable. The target syllable is also highlighted

in contrast to the sentence by means of intensity (IntM) and fundamental frequency (F0maxM), and is further characterized by its different duration as compared to the median of the durations (Dmax).

The group of speakers with dysarthria seems to combine more strategies to produce contrastive stress. Within the relevant acoustic features employed by this group, we found that along with the features used by the healthy population, speakers with dysarthria also use Int, dInt, dDrange, and Dm.

The most common strategy followed by this group of speakers to produce accent in Dutch is the contrast of F0max with the previous syllable (dF0max). The intensity is remarkably different from the rest of the sentence (IntM). As compared with the healthy group, they show more strategies related to duration (dDrange, Dm) and intensity (Int, dInt). Moreover, some of the speakers in this group are able to use the same strategies as healthy speakers (F0&Int, ΔF0), as most of them are diagnosed with mild dysarthria.

When the complete population is classified, common features of both groups are detected. In this case, the stronger predictors of accent are F0&Int and dF0max, followed by IntM. This means that both groups seem to use F0 and intensity changes within the target syllable, as well as the contrast of the maximum F0 with the previous syllable and an intensity contrast with the rest of the sentence, albeit possibly in different ways.

Table 5.5. Standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients of the relevant features for the speaker groups.

Parameters	Healthy	Dysarthric
Inherent to the syllable		
ΔF0	0.260	0.161
Int	-	0.179
F0&Int	0.405	0.275
In contrast to the previous syllable		
dF0max	-0.383	-0.436
dF0min	-0.165	-0.158
dInt	-	0.083
dDrange	-	0.112
In contrast to the sentence		
F0maxM	0.234	0.115

IntM	0.212	0.316
Dm	-	0.168
Dmax	0.148	-

Note: Coefficients with the highest impact are printed in bold.

Identification of accented and unaccented syllables by Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)

The characterization of a syllable, as the accent carrier of a contrastive sentence, is completely described by the feature set resulting from the LDA analysis. The correct classification of accented versus unaccented syllables for each group (in %) is shown in Figure 5.4.

The results of this classification are highly accurate for discriminating between accented and unaccented syllables in both normal and disrupted speech. It shows that the proposed objective features properly describe the strategies used by the speakers to produce accent.

Figure 5.4. Percentage of syllables correctly classified.

Table 5.6 shows the confusion matrix and confidence interval, summarizing the percentages of classification for accented and unaccented syllables. From these results, it can be inferred that in the worst possible case of the dysarthric group of speakers, the percentage of correct classification between accented and unaccented syllables can reach values above 78.8% if the proposed features are used. This finding shows good accuracy for detecting strategies for accent production.

Table 5.6. Confusion matrix and 95% confidence interval (C. I.) for the classification of the results.

LDA	Predicted Group Membership		C.I.
	Unaccented	Accented	
Syllables	Healthy speakers		
Accented	12.7%	87.3%	82.66-91.96
Unaccented	96.6%	3.4%	95.60-97.68
	Dysarthric speakers		
Accented	17.2%	82.8%	78.82-86.86
Unaccented	90.5%	9.5%	89.21-91.85

The LDA analysis confirms the presence of common features for both groups (see Table 5.5). The results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the common features (listed in Table 5.7) show that five of the six common features are statistically distinctive for each group, and only one, dF0min, shows no statistical difference for both distributions ($p = 0.470$). For cases where $p < 0.001$, the alternative hypothesis (H1) was accepted, meaning that common features are used in a different way for both populations to produce sentence accent.

Table 5.7. Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the common features in both speaker groups.

Features	Hypothesis	Significance (p)
$\Delta F0$	H ₁ (alternative)	$p < 0.001$
F0&Int	H ₁	$p < 0.001$
dF0min	H ₀ (null)	0.470
dF0max	H ₁	$p < 0.001$
F0maxM	H ₁	$p < 0.001$
IntM	H ₁	$p < 0.010$

Discussion

The accent in a sentence is determined by the communicative intention of the speaker. Therefore, the parameters derived from changes in fundamental frequency, intensity, and duration are controlled by the speaker to produce the desired focus. As demonstrated in this research, healthy speakers of Dutch use a pool of mechanisms to produce the desired accent in

a sentence. In that regard, fast variations in F0 are the dominant feature. This is expressed by (1) the increment of F0 during the utterance of the accented syllable, (2) a rise of the minimum and the maximum values of F0 in the target syllable in contrast with the previous one, (3) the production of the absolute maximum value of F0 in the target syllable, and (4) a significant difference between the F0 maximum and minimum values within the target syllable, supported by extra intensity. Moreover, this group of speakers uses an intensity contrast between the accented syllable and the rest of the sentence, as well as an increase of the syllable nucleus duration (which seems to play a minor role). Nevertheless, it is noticeable that more than one mechanism coexists for accent production. These findings agree with the results of Sluijter & Van Heuven (1996a, 1996b), where overall intensity and F0 were found as correlates of accent, and where accented words showed longer syllables. The present research provides a more detailed description, from an acoustical perspective, of those perceptually-based relationships described in the literature.

It is remarkable to point out that all of the selected features capable of describing accent (Table 5.5) are derived from frequency, intensity, and duration, but they are not the absolute values of these acoustic measures, which are not able to identify accent production by themselves. This can be the explanation why in the study of Tykalova et al. (2014) no significant difference in accent production was found between a group of speakers with Parkinson's disease and a control group when using the measurements of F0, intensity, intensity range, and duration.

The observed mechanisms to produce an accent in the group of speakers with dysarthria are related to the same strategies found in the healthy group. Six of the seven acoustic features are also valid for this group (Table 5.5). This finding agrees with the results of Lowit et al. (2014), who reported the use of the same pitch pattern by speakers with ataxic dysarthria and healthy speakers.

However, we identified a number of differences between both groups (Table 5.7) that need to be addressed. Despite $\Delta F0$ and $F0_{\text{Int}}$ being found in both groups, frequency changes within the target syllable have less prevalence in the dysarthric group. In this regard, the strongest acoustic feature to characterize accent in this group is based on the F0 differences between the target syllable and the previous one ($dF0_{\text{max}}$).

Other compensatory strategies used by this group to produce accent are related to intensity, and all of its derived features are included in the selection, playing an important role in this population. There is also evidence that contrasts in intensity and duration between the

target/accented syllable and the previous syllable are also characteristics of this group. This result supports the previous work of Patel (2003), who suggested that speakers with dysarthria probably compensate for their reduced ability to control F0 by exploiting their residual control of loudness and duration.

Two different durational features (dD_{range} and D_m) were included in the set as descriptors of accent production, considering the duration of the nucleus in the target syllable in contrast with the previous syllable, and the central tendency in duration within the rest of the sentence. Temporal cues seem to be more important in accent production by speakers with dysarthria than in healthy speakers. This finding agrees with former perceptual studies (Patel & Campellone, 2009; Patel, 2002a, 2002b) that reflected a use of duration to produce contrastive stress by severely dysarthric speakers. In addition, this result agrees with Lowit et al. (2014, 2018) who reported the effective use of duration and/or intensity contrast as compensatory mechanisms in patients unable to manipulate F0, resulting in a correct perceptual evaluation of their productions.

The results of this study show that patients with dysarthria still have residual control of F0. Moreover, they are able to use intensity and duration to compensate for a lack of F0 control. The fact that no statistical differences were found in $dF0_{min}$ between both groups (see Table 5.7) suggests that $dF0_{min}$ represents the residual F0 control, expressing the capacity to make a small increment or contrast in frequency between the accented syllable and the previous syllable.

The acoustic features introduced in this study can point out the strategies for a speaker to produce a sentence accent. Even when both groups of speakers make use of the same set of features, they do so in a different way.

Therefore, the hypothesis of this study is confirmed. The developed objective parameters allow for a quantitative description of accent production strategies. These measures can support auditory perceptual evaluations in clinical practice, and can be efficiently used as a tool for a personalized assessment and therapy orientation in cases of patients with dysarthria.

Conclusion

The results of this study allow for a better understanding of accent production in Dutch sentences. A limited set of acoustic features is provided to characterize the sentence accent. This research shows that acoustic features are reliable in the identification of sentence accents

in speakers of Dutch, whatever their quality of speech. The strongest predictive features are derived from frequency, intensity, and duration, not only within the syllable, but also in contrast to the previous syllable and the whole sentence. Although the majority of features are common for both groups of speakers, it seems that speakers with dysarthria use different compensatory mechanisms to produce sentence accent, frequently relying on intensity and/or duration-related features when the changes in fundamental frequency are difficult for them. This suggests that exercises for sentence accent can be personalized, and that therapists can use the recommended acoustic features for further evaluation. It also opens an opportunity for the development of an objective assessment of sentence accent. Furthermore, this research could be inspiring for speech-language pathologists looking for compensatory strategies in patients with speech disorders.

Future work

Further research is necessary to validate these acoustic features for larger groups of speakers, different languages, and different types of dysarthria and severity levels. Future work will address the use of state-of-the-art machine learning techniques, looking for a better classification rate with the features presented here. This machine learning application could be embedded in an assessment tool, and would be potentially useful for supporting perceptual evaluations of speech and language pathologists, for example, by aiding the specialist in the selection of specific therapy approaches for each type of patient.

CHAPTER 6

Acoustic identification of sentence accent in speakers with dysarthria: cross-population validation and severity related patterns

This chapter has been published in

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Abstract

Background

Dysprosody is a hallmark of dysarthria, which can affect the intelligibility and naturalness of speech. This includes sentence accent, which helps to draw listeners' attention to important information in the message. Although some studies have investigated this feature, we currently lack properly validated automated procedures that can distinguish between subtle performance differences observed across speakers with dysarthria.

Aims

This study aims for cross-population validation of a set of acoustic features that have previously been shown to correlate with sentence accent. In addition, the impact of dysarthria severity levels on sentence accent production is investigated.

Methods & Procedures

Two groups of adults were analysed (Dutch and English speakers). Fifty-eight participants with dysarthria and 30 healthy control participants (HCP) produced sentences with varying accent positions. All speech samples were evaluated perceptually and analysed acoustically with an algorithm that extracts ten meaningful prosodic features and allows a classification between accented and unaccented syllables based on a linear combination of these parameters. The data were statistically analysed using discriminant analysis.

Outcomes & Results

Within the Dutch and English dysarthric population, the algorithm correctly identified 82.8 and 91.9% of the accented target syllables, respectively, indicating that the capacity to discriminate between accented and unaccented syllables in a sentence is consistent with perceptual impressions. Moreover, different strategies for accent production across dysarthria severity levels could be demonstrated, which is an important step toward a better understanding of the nature of the deficit and the automatic classification of dysarthria severity using prosodic features.

Conclusions & Implications

The automatic algorithm demonstrated to be suitable for sentence accent detection across different speaker populations and languages. In addition, the embedded acoustic features are useful in the description of accent production by speakers with dysarthria.

Introduction

Prosody forms part of the suprasegmental characteristics of speech and reflects meaningful variations in pitch, loudness, length, and pause across words, phrases, and sentences. Prosodic disturbances are considered a perceptual hallmark of dysarthria, a neurological motor speech disorder (Darley, Aronson & Brown, 1969a, 1975; Duffy, 2020). Common manifestations include a slowed or accelerated speech rate, monopitch and monoloudness, rhythmic disturbances and reduced ability to vary stress and accent (Darley, Aronson & Brown, 1969b, 1975; Duffy, 2020; Peppé, 2009; Kent & Rosenbek, 1982; Rosenbek & LaPointe, 1985; Yorkston et al., 1984; Lowit et al., 2010, 2014). Stress is a structural, linguistic property of a word that specifies which syllable in the word is more prominent than the others, and it is determined by the language system (Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996a, 1996b; Cutler, 1984). Accentuation is associated with the communicative intention of highlighting important information within utterances (dependent on language behaviour), also known as focus (Peppé, 2009; Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996a, 1996b; Cutler, 1984; Rietveld & Van Heuven, 2009; Thies et al., 2020).

Changes in pitch, loudness and/or duration—represented acoustically by changes in fundamental frequency (F0), intensity (I) and duration (Peppé, 2009; Patel, 2011)—enable the speaker to make a clear distinction between the more and less important parts of his utterance. Consequently, effective accent or focus placement on an utterance is essential for the efficient conveyance of meaning (Cutler et al., 1997), and disturbances can lead to reductions in intelligibility and naturalness of speech (Darley et al., 1969a; Kent & Rosenbek, 1982; Yorkston et al., 1984; Patel, 2011; De Bodt et al., 2002).

Previous case studies suggest that healthy speakers and speakers with dysarthria rely on different combinations of changes in F0, intensity, and duration to achieve sentence accent (Lowit et al., 2010, 2014; Fry, 1955, 1958; Lieberman, 1960; Lehiste, 1970, 1976; Patel & Campellone, 2009), but more profound insight into these strategies is lacking. Objective analysis and detection of valid acoustic descriptors of sentence accent may increase our understanding and support the clinical assessment of speech in patients with dysarthria (Duffy, 2020).

Studies of acoustic correlates of sentence accent have provided valuable insight into this domain (Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996b; Pierrehumbert, 1980; Wang & Narayanan 2007a; Tamburini & Wagner, 2007; Al Moubayed & Beskow, 2010; Streefkerk, 1997). Acoustic

accent production descriptors have been studied in healthy speech (Streefkerk et al., 1999; Ananthakrishnan & Narayanan, 2007; Johnson & Kang, 2015; Nielsen et al., 2020; Scharenborg et al., 2020; Li et al., 2011, 2018; Li & Liu, 2010) and in dysarthria (Lowit et al., 2010, 2014, 2018; Patel, 2011; Patel & Campellone, 2009; Kuschmann & Lowit, 2019). Currently, there is general agreement in the literature that syllable duration, pitch pattern, and intensity (or sub-band energy) correlate with accentuation (Wang & Narayanan, 2007a; Tamburini, 2003). These acoustic parameters have been used in systems for automatic accent detection; however, there is a lack of validated automatic analysis techniques to investigate accent production in disordered populations.

A recent study by Mendoza et al. (2020) analysed the speech samples of 30 healthy control participants (HCP) and 50 participants with dysarthria, including different aetiologies and severity levels (ranging from mild to severe), who are all native Dutch speakers. The study demonstrated that sentence accent production could be characterised using a set of ten acoustic features. The selected features included not only the traditional values of F0, intensity, and duration measured within the target syllables, but also the differences of these three parameters with the values of their preceding syllable and with the median values of the entire utterance. These acoustic features demonstrated how a speaker manipulated F0, intensity, and duration to accentuate the target syllable within their prosodic capabilities. Furthermore, the combination of these features also allowed a reliable classification between accented and unaccented syllables in healthy and pathological speech. The study demonstrates the value of considering a more comprehensive range of variables and how they interact with each other in investigations of sentence accent production. However, further validation of the set of variables and the developed automatic analysis is necessary across different speaker populations varying in the type and severity of their speech disorders and spoken language.

Consequently, the purpose of this study is twofold. First, it aims to validate the methodology used by Mendoza et al. (2020) with a new sample of British English speakers. Although most Germanic languages tend to produce sentence accent similarly (Sluijter & Van Heuven, 1996a, 1996b; Fry, 1955; 1958; Kochanski et al., 2005), there might be subtle differences. Therefore, it is important to investigate whether Mendoza et al. (2020) feature pool can equally distinguish accented from unaccented syllables in impaired speech in other languages. Second, the study aims to investigate the extent to which a more detailed analysis of accent production has the potential to reflect the severity of dysarthria.

Methods

Speech samples

Samples of adult native speakers of Dutch and English were analysed. For the Dutch samples, 30 HCP and 50 participants with different types of dysarthria (spastic, flaccid, ataxic, hypokinetic, unilateral upper motor neuron (UUMN), mixed) and all severity levels were selected from the ‘Computerized Assessment and Treatment of Rate, Intonation, and Stress’ (CATRIS) corpus (Martens et al., 2013), which was composed for prosody research. It contains samples from 36 control and 55 speakers with dysarthria and different types of speech tasks. They all reported sufficient visual and auditory abilities to participate in the study. Cognitive skills were not explicitly screened, but all participants demonstrated sufficient abilities to understand and perform the assessment instructions appropriately. For the present study, only speech samples from the focus communicative function were selected, 1 of the 55 participants did not perform the focus task, and other samples from 10 speakers (6 HCP and 4 with dysarthria) were not included due to poor acoustic quality. The group with dysarthria included 31 male and 19 female participants with an age range between 30 and 87 years (mean = 61 years, std = 13 years). The control group included 10 male and 20 female participants with an age range between 18 and 75 years (mean = 40 years, std = 15 years).

For the English samples, eight out of ten speakers with hereditary ataxia and dysarthria first described in Lowit et al. (2010) were selected. Two speakers were excluded due to background noise in the audio recordings, making them unsuitable for the automatic analysis. The hearing and vision of all participants were normal or corrected-to-normal, and they had no significant cognitive deficits. The group included 3 male and 5 female participants with an age range between 28 and 72 years (mean = 52 years, std = 16 years).

The dysarthria severity level of all individuals ranged from mild over moderate to severe and was rated with a four-point grading scale (0 = normal; 1 = mild; 2 = moderate; 3 = severe) by three experienced speech and language pathologists (SLPs). Tables 6.1 and 6.2 summarise the selected speakers’ characteristics, based on the severity of dysarthric features and perceptually rated intelligibility.

Table 6.1. Characteristics of the selected Dutch speakers.

Dysarthria Type	Number of Subjects	Aetiology	Gender		Dysarthria Severity		
			F	M	1	2	3
UUMN	2	Stroke-1, TBI-1		2	1	1	
Spastic	2	Stroke-2		2	1		1
Flaccid	7	Encephalopathy-1, Stroke-5, TBI-1		7	5	1	1
Ataxic	2	Neuropathy-1, Stroke-1	1	1	1	1	
Hypokinetic	31	PD-28, Stroke-3	17	14	21	8	2
Mixed	3	ALS-1, Encephalopathy-1, Stroke-1		3	2	1	
Undetermined	3	BT-1, Stroke-2	1	2	3		
Total	50		19	31	34	12	4

Note: M = male; F = female; PD = idiopathic Parkinson's disease; TBI = Traumatic brain injury; BT = brain tumour; ALS = amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; UUMN = Unilateral upper motor neuron; Dysarthria severity scale: 1 = mild, 2 = moderate, 3 = severe.

Table 6.2. Characteristics of the selected English speakers.

Dysarthria Type	Number of Subjects	Aetiology	Gender		Dysarthria Severity		
			F	M	1	2	3
Ataxic	8	CA-3, FA-3, SCA6-1, SCA8-1	5	3	2	4	2

Note: M = male; F = female; CA = cerebellar ataxia of undefined type; SCA = spinocerebellar ataxia; FA = Friedreich's ataxia; Dysarthria severity scale: 1 = mild, 2 = moderate, 3 = severe.

Speech production tasks

The speech material consisted of a comparable set of sentences in both languages based on the standard paradigm to elicit sentence accent, i.e., repetitions of the same sentence with varying accent positions depending on the asked question (Lowit et al., 2010; Kuschmann & Lowit, 2019, 2021; Martens et al., 2011, 2016). The questions were structured to elicit new information rather than contrastive focus. For the Dutch speakers, the sample included 3 different sentences. Each sentence was elicited twice, with the focus occurring either in the initial (one case), medial (two cases), or final sentence position (three cases), resulting in six productions per participant, Table 6.3. A total of 180 and 300 sentences were available for the

control and dysarthric group, respectively. For the English sample, speakers produced a set of 10 sentences, in which the focus was either in the initial, medial, or final position (10 cases for each position), resulting in 30 productions per speaker. A total of 240 sentences were included for this group. Table 6.3 summarises the focus sentences used in each language. In all cases, the participants were instructed to accent the typographically highlighted word.

Table 6.3. Focus sentences used in each experiment.

Dutch Task	English Task
Ze wil geen telefoon meer krijgen. <i>She does not want to get any more calls.</i>	The gardener grew roses in London .
Luc werkt in het ziekenhuis . <i>Luke works at the hospital.</i>	The minister has a nanny from Norway .
Misschien heeft Piet vakantie . <i>Maybe Pete is on holiday.</i>	The model wrote her memoirs in Lima .
	The diva made a movie in Venice .
	The lawyer met the model in London .
	The widow bought a villa in Ealing .
	The neighbour plays melodies on her mandolin .
	The milliner got a memo from Melanie .
	The murderer met his lover in Limerick .

Note. English translations in italics for the sentences in Dutch.

In the Dutch samples, the perceived accent of each sentence was assessed by three experienced clinicians, who independently marked the accented syllables without knowledge of the target word. If at least two judges had assigned the label ‘accented’ to a particular syllable, that label was retained. For the perceptual analysis of the English speakers, five SLPs judged the samples, deciding whether single or multiple elements were accented and indicating their respective locations (Lowit et al., 2010). They had the option of selecting a single or multiple accented word. Decisions on which syllable(s) was accented were again made by majority rule. Native

speakers with intact hearing completed all the evaluations. Table 6.4 summarises the number of perceived accented syllables included in each group’s analysis.

Table 6.4. Perceptually detected accented and unaccented syllables for each group of speakers.

Syllables	Speaker Population		
	Control	Dysarthric Dutch	Dysarthric English
Accented	197	338	259
Unaccented	1160	1891	1988
Total	1357	2229	2247

Acoustic analysis

Set of parameters used to detect and describe sentence accent

The acoustic analysis was performed with MatLab software (version 2019b). An automatic algorithm described by Mendoza et al. (2020) was used to detect the syllable nuclei and extract fundamental frequency (F0), energy, and duration. F0 values and intensity values were then normalised to make them speaker-independent, i.e., F0 was transposed into semitones (ST) (‘t Hart et al., 1990), and intensity was normalised with respect to the maximum amplitude value of each sentence. Duration values (D) are reported as absolute values in milliseconds (ms). The algorithm automatically detected syllable nucleus boundaries, energy envelopes, and F0 and plotted them over the spectrogram of each utterance, where they could be visually and auditorily inspected as well as manually corrected, if necessary (see Mendoza et al., 2020), for a detailed description of the automatic algorithm). Syllable nucleus boundaries had been manually modified when the algorithm had erroneously marked the boundaries, and corrections of F0 were required in 25 sentences of the total population (3.47%). Subsequently, a total of ten acoustic features were calculated for each syllable nucleus within an utterance (Table 6.5). Three parameters were inherent to each syllable, four were calculated in comparison with the previously uttered syllable and three others in comparison with the median of the entire sentence (the median was selected because it is a good estimator of central tendency in small samples). These parameters were then used to determine the acoustic differences between perceptually identified accented and unaccented syllables.

Table 6.5. Set of parameters derived from F0, Duration, and Intensity used in this study (Mendoza et al., 2020).

Parameters inherent to the syllable
$\Delta F0$ —the difference between the initial and the final value of F0 within the syllable nucleus in semitones
Int —maximum intensity of the syllable nucleus, relative to the overall utterance amplitude envelope
F0&Int —the interaction of F0max (the maximum F0 value within the syllable nucleus) minus F0min (the minimum F0 value within the syllable nucleus) multiplied by Int
Parameters in comparison with the preceding syllable
dF0max —the difference between the F0max of each syllable with that of the preceding one
dF0min —the difference between the F0min of each syllable with that of the preceding one
dInt —the difference between Int of each syllable and that of the preceding one
dDrange —the difference between the duration of each syllable and that of the preceding one (dD) normalised to the range of all dD values in the sentence
Note. For initial syllables, the second syllable was used to calculate the difference
Parameters in comparison with the utterance
F0maxM —the difference between F0max and the median F0 of the utterance
IntM —the difference between Int and the median Int of the utterance
DM —the normalised duration (D, associated with the time length of the syllable nucleus) with respect to the median of all the D values in the sentence

Accent detection in dysarthric speech and description by severity levels

The set of independent acoustic features outlined in Table 6.5 was used as a predictor of accent placement. Discriminant analysis was performed to determine a linear combination of the ten parameters that enables the identification of the following two categories: accented and unaccented syllables (Klecka, 1980; Tharwat et al., 2017). The coefficients for the linear equation were calculated based on the group of Dutch speakers with dysarthria (Table 6.4). The discriminant analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

(SPSS) software (version 21). The discriminative capacity of the equation was then validated with the English corpus of speakers with ataxic dysarthria, which included a total of 2247 syllables classified as accented or unaccented.

To investigate the strategies used for accent production across the different dysarthria severity levels (DSL), we performed a discriminant analysis using the SPSS software (version 21). For this analysis, the Dutch and English data were merged. The front-end processing used the set of ten acoustic features previously defined in Table 6.5, the independent variables were used together, and the Wilks's Lambda criteria was selected (Klecka, 1980). The different severities of dysarthria (mild, moderate, and severe) were analysed separately; the aim was to identify the contribution of each acoustic feature to accent production for each severity level in order to look for possible differences in the accentuation patterns.

Results

Validation of the acoustic features for accent detection

The discriminant analysis was initially performed with the samples of the Dutch-speaking population with dysarthria. As a result, the unstandardised discriminant function coefficients were obtained (Table 6.6). They were used to construct the following actual prediction Equation (1), which was used to classify the new English language cases in this study:

$$Y = \beta_1 * \Delta F0 + \beta_2 * Int + \beta_3 * F0 \& Int + \beta_4 * dF0min + \beta_5 * dF0max + \dots + C \quad (1)$$

where Y is the discriminant score, β 's are the unstandardised discriminant function coefficients, and C is a constant. Y is the score obtained from the linear combination of the β coefficients (listed in Table 6.6) multiplied by each discriminant feature. For $Y \geq 0.86$, the syllable is classified as accented; for $Y < 0.86$, the syllable is unaccented. The cut-off value (0.86) is the mean of the two centroids (Table 6.7), which are the mean value of the discriminant score for a given category (un/accented) of the dependent variable.

Table 6.6. Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients.

Parameters	Function
$\Delta F0$	$\beta_1 = 0.043$
Int	$\beta_2 = 0.605$
F0&Int	$\beta_3 = 0.119$
dF0min	$\beta_4 = -0.042$

dF0max	$\beta_5 = -0.119$
dInt	$\beta_6 = 0.192$
dDrange	$\beta_7 = 0.336$
F0maxM	$\beta_8 = 0.041$
DM	$\beta_9 = -0.378$
IntM	$\beta_{10} = 1.095$
Constant	$C = -0.595$

Note: Unstandardized coefficients.

Table 6.7. Functions at Group Centroids.

Category	Function
Accented	2.094
Unaccented	-0.374

Note: Unstandardised canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means.

The linear combination of the ten acoustic parameters was then applied to classify accented and unaccented syllables in the English sample. As previously reported by Mendoza et al. (2020), the results for the Dutch speakers showed a percentage of correct classification of 82.8% for accented syllables and 90.5% for unaccented syllables for the speakers with dysarthria and 87.3 and 96.6% for the control group, respectively. Table 6.8 shows the confusion matrix with the results (in %) of correct classification for the two categories of the dependent variable (accented versus unaccented syllables) for the newly analysed English corpus, indicating that the approach worked equally well across the two speaker populations. The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve was represented in Figure 6.1; this is a graphical representation of the equation's performance, representing the true-positive rate against the false-positive rate. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) is a measure of how well the equation can discriminate between the two outputs (un/accented) syllables; for our study, AUC = 0.964, 95% confidence interval: 0.952–0.975, $p < 0.001$.

Table 6.8. Confusion matrix for the classification results of the English speakers with dysarthria.

Target Syllables	Predicted Group Membership	
	Accented	Unaccented
Accented	91.9%	8.1%
Unaccented	7.8%	92.2%

Figure 6.1. ROC curve representing the discriminatory ability of Equation (1) on the task of detecting un/accented syllables.

Impact of different dysarthria severity levels on production patterns for sentence accent

The discriminant analysis was applied individually to the different severity levels, showing the standardised canonical discriminant function coefficients per group. The magnitude of these coefficients indicates the relative importance of each independent acoustic feature in predicting the accent. They also allow for a comparison of the parameters measured on different scales (F0, Intensity, Duration). Coefficients with large absolute values correspond to acoustic features with greater discriminating ability. The discriminative coefficients are listed in Table 6.9.

Table 6.9. Standardised canonical discriminant function coefficients per group of dysarthria severity levels (mixed groups of English and Dutch speakers).

Parameters	Severity Levels			
	Control (30)	Mild (36)	Moderate (16)	Severe (6)
Inherent to the syllable				
$\Delta F0$	0.261	0.200	0.184	0.060
Int	0.015	0.104	0.226	0.240
F0&Int	0.420	0.436	0.241	0.175
In comparison with the preceding syllable				
dF0min	-0.175	-0.193	-0.200	-0.158
dF0max	-0.367	-0.337	-0.271	-0.230
dInt	0.029	-0.046	-0.007	-0.133
dDrange	-0.080	0.157	0.057	0.054
In comparison with the sentence				
F0maxM	0.239	0.146	0.113	-0.015
DM	-0.059	-0.263	-0.186	-0.076
IntM	0.212	0.168	0.435	0.568

The values of these coefficients indicated the features predominantly used to produce accent in healthy and dysarthric speech. Variations were observed between the severity levels. For example, the HCP tended to use changes in F0 and intensity (F0 & Int) within the target syllable supported by an increase in F0 in relation to the preceding syllable (dF0max) to produce a detectable accent. The group of speakers with mild dysarthria showed a similar tendency, meaning that they retained control over F0 to highlight important information in the sentence. Then, as the severity progressed, the pattern increasingly deviated from the HCP pattern. The group with moderate dysarthria used the same two main features, although they were not as prominent as in the HCP. In addition, the target syllables were highlighted by means of intensity contrast to the rest of the sentence (IntM). On the other hand, the participants with severe dysarthria only used one of the main features applied by HCP, (dF0max) and supplemented this strategy by manipulating intensity more prominently (Int and IntM). This group of speakers appeared to have less control over F0 but managed to compensate with intensity changes.

Discussion

Cross-population validation of acoustic features

This study validated an automatic system that extracts ten specific acoustic features derived from F0, intensity, and duration, used for sentence accent identification across different languages and speaker populations with atypical prosody. The acoustic features were divided into three categories (Table 6.5), the syllable's inherent parameters, the parameters of the syllable in contrast with the preceding syllable and the parameters of the syllable in contrast with the entire sentence. This set of features was used in a discriminant function to classify between accented and unaccented syllables, achieving 91.9% of correct classification of accented syllables and 92.2% of correct classification of unaccented syllables for the new population of English speakers affected with ataxic dysarthria. The classification accuracy results are comparable with the results of our previous study for native Dutch speakers (healthy and dysarthric speech) and with other studies of accent detection in healthy speech (Streefkerk et al., 1999; Ananthakrishnan & Narayanan, 2007; Johnson & Kang, 2015; Nielsen et al., 2020; Scharenborg et al., 2020; Li et al., 2018). The results suggest that combining the ten acoustic parameters developed by Mendoza et al. (2020) has a good capacity to discriminate between accented and unaccented syllables in healthy and speech-impaired speakers of Germanic languages with comparable accentuation patterns, such as English and Dutch.

In clinical practice, this automatic accent detection system could significantly reduce the time required to analyse speech data and provide quantitative information of prosodic parameters that could be useful as diagnostic and outcome measures. This could help clinicians define and implement more precise therapeutic approaches based on the identification of specific compensatory strategies of accent production. In addition, the current system's focus on within utterance variables may, in the future, allow a move away from structured sentence accent tasks toward more naturalistic speech samples as the basis for analysis, thus providing greater face validity to the information gained from the investigation of both healthy and disordered speech.

This study did not investigate the erroneous classifications in further detail. However, a preliminary inspection of the misclassified syllables showed some utterances where the system detected two accents and the listeners only one. Such cases could indicate specific dysarthric speech deficits such as excess stress where several syllables in an utterance received similar levels of accent as often reported for ataxic dysarthria or the reduced stress characteristic of hypokinetic dysarthria where no syllable, in particular, is highlighted from the rest. In such

cases, listeners might have felt compelled to identify a single accent target, leading to the mismatch between perceptual and acoustic analysis results. Further investigation of such utterances and perceptual studies of what prompts a listener to identify a particular word in an utterance as accented may shed more light on these cases in the future. In the meantime, it is important to keep in mind that the so-called errors made by the automatic analysis might not reflect analysis mistakes but additional features of dysarthric speech performance.

Impact of severity on accent production

As the current data show, the ability to accentuate or highlight information within an utterance is not related to the overall severity of the dysarthria, as even the severely affected participants (SAP) managed to place the accent in their sentences successfully. However, limited information is available to date on whether severity influences the acoustic patterns used to signal sentence accent. This could guide more effective intervention approaches for the speakers. Previous research, such as a study by Lowit et al. (2010), did not find a strong correlation between dysarthria severity and accent production patterns; however, this study was based on a much-reduced set of features than that applied by Mendoza et al. (2020).

The present study shows clear differences in how acoustic prosodic features were manipulated by the different speaker groups. The speakers with mild dysarthria tended to use similar strategies to the control group, i.e., they conveyed accent by making changes to F0 within the target syllable, with a simultaneous increase in the intensity (F0 & Int) and contrast in the frequency between the target syllable and the preceding syllable ($dF0_{max}$). This result is in line with previous studies that reported F0 as the primary marker for accent perception (Bolinger, 1958; Van Katwijk, 1974; Hasegawa & Hata, 1992) and found that speakers with acquired motor speech disorders could use the same pitch patterns as HCP (Lowit et al., 2014; Mennen et al., 2008; Verhoeven & Mariën, 2010).

The group of moderately affected participants (MAP) appeared to still have control over F0 in the target syllable and in contrast with the preceding syllable, although these features were not used as prominently as in the HCP. As a result, the MAP used additional compensatory strategies to produce accent, i.e., they also applied changes to intensity relative to the rest of the sentence (IntM).

The SAP demonstrated a reduced ability to control F0. However, they compensated for this by using mainly intensity (both within syllables (Int) and compared with the median intensity of the entire sentence (IntM)). This is an interesting observation given that Lowit et al. (2018)

demonstrated in a perceptual experiment that intensity could be a powerful signal for listeners and used in compensation for pitch. Thus, the speakers with ataxia seem to naturally employ the most effective compensatory feature to counteract their deficit in F0 manipulation.

This objective analysis of accent patterns within different levels of severity contributes to a better understanding of the nature of dysarthric speech and its deviant characteristics. It could also help clinicians determine the remaining acoustical cues for accent production in order to select optimal treatment strategies.

Limitations and further directions

Although the results of this study are promising for the automatic detection of sentence accent in dysarthria within different aetiologies and all severity levels, several topics require further research. The potential of this analysis can go beyond the traditional focus tasks and analyse more natural language production, which is highly important in clinical practice; therefore, this will be considered in future studies. The different patterns of accent production between groups of dysarthria severity levels observed in this study also deserve further investigation. More detailed investigations are required to further validate the generality of these results and to expand their scope. It would be useful to carry out a replication study on a larger population, which would allow for a more robust (statistical) analysis of the results.

As discussed above, there was a mismatch between the un/accented syllables classified by the automatic system and the listeners. Further analysis into listener strategies to identify accented words would be helpful to clarify the extent to which this phenomenon was due to speaker characteristics or measurement errors, which would require further refinement of the acoustic features in order to improve system performance. In addition, the quality of the recordings was not optimal in some samples, further analysis of the degree to which this might have impacted the accuracy of the results would be significant. Future studies could evaluate the algorithm performance in non-Germanic languages. Additionally, an investigation of accentuation patterns within different types of dysarthria might be useful to better understand underlying problems and compensatory strategies. Despite these limitations, the presented method is suitable for future research investigating larger samples of dysarthric speech. It can provide insight into the patients' motor control processes and support patient-tailored therapeutic interventions—what the problem is and how to compensate for it.

Conclusions

This cross-population study validated a detailed set of acoustic descriptors related to F0, intensity, and duration (calculated within utterances) used for the automatic detection of sentence accent in dysarthric speech. The discrimination between accented and unaccented syllables using the automatic algorithm was accurate for both populations (Dutch and English speakers with dysarthria).

In addition, the validated acoustic features could adequately describe the strategies used for accent production across different severities. They provided a detailed objective description and a deeper understanding of the strategies or compensatory mechanisms used by speakers with dysarthria to highlight important information in a spoken message.

The clinical significance of this study is threefold: faster automatic detection of accent production, an objective analysis useful as an outcome measure, and support in determining therapeutic strategies.

PART 4

EPILOGUE

CHAPTER 7

Summary and conclusions

Dysarthria is a neurological motor speech disorder that affects speech production due to weak, slow, inaccurate and uncoordinated movements of the speech musculature (Enderby, 2013; Duffy, 2019). Dysfunction of one or more of the subsystems involved in speech production (respiration, phonation, resonance, articulation and prosody) can compromise speech's overall intelligibility. Imprecise speech sound articulation and prosodic disturbances are reported in each type of dysarthria; therefore, they are considered perceptual hallmarks (Tjaden, 2007; Weismer, 2007; Darley et al., 1969, 1975; Duffy, 2019). Previous research showed that these two dimensions of speech (articulation and prosody) contribute considerably to overall intelligibility in dysarthric speech (De Bodt et al., 2002). Adults with dysarthria frequently face social, psychological, and daily communication problems, negatively impacting their well-being. Therefore, they should have access to an early diagnosis and therapy. Through decades, acoustic data has potentially been used for objective evaluations of speech disorders, providing scientific and engineering insight. Considering the adverse effects of disordered articulation and prosody on communication and quality of life, the overall aim of this thesis is to contribute to the clinical care and well-being of patients with dysarthria through the development of signal processing techniques and speech technology in general. This research increases the existing knowledge about behavioural treatments of articulation in this population and extends the understanding of prosodic mechanisms and strategies. In order to provide clinicians and patients with objective and automatic assessments and therapy tools, several research questions were answered; the main outcomes will be further summarized.

Articulation

Articulatory imprecision is considered a key feature of dysarthria (Tjaden, 2007), reflected by perceptual characteristics such as irregular articulatory distortions, distortion of vowels and extended phonemes (Duffy, 2019). Deficient articulatory movements are linked with reduced acoustic contrast for consonants and vowels, which leads to reduced intelligibility (Tjaden, 2007; Tykalova et al., 2017). The impact of dysarthria on articulatory movements and acoustic outcomes is, in general, comparable even when neurologic bases differ among different types (Tjaden, 2007). In most cases, speech therapy facilitates the recovery of articulatory skills. It is widely acknowledged that improving speech requires speaking, which means that for most patients, speech rather than non-speech tasks should be the focus of treatment activities. If the patient still has the neural and muscular potential to improve speech function, appropriate therapy can facilitate that process. A key feature of boost therapies is intensity, one of the main principles of motor learning and neuroplasticity, which are generally recognized as key for

speech therapy (Rosenbek & Jones, 2009; Kaipa, 2016; Duffy, 2019). Intensity can be achieved via the frequency of treatment, repetitions within sessions, or requiring greater force, effort, or accuracy during motor tasks.

Behavioural treatment of articulation in patients with dysarthria mainly involves indirect strategies, which have shown positive effects on speech intelligibility. Nevertheless, some studies indicate the possibility that focusing on compensating may counter the process of neural reorganization to reduce specific impairment (Dobkin & Thompson, 2000). Moreover, there is some evidence that direct treatment of articulation is worth the effort. Currently, only a few studies have combined motor learning principles with a segmental approach to traditional articulation therapy. Therefore, the evidence on the short-term effects of direct and intensive articulation therapy at the segmental level of speech is rather limited.

The first goal of this research was to investigate the effectiveness of boost articulation therapy (BArT) on speech intelligibility in patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria and the effect of dysarthria severity on the outcome. For **research question 1** (chapter 2), the feasibility and effectiveness of an intensive articulation therapy in patients with dysarthria were analyzed for all severity levels. The intensive and direct articulatory therapy programmes developed and applied in this first study intend to reduce the impairment instead of compensating it. The set of exercises (articulatory drills and minimal pairs) and training methods designed and used in this study were structured based on the general principles of motor learning for neurorehabilitation.

After five therapy sessions, significant intelligibility increases were observed for three different speech tasks, at a phoneme level (NSVO), in automatic sequences and even at the sentence level (NSVO-Z). Additionally, a positive effect of BArT was shown in each severity group (mild, moderate, and severe) in the tasks mentioned above. The acoustic analysis also reinforced perceptual findings. FCR analyses the formant frequencies of vowel articulation. Results pre- and post-treatment showed that FCR values had a positive tendency and correlated well with speech intelligibility in this study. This acoustic analysis documented the positive therapeutic effect of the BArT in the expansion of the vowel space. The outcomes of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of the BArT approach focused on the segmental level of speech. Results confirmed that this direct and intensive treatment successfully improves speech intelligibility at different dysarthria severity levels in a short period of time, while exploiting and developing all available residual motor skills in persons with chronic or progressive

dysarthria. Consequently, this makes it to be considered a suitable approach in the treatment of patients with chronic or progressive dysarthria.

In addition to the aforementioned results, pathological speech data was collected during the articulation therapy sessions. This provides a new corpus of pathological speech, valid for further development and evaluation of automatic therapy and assessment tools.

The first study results lead to the **second goal** of this thesis, to evaluate the feasibility (design and development) of a Virtual Articulation Therapist (VAT) that supports intensive articulation training of patients with dysarthria and to validate the system by end-users. This was addressed in (chapter 3 & chapter 4) and divided into three different research questions. **Research question 2**, modifications in existing algorithms necessary for precise and reliable phonological error detection in patients with dysarthria, **research question 3**, the feasibility of a VAT system and the acceptability, usability and interaction of end-users with it and **research question 4**, the development of an automatic score of the degree of phoneme distortion in adults with dysarthria.

Scientific and clinical evidence shows that improving articulatory skills demands intensive and frequent therapy (Duffy, 2019; Rosenbek & Jones, 2009). In addition, there is growing evidence that the content of speech therapy must meet the principles of motor learning (Duffy, 2019). Key elements of motor learning in clinical neurorehabilitation are intensive treatment, repetitive practice and sensory feedback (Kleim et al., 2003; Garvey et al., 2007; Kleim & Jones, 2008; Maas et al., 2008). It is generally accepted that greater therapy frequency may lead to better ultimate performance (Dobkin et al., 2000). In addition, extensive research in the speech therapy domain suggests that providing large amounts of practice over a shorter period can lead to better results/outcomes for adults with communication disorders (Bhogal et al., 2003; Fox et al., 2006). However, the current treatments of articulation are mainly limited in time to the interactive sessions in the presence of speech-language pathology (SLP).

Virtual therapy technologies are not entirely new. However, automatic systems addressing the needs of individuals with dysarthria are scarce. The idea of introducing a virtual therapist in speech therapy has existed already for some time, but it has not been brought to daily patient care. To our knowledge, there is no publicly available virtual articulation tool providing BArT with adequate feedback, especially not for Dutch-speaking subjects with articulatory deficits. The second study of this thesis (chapter 3) evaluates the feasibility of a VAT program and investigates its acceptability, usability and user interaction. The computer-based speech

therapy approach developed and applied in this study intends to support intensive articulation training for patients with dysarthria. This virtual therapy program only targets those persons with dysarthria who have sufficient cognitive, linguistic, motoric and sensory (auditory and visual) skills to benefit from speech therapy (Weismer, 2007). The VAT offers the possibility of an individualized and customized therapy programme, with an extensive database of exercises, visual and auditory models of the target utterances, providing adequate feedback based on automatic acoustic analysis of the speech signal, and built into a patient-friendly user interface.

The implemented algorithm to provide patient feedback uses state-of-the-art gated recurrent neural networks and it is based on existing models (Vásquez-Correa et al., 2019). The models were selected because of their previous accurate performance in the evaluation of dysarthria severity in patients with motor speech disorders (Orozco-Aroyave et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2020). The original models were designed for the Spanish language; also, vowel characteristics were more represented. Therefore, refinement and extension of the models were done. They were retrained using Dutch language-specific phonological features (place and manner of articulation and voiced characteristics) on healthy speech and extended for the reliable characterization of consonants. The newly trained algorithm extracts the phonological posterior probabilities from the acoustic signal, and it is used to identify more specific phonological errors present during the articulation training of subjects with dysarthria.

High accuracy of the acoustic models' performance was achieved, contributing to adequate automatic feedback of utterance production. The detailed information provided by the acoustic models is generally difficult to impossible to detect and quantify by the human ear. Consequently, the automatic feedback allows patients to work more precisely in the improvement of the articulatory movements.

The VAT addresses the need for an accessible therapy program. After two sessions of interacting with the system, patients with mild to moderate dysarthria evaluated general aspects of the virtual therapist, such as usability, operationality, layout, exercises, and feedback, among others. In general, all participants were optimistic about this new therapy approach. The visual feedback was found to be attractive, clear and easy to interpret; nevertheless, they showed interest in adding complementary auditory feedback. The exercises were found to be adequate, goal-oriented, well structured and sufficient in number, facilitating language recovery.

The computer-based intervention designed and developed in this study has been well accepted by the end-users, that highly appreciated the possibility of an independent speech training tool. Therefore, it can be concluded that the automatic BArT can overcome the limitation in time of

face-to-face traditional speech therapy. Furthermore, it offers patients the opportunity to have access to articulation therapy more intensively and frequently in their home environment.

In the existing context of the unprecedented sanitary crisis (COVID-19 pandemic) in which the need for innovative healthcare delivery has been highlighted, the VAT may contribute to the well-being of all those people affected with dysarthria, of which the majority are elderly and have high risks of contamination.

As a step forward for improving the VAT's automatic feedback, the last study on this research topic focused on developing and evaluating an objective score of articulatory distortion (chapter 4). It is widely acknowledged that within the different articulatory error types in dysarthria, speech sound distortion is the most predominant compared to substitutions, omissions, or additions (Johns & Darley, 1970; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1980; Tjaden, 2007; Kirshner, 2021). Deviations in the production of the sound-specific features related to the manner and places of articulation or voicing characteristics can contribute to the perceived distortion of the speech sounds in dysarthria. Therefore, developing a new model for objectively estimating the degree of phoneme distortion of dysarthric speech is considered highly clinically relevant. The newly implemented algorithm extracts phonological posterior probabilities from the speech signal using the models previously discussed in the second study of this thesis. Additionally, the computed phonological characteristics will be transformed into a set of 15 phonological log-likelihood ratio (PLLR) features which are considered to be a good representation of the speaker's performance. Based on the PLLR features, different prediction models were trained on pathological speech. The evaluation of the models' performance shows that a phoneme-independent ensemble classifier -subspace KNN- allows for a reliable and objective scoring of the degree of distortion at the phoneme level in dysarthric speech (from slightly to severely distorted sounds). The new model can predict the degree of distortion with an overall accuracy of 73.5%. Further research is necessary to fine-tune the algorithm performance. However, the current model is considered sufficiently reliable for its implementation as part of the automatic feedback in the VAT.

Prosody

Prosody, also known as suprasegmental characteristics of speech, reflects meaningful variations in pitch, loudness, length, and pause across words, phrases, and sentences. Focus is one of the communicative functions of prosody achieved by accent placement in an utterance and is responsible for highlighting important information. The assessment of prosodic

communicative functions in dysarthric speech is somehow controversial and challenging due to the inconsistencies related to disordered prosody (Peppé, 2009). Acoustic analysis of the speech signal is a non-invasive and effective objective measurement tool for the assessment of prosody that can also be useful for the characterization of a specific type of disorder or for monitoring the progression and effects of a therapeutic intervention. The current state of the art regarding sentence accent production in dysarthric speech is based on perceptual analysis. However, an objective assessment of this prosodic function can provide a thorough comprehension of the prosodic strategies used by patients with dysarthria, and it can offer a more detailed description of perceptually-based characteristics from an acoustical perspective. Accordingly, it is necessary to develop appropriate objective measures that support auditory perceptual evaluations. This would also facilitate the design of more personalized therapy methods.

This thesis's **third and final goal** was to identify relevant acoustic features that enable classification and objective characterization of sentence accent production for healthy and dysarthric speakers of Dutch, and to validate the methodology across different speaker populations varying in the type and severity of their speech disorders and spoken language. This goal was split into two different research questions. First, **research question 5** targets the identification of the acoustic features and prosodic strategies used by healthy speakers and speakers with dysarthria to produce sentence accent; this aim was addressed in chapter 5. Previous studies in normal speech using acoustic features to characterize sentence accent production are of significant value. On the contrary, research on the acoustic features of prosody in pathological speech is rather scarce; a literature review on the characterization and assessment of atypical prosody shows a need for more research in this domain (Diehl & Paul, 2009; Hargrove, Anderson & Jones, 2009; Peppé, 2009). An adequate objective approach needs specifically-designed methods that consider, e.g., absence of voice, lack of articulatory landmarks, and low intensity, among other deviant characteristics commonly observed in this population.

As a result of our study, a new set of relevant acoustic features correlated with sentence accent were detected in Dutch native speakers. These features include values of fundamental frequency (F0), intensity, and duration within a syllable, as well as the differences between the feature values of the target syllable with the values of the preceding syllable and also the differences with the median values of the complete utterance. Linear discriminant analysis was applied to reduce the dimensionality of the feature space and select relevant acoustic

characteristics with an efficient power to predict syllable accentuation. The selected features are embedded in an automatic algorithm that performs the objective and acoustic analysis of the speech signal and offers a highly reliable classification between accented and unaccented syllables within an utterance. The quantitative measures derived from the acoustic analysis are also used to objectively characterize and differentiate the varying patterns of dysarthric speech from the healthy speech in the production of sentence accent. The observed mechanisms of accent production in the group of speakers with dysarthria are related to the same strategies found in the healthy group. Nevertheless, results reveal that although both groups use some common features, they differ significantly ($p < 0.01$) in the way they achieve a perceptually noticeable/ prominent accent. While healthy speakers rely more on frequency changes with simultaneous intensity increment within the target syllable (F0&Int), speakers with dysarthria showed stronger use of F0 differences between the target syllable and the previous syllable (dF0max). They also rely on intensity changes with the rest of the sentence as a compensatory strategy, and/or frequently use duration-related features when the F0 changes are difficult for them to perform. Consequently, we could demonstrate that patients with dysarthria still have some residual control over F0, but strategically compensate for their reduced ability to manage F0 by exploiting intensity and temporal cues.

Drawing some conclusions from this study, we can confirm that the developed set of acoustic measures can accurately predict accented syllables within healthy and impaired speech utterances. Moreover, sentence accent production can be adequately and objectively described by the introduced acoustic features. The latest enables a better description and comprehension of different accent strategies in healthy and dysarthric speakers. This knowledge allows therapists to develop or modify intervention methods for more personalized rehabilitation of sentence accent.

The selected acoustic parameters were validated by means of a cross-population study in a group of Dutch and English speakers with different severity levels of dysarthria; fifty-eight participants were analyzed in total (**research question 6**, chapter 6). The pitch, loudness, and duration changes—that enable speakers to emphasize essential parts of their utterance—were represented by ten acoustic descriptors related to F0, intensity, and duration. A linear combination of those more prominent parameters was obtained by means of discriminant analysis for the efficient and automatic prediction of sentence accent. This equation (or discriminant function) accurately predicts accented and unaccented syllables in healthy and speech-impaired speakers, in accordance with perceptual impressions. The automatic

algorithm shows accurate results in both dysarthric populations, achieving 82.8% and 91.9% of correctly identified accented target syllables for Dutch and English, respectively.

In addition, a more detailed analysis of the impact of dysarthria severity levels during accent production was performed, demonstrating differences in the strategies used across mild, moderate or severe levels of dysarthria; this is a significant step toward a better understanding of the nature of the deficit. The analyzed data show that the ability to accentuate essential information in a sentence is not connected to the overall severity of the dysarthria, as even severely affected speakers achieved the task effectively. However, the different speaker groups showed clear differences in how acoustic prosodic features are manipulated. The speakers with mild dysarthria show a tendency towards normality, using similar strategies to the control group, i.e., F0 changes within the target syllable, together with an increase in the intensity (F0&Int) and frequency contrast between the target syllable and the preceding syllable (dF0max). The speakers with moderate dysarthria use additional compensatory strategies to convey accent; they seem to apply intensity changes relative to the entire sentence (IntM). On the other hand, the severely affected participants showed a reduced capability to control F0, although they mainly used intensity (Int and IntM) to compensate and achieve an effective accent placement on an utterance. Therefore, we can conclude that the selected acoustic parameters have the potential to reflect the severity of dysarthria. The automatic assessment depicts some misclassification errors, which is typical in the analysis of pathological speech. Nevertheless, we argue that the so-called errors might not reflect analysis mistakes but additional features of dysarthric speech performance that need further research.

The objective analysis performed in this study sheds more light on the extent to which dysarthria severity might impact the individual prosodic features. This study contributes to the development of alternative assessment procedures with reliable, precise and fast quantitative results, reducing biases due to subjectivity. The automatic evaluation of accent placement during speech rehabilitation lays the foundations for a more natural way of assessment during continuous speech, thus offering greater face validity to the obtained information from disordered speech.

Conclusions

The findings presented in this dissertation contribute to the advances in speech technology for the clinical care of patients with dysarthria. The results of the studies increase our insight into the evaluation and treatments of articulation and add a new dimension to the assessment and understanding of prosodic mechanisms and strategies. Furthermore, significant steps have been made toward a more accessible and individually targeted speech therapy, adding the possibility of remote and autonomous patient rehabilitation.

Concerning articulation, a clinically valuable set of exercises has been developed for direct and intensive therapy according to the principles of motor learning for speech rehabilitation. The exercises comprise articulatory drills and minimal pairs, both essential to motor learning. Also, a comprehensive and hierarchically structured training method for articulation has been designed. The intensive articulation therapy based on this methodology has proven to be feasible and effective for improving speech intelligibility in subjects with chronic or progressive dysarthria. Both the methodology and exercise material have been later incorporated in the VAT, a complementary technology-based intervention that facilitates patients working alone or under the supervision of a caregiver, allowing intensive practice as an extension of face-to-face therapy. Although this new therapy tool still requires some further refinements, there are multiple novelties in the design and implementation of the VAT: 1) modelling of the target utterance through a carefully designed database with audio-visual material, including clear oral movements (frontal and lateral views) and emphasizing specific features of the target phoneme/utterance; 2) providing adequate and relevant feedback regarding the accuracy of the target phoneme and insight in the specific errors of articulatory movements during production, based on acoustic algorithms; 3) tailored and user-friendly interface, suitable for patients with brain damage; 4) providing a well-structured and hierarchical package of exercises based upon the principles of motor learning. The VAT offers clear applicability in the medical management of patients with dysarthria, is well accepted by end-users and has an added value for the current Flemish healthcare situation. Another novelty of this thesis is related to the articulation assessment for automatic feedback. This involved developing and evaluating a phoneme-independent prediction model, which allows for a reliable estimation of the degree of distortion at the phoneme level in dysarthric speech.

Concerning prosody, a new acoustically-based multidimensional approach has been developed for the objective assessment and more comprehensive characterization of sentence accent in

atypical prosody of speakers with dysarthria. The clinically usable set of newly detected acoustic features correlating with accent, combines different measures of F0, intensity and duration within an utterance. The developed automatic algorithm can accurately predict accented and unaccented syllables in healthy and dysarthric speech of Germanic languages like English and Dutch comparable in accentuation patterns. A cross-population study validates the detailed set of acoustic descriptors of accent production, which shows high reliability. In addition, it provides an objective description of the strategies used for accentuation across different severities of the speech impairment. The introduced speech technology provides the speech therapist with an objective and automatic measure of sentence accent, supporting the understanding of atypical prosody production and helping make informed clinical decisions and select more tailored therapy approaches.

Samenvatting en conclusies

Dysartrie is een neurogene motorische spraakstoornis die de spraakproductie beïnvloedt als gevolg van zwakke, langzame, onnauwkeurige en ongecoördineerde bewegingen van de spraakmusculatuur (Enderby, 2013; Duffy, 2019). Dysfunctie van een of meer van de subsystemen die betrokken zijn bij de spraakproductie (ademhaling, fonatie, resonantie, articulatie en prosodie) kan de algehele spraakverstaanbaarheid in gevaar brengen. Onnauwkeurige articulatie en prosodische stoornissen worden gerapporteerd voor elk type van dysartrie; daarom worden ze beschouwd als perceptuele kenmerken (Tjaden, 2007; Weismer, 2007; Darley et al., 1969, 1975; Duffy, 2019). Eerder onderzoek toonde aan dat deze twee dimensies van spraak (articulatie en prosodie) aanzienlijk bijdragen tot de algehele verstaanbaarheid in dysartrische spraak (De Bodt et al., 2002). Volwassenen met dysartrie worden vaak geconfronteerd met sociale, psychologische en dagelijkse communicatieproblemen, die hun welzijn negatief beïnvloeden. Daarom is de toegang tot een vroege diagnose en therapie noodzakelijk. Gedurende tientallen jaren zijn akoestische analyses gebruikt voor objectieve evaluaties van spraakstoornissen, wat geleid heeft tot nieuwe wetenschappelijke en technische inzichten. Gezien de nadelige effecten van een gestoorde articulatie en prosodie op communicatie evenals de levenskwaliteit, is het algemene doel van dit proefschrift om bij te dragen tot de klinische zorg en het welzijn van patiënten met dysartrie door de ontwikkeling van signaalverwerkingstechnieken en spraaktechnologie in het algemeen. Dit onderzoek vergroot de bestaande kennis over gedragsmatige behandelingen van articulatie bij deze populatie en breidt het begrip van prosodische mechanismen en strategieën uit. Om klinici en patiënten te voorzien van objectieve en automatische beoordelingen en therapie-instrumenten, werden verschillende onderzoeksvragen beantwoord. De belangrijkste resultaten worden hier verder samengevat.

Articulatie

Articulatorische onnauwkeurigheid wordt beschouwd als een belangrijk kenmerk van dysartrie (Tjaden, 2007), wat wordt weerspiegeld door perceptuele kenmerken zoals onregelmatige articulatorische vervormingen, vervorming van klinkers en verlengde fonemen (Duffy, 2019). Gestoorde articulatorische bewegingen gaan samen met een verminderd akoestisch contrast voor medeklinkers en klinkers, wat leidt tot verminderde verstaanbaarheid (Tjaden, 2007; Tykalova et al., 2017). De impact van dysartrie op articulatorische bewegingen en akoestische outcomes is, in het algemeen, vergelijkbaar, zelfs wanneer de neurologische basis verschilt

tussen verschillende types (Tjaden, 2007). In de meeste gevallen vergemakkelijkt spraakrevalidatie het herstel van articulatorische vaardigheden. Algemeen wordt erkend dat voor het verbeteren van de spraakvaardigheid spreken nodig is, wat betekent dat voor de meeste patiënten spraak- in plaats van niet-spraaktaken de focus van de behandelingen moet zijn. Als de patiënt nog over het neurale en musculaire potentieel beschikt om de spraakfunctie te verbeteren, kan een geschikte therapie dat proces vergemakkelijken. Een belangrijk kenmerk van boosttherapieën is intensiteit, een van de belangrijkste principes van motorisch leren en neuroplasticiteit, die algemeen wordt erkend als de sleutel voor logopedie (Rosenbek & Jones 2009; Kaipa, 2016; Duffy, 2019). Intensiteit kan worden bereikt via de frequentie van de behandeling, herhalingen binnen sessies, of het vereisen van grotere kracht, inspanning, of nauwkeurigheid tijdens motorische taken.

Gedragmatige behandeling van articulatie bij patiënten met dysartrie bestaat voornamelijk uit indirecte strategieën waarvan positieve effecten op het spraakverstaan zijn aangetoond. Niettemin wijzen sommige studies op het risico dat het focussen op compenseren het proces van neurale reorganisatie om specifieke stoornissen te verminderen kan tegengaan (Dobkin & Thompson, 2000). Bovendien zijn er aanwijzingen dat directe behandeling van articulatie de moeite waard is. Op dit moment hebben slechts een paar studies motorische leerprincipes gecombineerd met een segmentale benadering van de traditionele articulatietherapie. Daarom is de evidentie over de korte-termijn effecten van directe en intensieve articulatietherapie op het segmentale niveau van de spraak eerder beperkt.

Het eerste doel van dit onderzoek was het onderzoeken van de effectiviteit van “boost articulation therapy” (BArT) op het spraakverstaan bij patiënten met chronische of progressieve dysartrie en het effect van de ernst van de dysartrie op het resultaat. Voor **onderzoeksvraag 1** (hoofdstuk 2) werden de haalbaarheid en effectiviteit van een intensieve articulatietherapie bij patiënten met dysartrie geanalyseerd voor alle ernstniveaus. De intensieve en directe articulatorische therapieprogramma's die in deze eerste studie zijn ontwikkeld en toegepast, beogen de stoornis te verminderen in plaats van te compenseren. De set van oefeningen (articulatorische oefeningen en minimale paren) en de trainingmethoden ontworpen en gebruikt in deze studie waren gestructureerd op basis van de algemene principes van motorisch leren voor neurorevalidatie.

Na vijf therapie sessies werden significante toenames in verstaanbaarheid waargenomen voor drie verschillende spreektaken, op foneem niveau (NSVO), in automatische sequenties en zelfs

op zinsniveau (NSVO-Z). Bovendien werd een positief effect van BAiT aangetoond in elke ernstgroep (mild, matig, en ernstig) in de bovengenoemde taken. De akoestische analyse versterkte ook de perceptuele bevindingen. FCR analyseert de formant frequenties van klinkerarticulatie. De resultaten voor en na de behandeling toonden aan dat de FCR waarden een positieve tendens vertoonden en goed correleerden met het spraakverstaan in deze studie. Deze akoestische analyse documenteerde het positieve therapeutische effect van de BAiT in de uitbreiding van de klinkerruimte. De uitkomsten van deze studie tonen de effectiviteit aan van de BAiT aanpak gericht op het segmentale niveau van de spraak. De resultaten bevestigen dat deze directe en intensieve behandeling het spraakverstaan op verschillende niveaus van ernst van de dysartrie in korte tijd succesvol verbetert, terwijl alle beschikbare residuele motorische vaardigheden worden benut en ontwikkeld bij personen met chronische of progressieve dysartrie. Bijgevolg kan het beschouwd worden als een geschikte benadering in de behandeling van patiënten met chronische of progressieve dysartrie.

In aanvulling op de bovengenoemde resultaten, werden pathologische spraakgegevens verzameld tijdens de articulatietherapie sessies. Dit leverde een nieuw corpus van pathologische spraak op, dat bruikbaar is voor de verdere ontwikkeling en evaluatie van automatische therapie- en beoordelingsinstrumenten.

De eerste onderzoeksresultaten leiden tot het tweede doel van dit proefschrift, namelijk het evalueren van de haalbaarheid (ontwerp en ontwikkeling) van een Virtuele Articulatie Therapeut (VAT) die intensieve articulatietraining van patiënten met dysartrie ondersteunt en het valideren van het systeem door eindgebruikers. Dit werd behandeld in (hoofdstuk 3 & hoofdstuk 4) en onderverdeeld in drie verschillende onderzoeksvragen. **Onderzoeksvraag 2**, de modificaties in bestaande algoritmen die nodig zijn voor een nauwkeurige en betrouwbare fonologische foutdetectie bij patiënten met dysartrie; **onderzoeksvraag 3**, de haalbaarheid van een VAT systeem en de aanvaardbaarheid, bruikbaarheid en interactie van eindgebruikers ermee en tenslotte **onderzoeksvraag 4**, de ontwikkeling van een automatische score van de mate van foneemdistortie bij volwassenen met dysartrie.

Wetenschappelijk en klinisch bewijs toont aan dat het verbeteren van articulatorische vaardigheden intensieve en frequente therapie vereist (Duffy, 2019; Rosenbek & Jones, 2009). Daarnaast is er steeds meer bewijs dat de inhoud van logopedie moet voldoen aan de principes van motorisch leren (Duffy, 2019). Belangrijke elementen van motorisch leren in klinische neurorevalidatie zijn intensieve behandeling, repeterende oefenen en sensorische feedback

(Kleim et al., 2003; Garvey et al., 2007; Kleim & Jones, 2008; Maas et al., 2008). Het is algemeen aanvaard dat een hogere therapiefrequentie kan leiden tot betere uiteindelijke prestaties (Dobkin et al., 2000). Bovendien suggereert uitgebreid onderzoek in het logopedische domein dat het aanbieden van grote hoeveelheden oefening over een kortere periode kan leiden tot betere resultaten/uitkomsten voor volwassenen met communicatiestoornissen (Bhogal et al., 2003; Fox et al., 2006). De huidige behandelingen van articulatie beperken zich echter voornamelijk in tijd tot de interactieve sessies in aanwezigheid van de logopedist.

Technologieën voor virtuele therapie zijn niet helemaal nieuw. Automatische systemen die inspelen op de behoeften van personen met dysartrie zijn echter schaars. Het idee van de introductie van een virtuele therapeut in de logopedie bestaat al enige tijd, maar het werd nog niet in de dagelijkse patiëntenzorg geïntroduceerd. Voor zover wij weten, is er geen publiek beschikbare virtuele articulatiETOOL die BArT van adequate feedback voorziet, zeker niet voor Nederlandstalige proefpersonen met articulatietekorten. De tweede studie van dit proefschrift (hoofdstuk 3) evalueert de haalbaarheid van een VAT programma en onderzoekt de aanvaardbaarheid, bruikbaarheid en gebruikersinteractie. De computer-gebaseerde logopedische aanpak die in deze studie ontwikkeld en toegepast wordt, is bedoeld ter ondersteuning van intensieve articulatietraining voor patiënten met dysartrie. Dit virtuele therapie programma richt zich alleen op die personen met dysartrie die voldoende cognitieve, linguïstische, motorische en sensorische (auditieve en visuele) vaardigheden hebben om te profiteren van logopedie (Weismer, 2007). De VAT biedt de mogelijkheid van een geïndividualiseerd en op maat gemaakt therapieprogramma, met een uitgebreide database van oefeningen, visuele en auditieve modellen van de doeluitspraken, die adequate feedback geven op basis van automatische akoestische analyse van het spraaksignaal, en ingebouwd in een patiëntvriendelijke gebruikersinterface.

Het geïmplementeerde algoritme om de patiënt van feedback te voorzien, maakt gebruik van state-of-the-art neurale netwerken en het is gebaseerd op bestaande modellen (Vásquez-Correa et al., 2019). De modellen werden geselecteerd vanwege hun eerder aangetoonde nauwkeurige prestaties bij de evaluatie van de ernst van dysartrie (Orozco-Aroyave et al., 2020; Miller et al., 2020). De oorspronkelijke modellen waren ontworpen voor de Spaanse taal; ook waren de klinkerkenmerken meer vertegenwoordigd. Daarom werden de modellen verfijnd en uitgebreid. Ze werden opnieuw getraind met behulp van Nederlandse taalspecifieke fonologische kenmerken (plaats en wijze van articulatie en stemhebbende kenmerken) op

gezonde spraak en uitgebreid voor de betrouwbare karakterisering van medeklinkers. Het nieuw getrainde algoritme extraheert de fonologische posterior waarschijnlijkheden uit het akoestische signaal, en het wordt gebruikt om meer specifieke fonologische fouten te identificeren die aanwezig zijn tijdens de articulatietraining van proefpersonen met dysartrie.

Er werd een hoge nauwkeurigheid van de prestaties van de akoestische modellen bereikt, wat bijdraagt aan adequate automatische feedback van de productie van uitspraken. De gedetailleerde informatie die door de akoestische modellen wordt geleverd is over het algemeen moeilijk tot onmogelijk te detecteren en kwantificeren door het menselijk oor. Bijgevolg stelt de automatische feedback de patiënten in staat nauwkeuriger te werken aan de verbetering van de articulatorische bewegingen.

De VAT voorziet in de behoefte aan een toegankelijk therapieprogramma. Na twee sessies interactie met het systeem evalueerden patiënten met lichte tot matige dysartrie algemene aspecten van de virtuele therapeut, zoals onder andere bruikbaarheid, operationaliteit, layout, oefeningen en feedback. Over het algemeen waren alle deelnemers optimistisch over deze nieuwe therapiebenadering. De visuele feedback werd aantrekkelijk, duidelijk en gemakkelijk te interpreteren gevonden; niettemin toonden zij belangstelling voor het toevoegen van aanvullende auditieve feedback. De oefeningen werden adequaat, doelgericht, goed gestructureerd en voldoende in aantal bevonden.

De in deze studie ontworpen en ontwikkelde computer-gebaseerde interventie werd goed geaccepteerd door de eindgebruikers, die de mogelijkheid van een onafhankelijk spraaktrainingsinstrument zeer op prijs stelden. Daarom kan geconcludeerd worden dat de automatische BArT de tijdsbeperking van face-to-face traditionele logopedie kan ondervangen. Bovendien biedt het patiënten de mogelijkheid om intensiever en vaker articulatietherapie te volgen in hun thuisomgeving.

In de huidige context van de ongekende sanitaire crisis (COVID-19 pandemie) waarin de nood aan innovatieve gezondheidszorg werd benadrukt, kan de VAT bijdragen tot het welzijn van al die mensen die getroffen zijn door dysartrie, waarvan de meerderheid bejaard is en een hoog risico op besmetting heeft.

Een verdere verbetering van de automatische feedback van de VAT, richtte de laatste studie over dit onderzoeksthema zich op het ontwikkelen en evalueren van een objectieve score van articulatorische vervorming (hoofdstuk 4). Het is algemeen erkend dat binnen de verschillende articulatorische fouttypes in dysartrie, spraakklankdisortie het meest predominant is in

vergelijking met substituties, omissies of addities (Johns & Darley, 1970; Yorkston & Beukelman, 1980; Tjaden, 2007; Kirshner, 2021). Afwijkingen in de productie van de klankspecifieke kenmerken met betrekking tot de manier en plaats van articulatie of intonatiekenmerken kunnen bijdragen aan de waargenomen vervorming van de spraakklanken bij dysartrie. Daarom wordt het ontwikkelen van een nieuw model voor het objectief schatten van de mate van foneemdistortie van dysartrische spraak als zeer klinisch relevant beschouwd. Het nieuw geïmplementeerde algoritme extraheert fonologische posterior waarschijnlijkheden uit het spraaksignaal met behulp van de modellen die eerder zijn besproken in de tweede studie van dit proefschrift. Bovendien worden de berekende fonologische kenmerken omgezet in een set van 15 fonologische log-likelihood ratio (PLLR) kenmerken die worden beschouwd als een goede representatie van de prestaties van de spreker. Op basis van de PLLR kenmerken werden verschillende voorspellingsmodellen getraind op pathologische spraak. De evaluatie van de prestaties van de modellen toont aan dat een foneem-onafhankelijke ensemble classifier - subspace KNN- een betrouwbare en objectieve score mogelijk maakt van de mate van vervorming op foneemniveau in dysartrische spraak (van licht tot ernstig vervormde klanken). Het nieuwe model kan de mate van vervorming voorspellen met een algemene nauwkeurigheid van 73.5%. Verder onderzoek is nodig om de prestaties van het algoritme te verfijnen. Het huidige model wordt echter voldoende betrouwbaar geacht om te worden geïmplementeerd als onderdeel van de automatische feedback in de VAT.

Prosodie

Prosodie, bekend als suprasegmentele kenmerken van spraak, weerspiegelt betekenisvolle variaties in toonhoogte, luidheid, lengte en pauze tussen woorden en zinnen. Focus is een van de communicatieve functies van prosodie die wordt bereikt door het plaatsen van accenten in een uiting en is verantwoordelijk voor het benadrukken van belangrijke informatie. De beoordeling van prosodische communicatieve functies in dysartrische spraak is op de een of andere manier controversieel en uitdagend vanwege de inconsistenties gerelateerd aan gestoorde prosodie (Peppé, 2009). Akoestische analyse van het spraaksignaal is een niet-invasief en effectief objectief meetinstrument voor de beoordeling van prosodie dat ook nuttig kan zijn voor de karakterisering van een specifiek type stoornis of voor het monitoren van de progressie en de effecten van een therapeutische interventie. De huidige stand van de techniek met betrekking tot de productie van zinsaccenten in dysartrische spraak is gebaseerd op perceptuele analyse. Echter, een objectieve beoordeling van deze prosodische functie kan een grondig begrip geven van de prosodische strategieën die gebruikt worden door patiënten met

dysartrie, en het kan een meer gedetailleerde beschrijving bieden van perceptueel-gebaseerde kenmerken vanuit een akoestisch perspectief. Daarom is het noodzakelijk om geschikte objectieve maten te ontwikkelen die auditieve perceptuele evaluaties ondersteunen. Dit zou ook het ontwerpen van meer gepersonaliseerde therapie methoden vergemakkelijken.

Het derde en laatste doel van dit proefschrift was het identificeren van relevante akoestische kenmerken die classificatie en objectieve karakterisering van zinsaccentproductie mogelijk maken voor gezonde en dysartrische sprekers van het Nederlands, en het valideren van de methodologie over verschillende sprekerspopulaties variërend in het type en de ernst van hun spraakstoornissen en gesproken taal. Dit doel werd opgesplitst in twee verschillende onderzoeksvragen. Ten eerste, **onderzoeksvraag 5** richt zich op de identificatie van de akoestische kenmerken en prosodische strategieën die worden gebruikt door gezonde sprekers en sprekers met dysartrie om zinsaccents te produceren. Dit doel werd behandeld in hoofdstuk 5. Eerdere studies in normale spraak die akoestische kenmerken gebruiken om de productie van zinsaccents te karakteriseren zijn van grote waarde. Daarentegen is onderzoek naar de akoestische kenmerken van prosodie in pathologische spraak eerder schaars; een literatuuroverzicht over de karakterisering en beoordeling van atypische prosodie toont een nood aan meer onderzoek in dit domein (Diehl & Paul, 2009; Hargrove, Anderson & Jones, 2009; Peppé, 2009). Een adequate objectieve benadering vereist specifiek ontworpen methoden die rekening houden met, bijvoorbeeld, afwezigheid van stem, gebrek aan articulatorische herkenningspunten, en lage intensiteit, naast andere afwijkende kenmerken die vaak worden waargenomen bij deze populatie.

Als resultaat van onze studie werd een nieuwe set van relevante akoestische kenmerken, gecorreleerd met zinsaccent, gedetecteerd bij Nederlandse moedertaalsprekers. Deze kenmerken omvatten waarden van de fundamentele frequentie (F_0), intensiteit, en duur binnen een lettergreep, evenals de verschillen tussen de waarden van de doelletergreep met de waarden van de voorafgaande lettergreep en ook de verschillen met de mediaanwaarden van de volledige uiting. Lineaire discriminant analyse werd toegepast om de dimensie van de karakteristieken te reduceren en relevante akoestische karakteristieken te selecteren met een efficiënte kracht om syllabe accentuatie te voorspellen. De geselecteerde kenmerken zijn ingebed in een automatisch algoritme dat de objectieve en akoestische analyse van het spraaksignaal uitvoert en een zeer betrouwbare classificatie biedt tussen geaccentueerde en niet-geaccentueerde syllaben binnen een uiting. De kwantitatieve maatstaven afgeleid uit de akoestische analyse worden ook gebruikt om de verschillende patronen van dysartrische spraak

objectief te karakteriseren en te onderscheiden van de gezonde spraak in de productie van zinsaccenten. De waargenomen mechanismen van accentproductie in de groep van sprekers met dysartrie zijn gerelateerd aan dezelfde strategieën gevonden in de gezonde groep. Desondanks tonen de resultaten aan dat, hoewel beide groepen een aantal gemeenschappelijke kenmerken gebruiken, ze significant verschillen ($p < 0.01$) in de manier waarop ze een perceptueel merkbaar/ prominent accent bereiken. Terwijl gezonde sprekers meer gebruik maken van frequentieveranderingen met gelijktijdige intensiteitsverhogingen binnen de doelletergreep (F0&Int), maken sprekers met dysartrie meer gebruik van F0-verschillen tussen de doelletergreep en de vorige lettergreep (dF0max). Ze vertrouwen ook op intensiteitsveranderingen met de rest van de zin als een compenserende strategie, en/of gebruiken vaak duur-gerelateerde kenmerken wanneer de F0-veranderingen voor hen moeilijk uit te voeren zijn. Bijgevolg konden we aantonen dat patiënten met dysartrie nog steeds enige controle hebben over F0, maar strategisch compenseren voor hun verminderde vermogen om F0 te beheersen door gebruik te maken van intensiteit en temporele kenmerken.

Uit deze studie kunnen we concluderen dat de ontwikkelde set van akoestische maatstaven nauwkeurig syllaben met accenten kan voorspellen binnen gezonde en gestoorde spraakuitingen. Bovendien kan de productie van zinsaccenten adequaat en objectief beschreven worden door de geïntroduceerde akoestische kenmerken. Dit laatste maakt een betere beschrijving en begrip mogelijk van verschillende accentstrategieën bij gezonde en dysartrische sprekers. Deze kennis stelt therapeuten in staat om interventiemethoden te ontwikkelen of aan te passen voor een meer gepersonaliseerde revalidatie van het zinsaccent.

De geselecteerde akoestische parameters werden gevalideerd door middel van een cross-validatie studie in een groep van Nederlandse en Engelse sprekers met uiteenlopende ernstniveaus van dysartrie (**onderzoeksvraag 6**, hoofdstuk 6). Achtenvijftig deelnemers werden in totaal geanalyseerd. De toonhoogte, luidheid en duur veranderingen -die sprekers in staat stellen om essentiële delen van hun uiting te benadrukken- werden gerepresenteerd door tien akoestische descriptoren gerelateerd aan F0, intensiteit, en duur. Een lineaire combinatie van deze meest prominente parameters werd verkregen door middel van discriminantanalyse voor de efficiënte en automatische voorspelling van zinsaccent. Deze vergelijking (of discriminant functie) voorspelt accuraat geaccentueerde en ongeaccentueerde lettergrepen in gezonde en spraakgestoorde sprekers, in overeenstemming met de perceptuele indrukken. Het automatische algoritme toont accurate resultaten in beide dysartrische populaties, met 82.8%

en 91.9% correct geïdentificeerde geaccentueerde doelsyllaben voor respectievelijk Nederlands en Engels.

Daarnaast werd een meer gedetailleerde analyse uitgevoerd van de impact van de ernst van de dysartrie tijdens accentproductie, waarbij verschillen werden aangetoond in de gebruikte strategieën bij milde, matige of ernstige niveaus van dysartrie. Dit is een belangrijke stap in de richting van een beter begrip van de aard van de tekortkoming. De geanalyseerde data laten zien dat het vermogen om essentiële informatie in een zin te accentueren niet samenhangt met de algehele ernst van de dysartrie, aangezien zelfs sprekers met een ernstige vorm van dysartrie deze taak effectief uitvoeren. De verschillende sprekersgroepen vertoonden echter duidelijke verschillen in de manier waarop akoestische prosodische kenmerken worden gemanipuleerd. De sprekers met milde dysartrie vertonen een tendens naar normaliteit, en gebruiken vergelijkbare strategieën als de (gezonde) controlegroep, i.e., F0 veranderingen binnen de doellettergreep, samen met een toename in de intensiteit (F0&Int) en het frequentiecontrast tussen de doellettergreep en de voorafgaande lettergreep (dF0max). De sprekers met matige dysartrie gebruiken extra compenserende strategieën om het accent over te brengen. Zij lijken intensiteitsveranderingen toe te passen ten opzichte van de hele zin (IntM). Anderzijds vertoonden de ernstig getroffen deelnemers een verminderd vermogen om F0 te controleren, hoewel ze voornamelijk intensiteit (Int en IntM) gebruikten om te compenseren en een effectieve accentplaatsing in een uiting te bereiken. Daarom kunnen we concluderen dat de geselecteerde akoestische parameters het potentieel hebben om de ernst van dysartrie weer te geven. De automatische evaluatie vertoont enkele fouten bij de classificatie, wat typisch is voor de analyse van pathologische spraak. Niettemin stellen wij dat de zogenaamde fouten misschien geen analysefouten weerspiegelen maar aanvullende kenmerken van dysartrische spraakprestatie die verder onderzoek behoeven.

De objectieve analyse in deze studie werpt meer licht op de mate waarin de ernst van dysartrie de individuele prosodische kenmerken kan beïnvloeden. Deze studie draagt bij tot de ontwikkeling van alternatieve beoordelingsprocedures met betrouwbare, precieze en snelle kwantitatieve resultaten, die biases als gevolg van subjectiviteit verminderen. De automatische evaluatie van accentplaatsing tijdens spraakvalidatie legt de basis voor een meer natuurlijke manier van evaluatie tijdens continue spraak, en biedt zo een grotere face validity aan de verkregen informatie van ontregelde spraak.

Conclusies

De bevindingen van dit proefschrift dragen bij aan de vooruitgang in spraaktechnologie voor de klinische zorg van patiënten met dysartrie. De resultaten van de studies vergroten ons inzicht over de evaluatie en behandeling van articulatie en voegen een nieuwe dimensie toe aan de beoordeling en het begrip van prosodische mechanismen en strategieën. Bovendien zijn er belangrijke stappen gezet in de richting van een meer toegankelijke en individueel gerichte logopedie, met toevoeging van de mogelijkheid om patiënten op afstand en autonoom te revalideren.

Wat articulatie betreft, is een klinisch waardevolle reeks oefeningen ontwikkeld voor directe en intensieve therapie volgens de principes van motorisch leren voor spraakrevalidatie. De oefeningen bestaan uit articulatorische oefeningen en minimale paren, beide essentieel voor motorisch leren. Ook is een uitgebreide en hiërarchisch gestructureerde trainingsmethode voor articulatie ontworpen. De intensieve articulatietherapie op basis van deze methodologie is haalbaar en effectief gebleken voor het verbeteren van het spraakverstaan bij personen met chronische of progressieve dysartrie. Zowel de methodologie als de oefenstof zijn later opgenomen in de VAT, een aanvullende op technologie gebaseerde interventie die patiënten in staat stelt alleen of onder toezicht van een verzorger te werken, waardoor intensieve oefening als uitbreiding van face-to-face therapie mogelijk wordt. Hoewel dit nieuwe therapie-instrument nog enige verdere verfijning behoeft, zijn er meerdere nieuwigheden in het ontwerp en de implementatie van de VAT: 1) modellering van de doeluitspraak door middel van een zorgvuldig ontworpen database met audiovisueel materiaal, inclusief duidelijke mondbewegingen (frontaal en lateraal) en het benadrukken van specifieke kenmerken van het doelfoneem/de doeluitspraak; 2) het geven van adequate en relevante feedback met betrekking tot de nauwkeurigheid van het doelfoneem en inzicht in de specifieke fouten van articulatorische bewegingen tijdens de productie, gebaseerd op akoestische algoritmen; 3) op maat gemaakte en gebruiksvriendelijke interface, geschikt voor patiënten met hersenletsel; 4) het aanbieden van een goed gestructureerd en hiërarchisch pakket van oefeningen, gebaseerd op de principes van motorisch leren. De VAT biedt een duidelijke toepasbaarheid in de medische behandeling van patiënten met dysartrie, wordt goed aanvaard door eindgebruikers en heeft een toegevoegde waarde voor de huidige Vlaamse gezondheidszorgsituatie. Een andere nieuwigheid van dit proefschrift is gerelateerd aan de articulatiebeoordeling voor automatische feedback. Hiervoor werd een foneemonafhankelijk voorspellingsmodel

ontwikkeld en geëvalueerd, dat een betrouwbare schatting van de mate van vervorming op foneemniveau in dysartrische spraak mogelijk maakt.

Wat prosodie betreft, werd een nieuwe akoestisch-gebaseerde multidimensionele benadering ontwikkeld voor de objectieve beoordeling en meer uitgebreide karakterisering van zinsaccent in atypische prosodie van sprekers met dysartrie. De klinisch bruikbare set van nieuw gedetecteerde akoestische kenmerken die correleren met accent, combineert verschillende maten van F0, intensiteit en duur binnen een uiting. Het ontwikkelde automatische algoritme kan accuraat geaccentueerde en ongeaccentueerde syllaben voorspellen in gezonde en dysartrische spraak van Germaanse talen zoals Engels en Nederlands, vergelijkbaar in accentuatiepatronen. Een cross-populatie studie valideert de gedetailleerde set van akoestische descriptoren van accentproductie, die een hoge betrouwbaarheid vertoont. Bovendien levert het een objectieve beschrijving op van de strategieën die gebruikt worden voor accentuering bij verschillende ernst van de spraakstoornis. De geïntroduceerde spraaktechnologie biedt de spraaktherapeut een objectieve en automatische maat voor het zinsaccent, wat het begrip van atypische prosodieproductie ondersteunt en helpt bij het maken van geïnformeerde klinische beslissingen en het selecteren van meer op maat gesneden therapieën.

CHAPTER 8
SWOT analysis

SWOT – analysis articulation

Strengths

- Development of the Boost Articulation Therapy (BArT), a unique, well-structured therapy program for intensive, direct articulation therapy based on the principles of motor learning
- BArT is feasible and well-tolerated by the patients
- Both perceptual and objective outcome measures in the BArT-study
- BArT significantly improves speech intelligibility in patients with chronic and progressive dysarthria at different levels of the impairment
- Shown accuracy for the Dutch-specific phonological error detection algorithm
- Development of a patient-friendly interface of the Virtual Articulation Therapist (VAT)
- The newly developed VAT provides a set of exercises, visual and auditory modelling of target utterances and adequate feedback with accurate performance
- The visual feedback within the VAT was found to be attractive, clear and easy to interpret
- Development and validation of an automatic score of articulatory distortion at phoneme level for dysarthric speech

Weaknesses

- Relative small sample sizes
- Lack of control group in the BArT-study
- Relatively short observation period
- Preliminary results on the acceptability, usability and user interaction in the VAT

Opportunities

- Further cross-population validation of BArT (i.e. larger sample size per type and severity of dysarthria; other languages)
- Randomized-controlled trial for BArT
- Investigating the long-term and generalization effects of BArT
- Investigating the cost-effectiveness of BArT
- The VAT addresses the need for an accessible program granting patients the opportunity to train their articulatory skills more intensively and frequently
- Adding auditory and visual indications of successful productions to the VAT
- Adding new functionalities to the VAT
- A large, well-designed study investigating the effect of VAT on speech production

Threats

- Patients do not achieve full retention and generalization of the motor skills treated with BArT
- Barriers for clinical implementation of the VAT
- Barriers to make and maintain the VAT available for patients and clinicians

SWOT – analysis prosody

Strengths

- A high number of pathological speech samples with different severity levels and with different underlying etiologies
- Innovative (newly-developed) acoustic approach: acoustic contrast not only within the syllable but also in contrast with the previous syllable and in contrast with the entire sentence
- Identification and validation in Dutch and English speaking healthy and dysarthric speakers of a clinically usable set of acoustic features for sentence accent
- The identified features are valid regardless of the severity of dysarthria
- The developed algorithm, based on the identified acoustic features for sentence accent, is able to distinguish accented and unaccented syllables in sentences and this both in English and Dutch speaking subjects
- Cross-population validation has been achieved
- Prosodic profiles reflect the severity of dysarthria

Weaknesses

- Persons with severe dysarthria are not strongly represented within the first study cohort
- Relatively small and homogeneous sample of British English speakers
- Insufficient number of subjects to investigate specific characteristics of accent for specific types of dysarthria

Opportunities

- Development of an objective assessment for sentence accent in patients with dysarthria
- The automatic tool could significantly reduce the time required to analyze prosody in clinical practice
- Development of an objective therapy tool providing automatic feedback on sentence accent production; groups of interest: persons with pathological speech (dysarthria, apraxia of speech, hearing impairment) and second language learners
- More extensive cross-population validation (larger population; larger groups/dysarthria type/ non-Germanic languages)
- Validation of the features and algorithm for more natural language production

Threats

- Barriers for implementation into clinical practice
- The sound quality of speech recordings

CHAPTER 9
Future perspectives

Speech technology plays a major active role in the clinical care of patients with dysarthria, contributing significantly to the development of assistive tools for the assessment and rehabilitation of speech disorders. This thesis represents a further step towards better clinical management of patients with dysarthria. However, new research challenges concerning prosody and articulation lie ahead of us. Possible future directions for the development of speech technology tools at the patients' care disposal will be discussed in this chapter.

Articulation

Direct and intensive treatment of articulation demonstrates intelligibility improvements at different levels in speakers with dysarthria. Obviously, these are promising results, and continued investigation is necessary. Further directions should include a randomized-controlled trial for BArT to determine indirect factors that can influence the effects of the intervention. For that purpose, we can compare the proposed BArT against traditional or standard methods of dysarthria therapy. Another direction would be a cross-population validation study of the BArT, i.e. larger sample size per type and severity of dysarthria and other languages since our study included only Dutch native speakers. Although the BArT has shown to be effective, it is essential to investigate the long-term effects and its generalization to other speech levels. We also discussed the feasibility and first steps towards a VAT. This prototype includes a package of exercises comprising articulatory drills and minimal pairs to train articulatory imprecisions. However, we believe that adding new functionalities can also benefit the end-users. Including exercises of higher linguistic levels and non-speech tasks such as breathing and strength exercises that can be appropriate to improve imprecisions due to reduced respiratory support or velopharyngeal insufficiency. Additionally, some patients can also benefit from indirect approaches to improve articulation. Therefore, including in the VAT exercises to slow down the speech rate, increase the intensity and/or accentuate specifically targeted syllables also have the potential to alter articulatory behaviour in convenient ways. This type of exercise would also be supported by visual modelling and requires the design and development of new therapy material. Further improvements of the VAT also include adding auditory and visual feedback of successful acoustic productions; steps in this direction are currently being taken. We are also interested in a large, well-designed study evaluating the therapeutic effects of the VAT on the accuracy of speech production, comparing outcome measures of intelligibility between computerized and face-to-face traditional therapy. Additionally, expanding the acoustic models of the VAT to other languages would make it

more robust and usable in a larger population. We will communicate and promote the VAT in the near future through professional organizations of speech therapists and patient groups.

Prosody

The innovative acoustic approach developed in this thesis for automatic detection of sentence accent in speakers with dysarthria has advanced our knowledge of prosodic features and possible accent strategies and has offered a viable solution for an objective assessment of this task. Further directions in this domain include fine-tuning the acoustic features to improve system performance, to validate the acoustic features and algorithm in a more natural language production, where the analysis can go beyond the traditional focus/sentence tasks, is of high clinical importance. Additionally, a more extensive cross-population validation with a larger population, larger groups of dysarthria type and non-Germanic languages deserve further investigation. Finally, accent has an important role when considering treatment approaches for prosodic skills. Therefore, it seems appealing to develop an objective therapy tool that provides practice (hierarchical exercises) and automatic feedback on sentence accent production; the groups of interest are persons with pathological speech such as dysarthria and apraxia of speech hearing impairment and second language learners.

In conclusion, this thesis provides answers and solutions in the field of speech technology in pathological speech, but opens at the same time new research goals that suppose continued investigations.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AD	Articulatory drill
ALS	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
ASR	Automatic speech recognition
AUC	Area under the ROC curve
BArT	Boost articulation therapy
BT	Brain tumour
CA	Cerebellar ataxia
CATRIS	Computerized assessment and treatment of rate, intonation, and stress corpus
CGN	Spoken Dutch Corpus
CI	Confidence interval
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease
CV	Consonant -vowel
CV	Cross-validation
dB	Decibels
DIA	Dutch phoneme intelligibility assessment
DSL	Dysarthria severity levels
EMG	Electromyography
EPG	Electropalatography
F0	Fundamental frequency
FA	Friedreich's ataxia
FCR	Formant centralization ratio
FNR	False Negative Rates
GOP	Goodness of Pronunciation
GPR	Gaussian process regression
GRNN	Gated recurrent neural networks
GRU	Gated recurrent units
HCP	Healthy control participants
Hz	Hertz
ICC	Intraclass correlation coefficient

IPA	International phonetic alphabet
KNN	k-nearest neighbour
KR	Knowledge of results
LDA	Linear discriminant analysis
LMN	Lower motor neuron
LSVT	Lee Silverman voice treatment program
MAP	Moderately affected participants
MoCa	Montreal cognitive assessment test
MP	Minimal pairs
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
MS	Multiple sclerosis
ms	Milliseconds
N or n	Number
NSVO	Nederlandstalig Spraakverstaanbaarheidsonderzoek
NSVO-Z	Nederlandstalig Spraakverstaanbaarheidsonderzoek - Zinsniveau
PD	Parkinson's disease
PLLR	Phonological log-likelihood ratio
PML	Principles of motor learning
PPT	Phonetic placement therapy
R^2	Coefficient of determination
RMSE	Root mean squared error
RNNs	Recurrent neural networks
ROC	Receiver operating characteristic curve
SAP	Severely affected participants
SCA	Spinocerebellar ataxia
SD or Std	Standard deviation
sEMG	Surface electromyography
SHI	Speech handicap index
SLP	Speech-language pathologists
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
ST	Semitones
SVM	Support vector machine
TBI	Traumatic brain injury

TIA	Transient ischemic attack
TPR	True Positive Rates
UMN	Upper motor neuron
UUMN	Unilateral upper motor neuron
VAS	Visual analogue scales
VAT	Virtual articulation therapist
VC	Vowel -consonant

Applied questionnaire

Use and operation	Program and layout
<p>The program is user-friendly The program can be used independently The program provides clear instructions It is clear how to select a target sound It is clear how to play, pause, and stop the instructions about the target sound production It is clear how to select levels and exercises It is clear how to go to a previous or next exercise It is clear how you can listen to your pronunciation I would use the program daily at home</p>	<p>The home screen is attractive The visual support for target sound production is clear The visual support for target sound production is attractive The size of the buttons is adequate/ sufficient. The font is clear The font size is adequate/ sufficient The computer screen size is adequate I would recommend the program</p>
Exercises	Feedback
<p>The exercises are clear The type of exercise is useful The number of exercises per target sound is sufficient The degree of difficulty of the exercises matches my ability</p>	<p>The feedback is attractive The feedback is clear The feedback is easy to interpret The feedback is useful The feedback is motivating The feedback ensures that my articulation improves</p>
Use of Multimedia	
<p>I use the internet regularly I have one or more devices for multimedia (computer, smartphone, tablet, etc.) I use multimedia for relaxation/entertainment I use multimedia for work I use multimedia to search for things/information</p>	

Comments and suggestions:

Regression models' performance

Regression Model Type	b		y		d		f		fi		j		k		l		m		n	
	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²
<i>Linear Regression Models</i>																				
Linear	2.13	-0.46	1.79	0.23	1.6	0.24	1.01	0.11	2.12	0	1.11	0.01	2.13	-0.12	1.45	0.04	1.81	0.05	1.18	0.29
Robust Linear	2.19	-0.54	1.91	0.13	1.65	0.19	1.07	0.01	2.15	-0.03	1.21	-0.19	2.1	-0.09	1.59	-0.15	1.88	-0.02	1.48	-0.12
Stepwise Linear	5.33	-8.12	1.81	0.22	1.65	0.19	1.05	0.04	2.24	-0.12	1.31	-0.39	2.38	-0.4	1.46	0.03	1.86	-0.01	1.17	0.3
<i>Regression Trees</i>																				
Fine Tree	2.05	-0.35	2.01	0.04	1.98	-0.16	1.26	-0.39	2.55	-0.45	1.17	-0.11	2.38	-0.4	1.73	-0.36	2.1	-0.29	1.43	-0.04
Medium Tree	1.94	-0.21	1.91	0.13	1.81	0.03	1.14	-0.13	2.3	-0.18	1.02	0.16	2.22	-0.21	1.57	-0.13	1.9	-0.05	1.3	0.13
Coarse Tree	1.76	0	1.82	0.21	1.69	0.15	1.03	0.07	2.06	0.05	1.06	0.09	2.14	-0.13	1.49	-0.01	1.8	0.06	1.25	0.19
<i>Support Vector Machines</i>																				
Linear SVM	1.93	-0.2	1.89	0.14	1.67	0.17	1.04	0.05	2.11	0.01	1.17	-0.1	2.21	-0.2	1.57	-0.12	1.91	-0.06	1.29	0.14
Quadratic SVM	2.12	-0.44	1.85	0.19	1.68	0.16	1.06	0.03	2.17	-0.05	1.2	-0.17	2.16	-0.15	1.47	0.01	1.87	-0.02	1.15	0.32
Cubic SVM	3.32	-2.55	2.13	-0.08	1.72	0.12	1.24	-0.33	3.75	-2.13	1.29	-0.34	2.43	-0.46	1.51	-0.04	2.3	-0.53	1.23	0.22
Fine Gaussian SVM	1.74	0.02	1.95	0.1	1.8	0.04	1.06	0.02	2.13	-0.02	1.15	-0.06	2.06	-0.05	1.49	-0.02	1.84	0.01	1.38	0.02
Medium Gaussian SVM	1.92	-0.19	1.77	0.25	1.66	0.19	1.04	0.06	2.07	0.05	1.1	0.02	2.12	-0.11	1.47	0.01	1.8	0.05	1.21	0.25
Coarse Gaussian SVM	1.8	-0.05	1.93	0.11	1.7	0.14	1.05	0.05	2.1	0.01	1.16	-0.08	2.2	-0.2	1.56	-0.11	1.91	-0.06	1.32	0.11
<i>Ensembles of Trees</i>																				
Boosted Trees	1.92	-0.19	1.73	0.29	1.64	0.21	1.02	0.09	2.17	-0.05	1.09	0.04	2.17	-0.16	1.4	0.1	1.83	0.03	1.2	0.26
Bagged Trees	1.89	-0.15	1.76	0.26	1.65	0.19	1.02	0.1	2.02	0.09	1.06	0.1	2.11	-0.1	1.44	0.06	1.77	0.09	1.2	0.26
<i>Gaussian Process Regression Models</i>																				
Squared Exponential GPR	1.76	0	1.69	0.32	1.63	0.22	1.04	0.05	2.06	0.06	1.04	0.13	2.04	-0.03	1.39	0.12	1.73	0.12	1.16	0.31
Matern 5/2 GPR	1.76	0	1.68	0.33	1.63	0.21	1.04	0.06	2.05	0.06	1.04	0.13	2.03	-0.02	1.39	0.12	1.72	0.14	1.14	0.33
Exponential GPR	1.76	0	1.66	0.34	1.63	0.21	1.03	0.08	2.06	0.06	1.02	0.17	2.02	-0.01	1.39	0.12	1.71	0.15	1.12	0.35

Rational Quadratic GPR	1.76	0	1.69	0.32	1.63	0.21	1.05	0.04	2.06	0.06	1.05	0.11	2.04	-0.03	1.4	0.1	1.73	0.12	1.14	0.33
	q		p		r		s		j		t		v		w		x		z	
Regression Model Type	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE	R ²										
<i>Linear Regression Models</i>																				
Linear	4.13	-3.44	2.68	0.19	1.85	0.29	1.38	0.42	1.76	0.09	2.6	0.24	1.45	0.52	0.95	0.07	1.41	0.18	1.29	0.28
Robust Linear	4.12	-3.43	2.68	0.18	1.88	0.27	1.41	0.4	1.85	0	2.61	0.24	2.25	-0.16	1.04	-0.13	1.54	0.03	1.43	0.11
Stepwise Linear	4.34	-3.91	2.93	0.03	1.85	0.29	1.4	0.4	2.2	-0.42	2.66	0.2	1.29	0.62	0.94	0.08	1.44	0.15	1.38	0.17
<i>Regression Trees</i>																				
Fine Tree	2.4	-0.5	3.16	-0.14	2.3	-0.1	1.55	0.26	1.82	0.03	3.22	-0.16	1.52	0.47	1.16	-0.39	1.63	-0.1	1.66	-0.19
Medium Tree	1.96	0	2.7	0.13	2.02	0.16	1.44	0.36	1.6	0.24	2.88	0.07	1.44	0.52	1.02	-0.08	1.49	0.08	1.36	0.2
Coarse Tree	1.96	0	2.7	0.13	1.91	0.24	1.4	0.4	1.85	0	2.74	0.16	1.56	0.45	0.99	-0.01	1.42	0.17	1.28	0.29
<i>Support Vector Machines</i>																				
Linear SVM	2.04	-0.09	2.7	0.13	1.89	0.26	1.39	0.41	1.59	0.26	2.67	0.2	1.7	0.34	1.02	-0.09	1.48	0.1	1.35	0.22
Quadratic SVM	1.84	0.12	2.89	0.05	1.91	0.25	1.46	0.35	1.61	0.23	2.63	0.22	1.32	0.6	0.99	-0.03	1.44	0.15	1.36	0.19
Cubic SVM	2.51	-0.65	3.83	-0.66	2.15	0.04	2.09	-0.33	3.81	-3.24	2.84	0.09	1.29	0.62	0.99	-0.01	1.65	-0.13	1.71	-0.26
Fine Gaussian SVM	1.95	0.01	2.86	0.07	2.04	0.14	1.51	0.3	1.76	0.1	2.77	0.14	1.74	0.31	1	-0.04	1.57	-0.02	1.53	-0.01
Medium Gaussian SVM	1.85	0.11	2.69	0.18	1.84	0.3	1.31	0.47	1.58	0.27	2.51	0.29	1.43	0.53	0.99	-0.02	1.43	0.16	1.29	0.28
Coarse Gaussian SVM	1.94	0.02	2.79	0.12	1.9	0.26	1.37	0.43	1.57	0.27	2.69	0.19	1.93	0.15	1.02	-0.08	1.51	0.06	1.35	0.22
<i>Ensembles of Trees</i>																				
Boosted Trees	2.3	-0.38	2.53	0.28	1.84	0.3	1.31	0.48	1.61	0.24	2.52	0.29	1.3	0.61	0.95	0.07	1.42	0.17	1.33	0.24
Bagged Trees	2.05	-0.1	2.71	0.17	1.83	0.31	1.32	0.46	1.67	0.18	2.56	0.26	1.35	0.58	0.94	0.09	1.38	0.22	1.31	0.26
<i>Gaussian Process Regression Models</i>																				
Squared Exponential GPR	1.96	0	2.74	0.15	1.82	0.32	1.38	0.42	1.51	0.33	2.47	0.31	1.21	0.66	0.93	0.11	1.4	0.19	1.33	0.23
Matern 5/2 GPR	1.96	0	2.72	0.16	1.81	0.33	1.36	0.44	1.51	0.33	2.48	0.31	1.21	0.67	0.92	0.11	1.39	0.2	1.32	0.25
Exponential GPR	1.96	0	2.68	0.18	1.77	0.35	1.31	0.47	1.51	0.33	2.48	0.31	1.2	0.67	0.92	0.12	1.37	0.22	1.28	0.29
Rational Quadratic GPR	1.96	0	2.68	0.19	1.79	0.33	1.33	0.46	1.51	0.33	2.48	0.31	1.21	0.66	0.93	0.11	1.4	0.19	1.32	0.25

CURRICULUM VITAE

Viviana Mendoza Ramos was born in Cabaiguán (Cuba) in 1991. In 2014, she obtained a Biomedical Engineering degree at the Central University “Marta Abreu” of Las Villas (Cuba), with a thesis entitled “Implementation and application of morphological Granulometric functions for microscopy cell image classification” (Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Juan V. Lorenzo Ginori).

From 2014 to 2016, she worked as an Instructor and Scientific Researcher at the University of Sancti Spíritus “José Martí Pérez” (Cuba) and at the Central University “Marta Abreu” of Las Villas (Cuba).

From 2016 to 2018, she worked as a Principal Specialist in Electromedicine at the Center for Clinical Engineering and Electromedicine (Santa Clara, Cuba).

In 2018, she started working as a Scientific Collaborator at the University Hospital of Antwerp (Belgium) as part of the TAPAS project (Training Network on Automatic Processing of Pathological Speech), a Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Innovative Training Network European Training Network (MSCA-ITN-ETN) project that aims to transform the well being of people with speech and communication disabilities.

In 2019, she officially started her PhD-program at the University of Antwerp, supervised by Prof. Dr. Gwen Van Nuffelen and Prof. Dr. Marc De Bodt. In 2021, she received a scholarship from the University of Antwerp to accomplish her doctoral thesis. Her main research interests were focused on dysarthric speech processing and speech technology for the automated assessment and treatment of articulatory insufficiencies and prosodic disorders. The present dissertation is the result of her research.

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